

CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY –
THEORY TO PRACTICE.

CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY AS A BRAND
IMAGE OR CONTRIBUTION TO SOCIETY

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Dedication

This dissertation is dedicated to my family who has always been my source of encouragement during my study. I dedicate this work to my parents who taught me how to work and be honest; and to my brother who always encouraged me all the time. I also dedicate this work to people who work on making the world better with the help of CSR programmes, showing the audience how everyone can make the world better and equal. Finally, to my supervisors and friends, great appreciation goes to you for your insights and moral support that contributed towards this work. You will always be a part of my work in ways that will last a lifetime.

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List of Figures

Figure 1: Research Hypotheses..... 21

Figure 2: History of CSR 32

Figure 3: CSR and nonfinancial organisational performance (NFOP) of for-profit public and private enterprises in Yemen 61

Figure 4: Theoretical Framework 76

Figure 5: Carroll’s Pyramid of CSR 90

Figure 6: Conceptual Framework 99

Figure 7: Summary of Theories 102

Figure 8: The Research Honeycomb Structure 105

Figure 9: Participants’ Educational Qualifications 167

Figure 10: Age of the Participants 168

Figure 11: Effect of CSR Activities on Quality of Products and Services 169

Figure 12: Participants’ Awareness About Favourite Retail Brand’s History of Operation 169

Figure 13: Impact of Brand History on Purchasing Decisions 170

Figure 14: Participant’s Opinion Regarding Brands CSR Committee on the Board..... 171

Figure 15: Existence of Transparent and Effective Monitoring Mechanisms 172

Figure 16: Basis of Choosing Favourite Brands 173

Figure 17: Most Effective CSR Activities 174

Figure 18: Effect of CSR on Consumer Attitude Toward the Brand..... 175

Figure 19: Participants’ Willingness to Pay Extra For Retailer that Guarantees Good Work
Conditions and Fair Wages to Factory Workers 176

Figure 20: Aspects that Make a Business Accountable 177

Figure 21: Most Important Reasons for Companies to Engage in CSR Activities..... 178

Figure 22: Common CSR Activities 179

List of Tables

Table 1: Demographic of the Participants 161

Table 2: Respondents’ Awareness About CSR 164

Table 3: CSR Influence on Purchasing Pattern..... 165

Table 4: Descriptive statistics of items of CSR relationship with people (general public) 180

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics of Brand Image / Purchasing Pattern Items 181

Table 6: Descriptive Statistics of Items of CSR - Financial Performance..... 182

Table 7: Descriptive Statistics of CSR-Management 184

Table 8: KMO and Bartlett’s Test 186

Table 9: Principal Component Analysis 187

Table 10: KMO and Bartlett’s Test 188

Table 11: Items’ Principal Components Analysis (PCA) 189

Table 12: KMO and Bartlett’s Test 190

Table 13: Principal Components Analysis of Items 191

Table 14: KMO and Bartlett’s Test 192

Table 15: Component Matrix of items of society 192

Table 16: KMO and Bartlett’s Test 193

Table 17: PCA of items of Management 194

Table 18: Correlation between CSR Policies (CSR 1) and Brand Image / Purchasing Pattern,
Management / Laws, Financial Performance and Society 196

Table 19: Correlation between CSR Activities (CSR 2) and Brand Image / Purchasing Pattern,
Management / Laws, Financial Performance and Society 199

Table 20: Tests of Normality 202

Table 21: Multi-collinearity Coefficient of CSR Policies 203

Table 22: Relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR 1) and Business Image, Stakeholders (Management/Laws), Financial Performance and Society 204

Table 23: Regression Coefficients 205

Table 24: Relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility Policies (CSR 2) and Business Image, Stakeholders (Management / Laws), Financial Performance and Society 206

Table 25: Regression Coefficients 207

Table 26: Relationship Between Identified CSR Policies with Consumer Purchase Behaviour 208

Table 27: Regression Coefficients 208

Table 28: Are CSR policies and activities a competitive advantage effective in adding value to the business? 209

Table 29: Regression Coefficients 209

Table 30: H1 CSR practises employed by garment organisations in South Asian countries have a favourable impact on the sector. 210

Table 31: H2 CSR policies have a positive effect on the brand image, company reputation, and profitability of garment-producing organisations in South Asia. 211

Table 32: H3 CSR activities positively impact customer purchase patterns in garment-producing organisations in South Asia. 212

Table 33: H4 The CSR activities undertaken by the organisations in the garment industry in South Asia have improved labour conditions 213

Abstract

Background. CSR is now recognised as a business model that is critical for the success of a company's image and positive financial performance. In this context, the understanding and implementation of CSR have reaffirmed its importance for companies as business demands grow and escalate to respond to societal responsibilities in South Asia. An aspect to be investigated by the research is the impact that sustainable business practises have on performance in today's dynamic world economy. To fill this research gap, the study sought to give a better understanding of companies' ethical practises and sustainability among garment firms in South Asian countries.

Aim: The objective of the study is to review CSR policies within South Asian business organisations, their effects on society, and the relationship between ethical CSR and its contributions towards the improvement of business image and profitability. This research aims to contribute to understanding the mediating function of CSR in business sustainability.

Methodology: This research used both quantitative and qualitative instruments of data collection to advance the study. For qualitative data, semi-structured interviews were applied to gain detailed information from the primary stakeholders, whereas questionnaires contained quantitative data. Thematic and statistical methods were used to analyse qualitative and quantitative data respectively.

Findings: The study found that good CSR policies improve organisational image and income in South Asian firms. Those firms that conduct ethical CSR activities that include revolutionising labour conditions and supporting social well-being, are perceived positively by the public and consumers. In addition, CSR activities have social relevance, as they enhance the community and solve social problems. Nevertheless, this study has highlighted some drawbacks, including

shallow implementation of CSR policies and practises which may produce negative returns and erode society's trust in firms that are not implementing CSR properly in the long term.

Recommendations: Businesses should pay attention to CSR activities addressing labour and community concerns to gain sustainable trust in the firms' sustainability policies. In addition, CSR strategies should be closely connected to the business frameworks to increase profit and positive customer relations, rather than having only symbolic actions for change.

Keywords: Brand image, CSR, profitability, performance, garment businesses, South Asian countries

Table of Contents

Dedication	1
Acknowledgement	2
List of Figures	3
List of Tables	5
Abstract	7
Chapter 1: Introduction	14
<i>1.1 Background Context</i>	14
<i>1.2 Aims and Objectives</i>	20
1.2.1 Research Aims	20
1.2.2 Research Objectives	20
<i>1.3 Research Hypotheses</i>	20
<i>1.4 Research Questions</i>	22
<i>1.5 Justification and Significance of the Research</i>	22
<i>1.6 Introduction to the Theoretical Framework</i>	24
<i>1.7 Introduction to the Research Methodology</i>	25
<i>1.8 Summary and Conclusion</i>	25
Chapter 2: Literature Review	27
2.1 Introduction.....	27
2.2 Definition of CSR	27
2.3 History and Evolution of CSR.....	30
2.4 Impact of CSR on Business.....	34
2.4.1 Impact of CSR on brand image	34

2.4.2 Impact of CSR on purchasing pattern.....	38
2.5 <i>CSR and Social Contribution</i>	40
2.6 <i>CSR Strategies Deployed by Global Organisations</i>	44
2.7 <i>CSR Strategies in South Asian Organisations</i>	53
2.7.1 CSR policies used by Indian companies.....	53
2.7.2 CSR activities of organisations in Bangladesh.....	58
2.7.3 CSR activities of organisations in Pakistan	60
2.8 <i>Advantages and Challenges in CSR Strategies' Implementation</i>	61
2.8.1 Advantages of CSR policies implementation.....	61
2.8.2 Challenges in CSR policies' implementation.....	66
2.9 <i>Literature Gaps</i>	71
2.10 <i>Summary and Conclusion</i>	72
Chapter 3: Theoretical and Conceptual Framework	75
3.1 <i>Introduction</i>	75
3.2 <i>Coercive Isomorphism</i>	76
3.3 <i>Mimetic Isomorphism</i>	79
3.4 <i>Institutional Isomorphism</i>	80
3.4 <i>Normative Isomorphism</i>	82
3.5 <i>Stakeholder Theory of CSR</i>	84
3.6 <i>Legitimacy Theory</i>	86
3.7 <i>Elkington's Triple Bottom Line</i>	88
3.8 <i>Carroll's CSR</i>	89
3.9 <i>Linking the Theories to the Research</i>	92

3.10 Conceptual Framework..... 93

3.11 Summary of the Theoretical and Conceptual Framework 100

Chapter 4: Research Methodology..... 104

4.1. Introduction..... 104

4.2. Research Philosophy..... 106

 4.2.1 Ontology 107

 4.2.2 Epistemology 107

 4.2.3 Research values or axiology 108

 4.2.4 Selecting the philosophy..... 109

4.3. Research Approach 112

 4.3.1 Inductive approach 112

 4.3.2 Deductive approach 112

 4.3.3 Abductive approach..... 113

4.4 Research Strategy..... 114

4.5 Research Design..... 118

 4.5.1 Exploratory research design 118

 4.5.2 Explanatory research design..... 119

 4.5.3 Descriptive research design 120

 4.5.4 Cross-sectional study 121

 4.5.5 Experimental study design..... 122

4.6 Population and Sampling for Survey and Interview 122

 4.6.1 Population Selection..... 123

 4.6.2 Sampling Process..... 125

4.7 Data Collection Process.....	127
4.8 Data Analysis Techniques	133
4.8.1 Descriptive statistics	134
4.8.2 Inferential statistics.....	135
4.8.3 Thematic analysis	137
4.9 Validity and Reliability.....	139
4.10 Pilot Study	140
4.11 Ethical Considerations.....	142
4.12 Summary and Conclusion	143
Chapter 5: Data Analysis and Interpretation.....	145
5.1 Introduction.....	145
5.2 Qualitative Results	146
5.2.1 Impact of CSR on competitive advantage and value added on business.....	146
5.2.2 Key influences of CSR policies and activities on business image, stakeholders, and society	151
5.2.3 Ways CSR helps in developing society and community	156
5.3 Quantitative Results	159
5.3.1 Frequency analysis	161
5.3.2 Descriptive Sstatistics.....	166
5.3.2 Validity of items	185
5.3.4 Correlation analysis	194
5.3.5 Testing the normality assumption.....	201
5.3.6 Regression analysis.....	203

5.3.7 Hypothesis assessment	210
5.4 Chapter Summary and Conclusion	213
Chapter 6 : Discussion	215
6.1 Introduction.....	215
6.2 The Current CSR Applied Policies.....	215
6.3 Corporate Social Responsibility Initiatives in the Society.....	218
6.4 The Relationship Between CSR and Profitability Through Assessing Customer Purchase Patterns	222
6.5 CSR Policies and Business Profitability and Brand Image	227
6.6 Chapter Summary.....	229
Chapter 7: Summary, discussion, recommendation and Conclusion.....	231
7.1. Introduction.....	231
7.2. Research Summary and Major Findings.....	231
7.3. Recommendations.....	241
7.4. Implications of the Findings.....	243
7.5. Limitation of the Research	244
7.6. Conclusion.....	246
References.....	248
Appendices.....	286

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Background Context

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) strategies are all-encompassing plans companies use to establish, execute, and enhance their social responsibility initiatives. These tactics offer several advantages, including boosting employee morale and establishing a sense of community among management and employees. Davis (1973) defines CSR as considering problems outside the company's restricted financial, technological, and legal requirements. Crifo and Forget (2014) define CSR as firms' activities that go beyond the law in integrating social, ethical, environmental, and consumer concerns into operations to generate stakeholder and shareholder value. Blowfield (2005) define CSR as a concept that encompasses business responsibilities to the environment, stakeholders, and larger society. Carroll (1979) Carroll (1979) defines CSR as the social responsibility of a business that encompasses legal, ethical, philanthropic, and economic expectations that society has of organisations at a given time. The definitions provide the fundamental ideologies, including the nature of activities undertaken. Overall, CSR encompasses activities that address legal, economic, ethical, and philanthropic expectations. The motivation to undertake CSR activities arose from their positive impact on stakeholders and shareholder value. The current research adopts Carroll's definition of CSR (1979), which encompasses critical responsibilities, including ethical, economic, legal, and philanthropic. The definition depicts the evolution of CSR from voluntary activities undertaken by firms to mandatory duties to society in legal, ethical, philanthropic, and economic aspects.

The company's management makes the CSR model. Through the implementation of CSR, businesses can be aware of how they affect the social, economic, and environmental parts of society (Singh and Misra, 2021). Supporting society through philanthropy and charitable

activities helps businesses to build brand value (Jeong and Cho, 2020). CSR events help employees to be productive and connected to the rest of the world.

CSR activities create a positive impact on society by addressing social and environmental concerns. By adopting sustainable business models, businesses can impact the community's welfare and foster the protection of the environment and the welfare of the people in an organisation, thus stabilising future generations (Lee, Zhang and Abitbol, 2019). For example, people choose cosmetics and skincare brands, reducing interest in animal products. CSR activities potentially improve an organisation's brand value and customer base. Ghosh (2018) stated that CSR activities improve a company's public image and awareness. CSR increases brand recognition, proving its concern for society and the environment. When organisations participate in activities presumably aimed at enhancing societal well-being or solving community problems, the brand is positively perceived by consumers, leading to trust, brand loyalty, and other positive attitudes towards the firm. Boğan and Dedeoğlu (2019) argued that CSR activities influence customers' attitudes toward the brand. Moreover, employees instead work for a company with a good reputation and a solid commitment to human rights.

Significant research on CSR in developing and emerging economies identified its positive impact on financial performance (Sameer, 2021; Ngo and Thanh, 2023; Saeed, Alnori and Yaqoob, 2023). However, minimal studies have been undertaken in Bangladesh despite the importance of CSR activities to society. Latapí Agudelo, Jóhannsdóttir and Davídsdóttir (2019) highlight the need to comprehend the underlying socioeconomic factors that influence the success of CSR initiatives. CSR means business awareness of social responsibility for the good of society (Yu et al., 2021). CSR is a company's commitment to sustainable activities that

improve employees' lives, families, communities, and society (Marco-Lajara et al., 2022). As a result of globalisation, many South Asian organisations are embracing CSR practices.

Different CSR policies are implemented in South Asian companies, including TCS, Reliance Industries, and Indian Oil Corporation. Woerkom and Zeijl-Rozema (2017) argue that although CSR activities are popular, they are not effectively implemented in countries like India, Bangladesh, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, and South Asian countries. Medium-sized enterprises in South Asia lack appropriate CSR policies (Shah et al., 2017). As a result, it is difficult for many MSEs in South Asia to effectively implement adequate CSR policy, sometimes because of restrictions on funds and the absence of official pledges (Shah et al., 2017). For instance, companies in Bangladesh's textile sector may have a simple code of conduct regarding CSR; however, they may not have/indexed programmes and have long-term planning on CSR strategy. In India, some manufacturing-based SMEs have CSR policies only in the documentary formal compliance sense, responding to the lowest legal expectations and not going beyond that in contributing to social concerns (Farooq et al., 2019). Likewise, mid-sized Sri Lankan firms in the food processing sector may have occasionally made charitable and local sponsorships lack steady, genuine attempts towards sustainability and better employment standards. This gap implies a dire need for enhanced CSR frameworks in South Asian MSEs to support the delivery of effective and enduring CSR impact on society and the environment. The world's best-known brands, like Bon Marche (UK), The Children's Place (USA), El Corte Inglés (Spain), Kik (Germany), Mango (Spain), Taxman (Denmark), and Primark (UK/Ireland), have their factories in India, Sri Lanka, and Bangladesh (Baena 2018). In the last few decades, outsourcing production to countries like India and Bangladesh has become a common way to reduce costs and improve manufacturing strategies. Major Western fashion companies have moved factories to South Asian countries like

India and Bangladesh because of low wages and cheap materials (Shah et al., 2017). However, there is a concern regarding ways brands develop their environmental strategies to foster social growth.

CSR has a negative effect on developing countries like India, Sri Lanka, and Bangladesh because government regulatory agencies are ineffective. Evidence suggests that governments in developing countries lack commitment when implementing CSR policies and laws (Farooq et al., 2019). Compared globally, Bangladesh is much lower on the CSR index due to weak laws and a scarcity of resources for enforcing CSR (Farooq et al., 2019). Although legal requirements for CSR vary depending on the industry, the general overall picture demonstrates poor compliance and insufficient attempts at strategic integration, showing that many companies in Bangladesh fail to provide a satisfactory realisation of CSR on the global level (Farooq et al., 2019). As a result of globalisation, multinational companies are likely to stay involved in developing countries. In this regard, CSR must be addressed in developing countries (Kyove et al., 2021). Companies execute CSR by sending their employees out in matching T-shirts to paint walls or write checks to a museum, while other countries where the products are manufactured deal with issues like inadequate education opportunities and healthcare. The CSR initiatives capture the customers' attention but may fail to solve real social problems in the community (Nickerson, 2022). The garment industry in South Asian countries does not give enough attention to the safety, security, and retention of workers. Low-cost labourers are the main reason Zara, Mango, and international clothing companies have set up factories in South Asia (Alamgir and Banerjee, 2019). Since there are more workers than jobs available, organisations have more bargaining power than their employees. People work for companies that lack a good work health and safety plan, or other benefits expected in most developed countries. The Rana Plaza building collapsed

on 24 April 2013 at the Savar Industrial Belt near Dhaka, Bangladesh, one of the major industrial disasters in the world, killing more than a thousand garment workers and leaving hundreds injured (Alamgir and Banerjee, 2019). The incident revealed concerns about building construction and authorities, safety standards, and the absence of regard for employees in the textile industry of Bangladesh (Kyove et al., 2021). This calamity underscored the necessity of higher standards of safety measures and enhanced responsibility on the contributors and on the multinational firms which supply the products created in factories positioned in developing countries.

CSR is about how an organisation affects people and society. CSR transcends the evaluation of financial performance, stressing ethics, sustainable development, and work with society (Perry, 2012). People retain and trust those businesses that include them as they seek to solve societal and ecological problems while supporting business goals. Before the accident at Rana Plaza, lack of effective CSR was in the ready-made clothing industry. In Bangladesh, findings from safety inspection exercises are not given the required attention to mitigate potential accidents. Ever since, the ready-made garment (RMG) industry has received much attention from different facets because there was no intense safety audit and minimal safety management from the plant owner and safety manager (Alamgir and Banerjee, 2019). This negligence has left many citizens working under dangerous conditions and environments, poor fire safety measures, and weak factory structures (Alamgir and Banerjee, 2019). Most importantly, improper inspection frequencies, lack of enforcement of building codes and failure to provide necessary training place workers at higher risk since inadequate watchfulness leads to worker-endangering outcomes such as the Rana Plaza tragedy.

Bangladesh's RMG sector experiences a high number of workplace-related deaths mainly because of substandard buildings, poor emergency evacuations and crowded working environments. Working environments in factories are likely to dilapidate structures without practical fire exits and health catastrophe plans, posing high potential threats to lives (Kim, Saito and Avvari, 2020). A minimum of 230 garment factory fire incidents occurred between 2006 and 2009, which claimed 414 factory workers' lives, emphasising the sense of security issues (Nickerson, 2022). Altogether, in 2010, 21 different accidents took the lives of 79 workers (Farooq et al., 2019). These figures reveal severe problems of regulatory negligence, poor compliance with safety requirements, and minimal penal responsibility of factory proprietors (White, Nielsen and Valentini, 2017). Conditions like these compromise workers' lives and the industry's sustainability, although to promote the need for safety audits, compliance with international safety standards, and stricter regulatory compliance to protect the lives of Bangladesh garment workers (Farooq et al., 2019). Interest in the topic has grown since the 1990s, as proven by the number of garment factories (Perry, Wood and Fernie, 2015). CSR is the company's ongoing commitment to helping the economy grow while improving the quality of care for workers and families, the local community, and society (Alamgir and Banerjee, 2019). The goal of the research is to explore ways CSR is used as a brand-image strategy and giving back to society. Even though many organisations are starting up CSR initiatives in South Asian countries, they do not focus on helping people in South Asian countries which host their factories (Kim, Saito and Avvari, 2020). Even though medium-sized to large businesses engage in CSR activities, the primary goal is to get consumers' attention and increase their profit margins. These companies are not focused on improving society through their CSR activities. This research

examines the effectiveness of real-life CSR policies that international and local garment manufacturers in South Asia have implemented.

1.2 Aims and Objectives

1.2.1 Research Aims

The aim of the research is to assess the effectiveness of CSR policies and their impact on society. In addition, the study aims to explore ethical CSR practises that positively impact business image profitability of the south Asian business organisations.

1.2.2 Research Objectives

The key objectives of the study are as follows:

- i. To investigate current CSR-applied policies and to determine their value, effectiveness, and impact on business
- ii. To identify essential CSR policies that can positively impact business profitability and brand image.
- iii. To examine the relationship between CSR and profitability by assessing customer purchase patterns.
- iv. To investigate how CSR helps the wider community.

1.3 Research Hypotheses

The key aim of the research hypothesis is to test the study's objectives above. The research hypotheses tested in this research are:

Hypothesis 1

H₀: The current CSR policies used by the garment organisations of South Asian countries do not impose a positive impact on the industry.

H_a: The current CSR policies used by the garment organisations of South Asian countries impose a positive impact on the industry.

Hypothesis 2

H₀: The CSR policies do not impose a positive impact on the profitability and brand image of South Asian garment organisations.

H_a: The CSR policies impose a positive impact on the profitability and brand image of South Asian garment organisations.

Hypothesis 3

H₀: There exists a negative relationship between the CSR activities of South Asian Garment organisations and profitability through assessing customer purchase patterns.

H_a: There exists a positive relationship between the CSR activities of South Asian garment organisations and profitability by assessing customer purchase patterns.

Hypothesis 4

H₀: The CSR activities undertaken by organisations in the garment industry in South Asia do not improve labour conditions.

H_a: The CSR activities undertaken by organisations in the garment industry in South Asia have improved labour conditions.

The hypotheses identified are showcased in Figure 1.1 below.

Figure 1.1 Hypotheses in the research

Figure 1: Research Hypotheses

Source: (Author, 2024)

In Figure 1.1, the various hypotheses in the research are showcased, indicating the link between CSR activities and brand image, consumer purchase patterns, and benefits to sector and society.

1.4 Research Questions

The research questions of this study are as follows:

- i. Is CSR a competitive advantage, and can it add value to business?
- ii. What are the critical influences of CSR policies and activities on business image, stakeholders, and society?
- iii. Is there a proven relationship between identified CSR policies and consumer purchase behaviour?
- iv. How do CSR activities impact the community?

1.5 Justification and Significance of the Research

The rationale for undertaking the study is to bridge the research gap regarding whether garment industry firms in South Asia implement CSR policies and their impact on brand

reputation and relationships with other firms and society. While previous scholars have examined how CSR affects the reputation and brand equity of garment-producing companies in industrialised countries such as the United States, Australia, and the United Kingdom, a few studies investigated the garment-producing industry in developing South Asian countries. A few examples of studies conducted in South Asia include Nurhayati, Taylor, and Tower (2015), which showed that CSR disclosure in the Indian garment industry improved reputation and financial performance due to attracting diverse customers. When firms implement socially responsible programmes, they act out their ethical functions while winning the confidence of the consumers through their sustainable and consummate image (Nurhayati, Taylor and Tower, 2015). CSR practises enhance current practices and reveal the role of CSR policies on the brand image of garment-producing firms and their reputation. Donaghey and Reinecke (2018) highlight a need to understand the underlying ideas regarding CSR practises to ensure easy implementation. The study reveals how firms in the South Asian garment industry engage in CSR activities and benefit stakeholders and society.

The research contributes to managerial outcomes where insights are established regarding the role of CSR policies in enhancing brand reputation and consumer relationships. Managers can understand the value of engaging in CSR activities to improve employee morale and attract talent to the firm. The research informs managers about the importance of ethical operations in enhancing the reputation of their firms in the garment industry. Li, Pinto and Diabat (2020) demonstrated that CSR activities improve the reputation of the garment industry based on their contribution to environmental sustainability. As a result, the study provides insights into enhancing the working environment. The research outcomes also contribute to practice by indicating how CSR activities and policies can improve the well-being of society. Developing

countries, including India, Bangladesh, Pakistan, and Sri Lanka, face unemployment challenges and stiff worker competition. As a result, garment-producing companies exploit workers with low wages and overworking because of the high number of workers compared with the number of available jobs. The findings from the current research reveal whether garment-producing companies that engage in CSR activities influence their employee morale and protect their health.

The research is also significant to theoretical advancement, where insights are established regarding the relevant theoretical paradigms that influence companies in the garment-producing industry to engage in CSR activities. Nurhayati, Taylor and Tower (2015) identified the significance of legitimacy theory as a lens for understanding the motivation of Indian textile companies to engage in CSR activities and processes. Additionally, the findings advance the research topic concerning the relationship between CSR activities, brand reputation, and profitability. Other scholars interested in the topic can utilise the findings to understand better CSR practises and address the existing knowledge gaps. Scholars can rely on the findings as a guide to investigate the CSR activities of South Asian clothing businesses.

1.6 Introduction to the Theoretical Framework

Theoretical evidence exists for several economic, social, and industrial factors influencing brand image and company success. The situation is assessed based on a thorough theoretical comprehension of these elements. Coercive isomorphism, mimetic isomorphism, institutional isomorphism, normative isomorphism, stakeholder theory, legitimacy theory, Elkington's triple bottom line, and Carroll's CSR are acknowledged as significant ideas. The four theories of isomorphism, namely coercive isomorphism, mimetic isomorphism, institutional isomorphism, and normative isomorphism are used to reveal organisational structural forces and

conceptual notions from social and environmental viewpoints (Zahari et al., 2020). The evolution of isomorphism may result in problems that inhibit growth. Regional producers must adhere to Carroll's responsibility pyramid, which emphasises ethical, legal, economic, and charitable dimensions of accountability (Deegan et al., 2002). The stakeholder model emphasises enabling individuals harmed by a company's actions to file ethical claims with the support of stakeholders. Legitimacy theory postulates that a "social contract" exists between a firm and its target society. He coined the term "triple bottom line" to define his method for analysing company performance and consequences, focusing on the financial, human, and environmental perspectives.

1.7 Introduction to the Research Methodology

The research methodology is organised using the honeycomb model. Research philosophy is the first phase of the Honeycomb research process. The pragmatic research philosophy was used for this study. This study employs an abductive approach. Descriptive research designs are included in objective-based research designs. Data collection methods are included in the fifth step of the Honeycomb model. Primary data is gathered and used to make the findings. Interviews were conducted to collect in-depth qualitative data, which was analysed thematically to comprehend the study topic. In addition, surveys are used to collect quantitative data. A descriptive statistical approach was also used to analyse data and analyse the participants' demographic information while examining the survey data. SPSS data analysis software was used for descriptive and inferential statistics to make the data analysis accurate.

1.8 Summary and Conclusion

The background context of the current research is provided, and the core problem to be addressed is outlined. The insights revealed the lack of empirical studies examining the impact of CSR activities on the reputation and profitability of garment-producing companies in South Asia.

The importance of the research in contributing to managerial and theoretical outcomes was further underscored. The theoretical framework guiding the research was presented where fundamental CSR theories were justified. The chapter also highlighted the choice of the mixed method, which would guide the collection and analysis of data in the study.

The dissertation is structured into six chapters. The second chapter presents findings from the literature review related to different thematic topics. The third chapter details the theoretical and conceptual framework guiding the study. In the fourth chapter, research methodology is showcased, indicating the philosophical paradigm, data collection, and analysis techniques utilised. The fifth chapter details the analysis and interpretation of the data. In the sixth chapter, the findings are discussed, and the research is concluded. Recommendations for future practice are also documented.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

The focus of the chapter is to critically discuss the literature related to various topics in the study. The assessment of the literature reveals insights into the definitions of CSR and its historical evolution. The study examines the impact of CSR strategies on business and how the concept contributes to societal well-being. The adoption of CSR strategies in South Asian organisations is also examined in India, Pakistan, and Bangladesh. The discussion also evaluates the benefits of CSR implementation, and the challenges faced during the implementation process. The literature gap is presented, and a summary of core findings from within the chapter is also showcased. The literature gaps encompass the dearth of studies focused on CSR implementation in Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan. Gaps arose in the lack of empirical work examining how CSR impacted society in South Asian countries and the profitability and brand image of textile companies in South Asia. Additionally, the literature gaps encompass the limited studies evaluating how culture influences attitudes towards adopting CSR in South Asian textile companies. The gaps also concern the limited empirical work concerning how CSR activities impact society and businesses in South Asian countries.

2.2 Definition of CSR

CSR is a philosophy of management in which companies integrate social, environmental and shareholder issues into their commercial activities. CSR is how an organisation maintains a mix of financial, social, and environmental requirements (Triple Bottom line approach) whilst simultaneously meeting the expectations of shareholders and stakeholders (Varyash et al., 2020). Thus, it is important to distinguish CSR, which is characterised by charity, sponsorship, or philanthropy, as a strategic business management principle. According to Davis (1973), CSR

encompasses the consideration of problems outside the company's restricted financial, technological, and legal requirements. Carroll (1999) and Davis (1973) posit that CSR activities involve the economic, legal, ethical, and discretionary expectations of society for organisations. These insights indicate that society holds companies responsible for their CSR activities.

While CSR also plays a vital role in alleviating poverty, improving the image of a company, and strengthening its brand, the idea of CSR goes beyond. Encouraging the adoption of CSR requires understanding ways to meet their needs and capabilities that are not detrimental to their economic survival (Yadlapalli, Rahman and Gunasekaran, 2020). However, Davis (1960) argued that CSR activities were justified in companies due to their positive impact on economic gain in the long run and ensuring the social responsibility of the firms. CSR activities can enhance the performance of companies by mediating their brand image.

The TBL technique is used as a tool to review and evaluate the performance of organisations against economic, social and environmental results. It is an endeavour to align private enterprises with the objective of sustainable global development by granting them a detailed set of operational objectives rather than simply profit. An agency must be financially secure, limit its adverse consequences on the environment, and operate in accordance with community standards. TBL's approach is based on CSR programmes, a productive instrument for SMEs in developing and developed nations to help meet environmental and social expectations without hampering their competitiveness. Farrington et al. (2017) argue that CSR enables businesses to be socially responsible to stakeholders and society. CSR can take a variety of forms depending on the industry and organisation. Companies may serve society by developing CSR and philanthropic projects. By practising CSR, organisations develop awareness that they have an impact on every aspect of society, including the social, economic, and environmental aspects.

Commitment to CSR ensures that corporations work in a regular business environment and do not adversely affect people and the environment. Further, CSR activities create a strong link between workers and businesses, which eventually increases productivity. To become socially responsible, the organisation must be accountable and responsible to itself along with its stakeholders (Galant and Cadez, 2017). Thus, CSR is essentially a strategy for developing corporate image.

Different studies reveal the importance of CSR among modern companies. Wang and Sarkis (2017) highlight that Starbucks gives immense importance to CSR. Starbucks is known for its CSR initiatives, along with its commitment to sustainability and welfare, for a prolonged period. Akbari et al. (2021) concur with Wang and Sarkis (2017) by reporting that manufacturing companies are adopting CSR to enhance their innovative practices and improve financial performance. Correctly implemented CSR offers competitive advantages, which include improved access to finance and markets and higher revenues. As a result, firms realise benefits such as cost savings, enhanced efficiency, improved quality, a productive staff base, increased brand image and credibility, improved customer satisfaction, and risk-efficient managing processes. Akbari et al. (2021) added to Benites et al. (2018) by stating that the primary CSR issues handled by organisations include environmental sustainability, responsible procurement, eco-efficiency, labour standards, stakeholder participation and working conditions, staff and community relations, social justice, human rights, gender equality, good governance and initiatives to eradicate corruption. However, Su and Lu (2023) contradict Benites et al. (2018) and Akbari et al. (2021) by suggesting that CSR activities negatively impact firm value due to increased spending on non-income-generating activities. The misalignment implies that

scepticism against CSR arises from the short-term reduction of the firm revenue by investing in activities that promote non-financial benefits such as a good reputation among stakeholders.

2.3 History and Evolution of CSR

The current section elaborates on the history and evolution of CSR. Benites et al. (2018) posit that the CSR history is traced back 5000 years in the past. Around 1700 BC, in ancient Mesopotamia, King Hammurabi introduced a code in which developers, shopkeepers or farmers were punished with death for negligence or misconduct detrimental to the residents of the nation or causing significant inconvenience to local people (Benites et al., 2018). In the early ancient Roman context, CSR-like practices were realised when firms were required to levy their contribution to support the state, for instance, by providing finance for military activities (Benites et al., 2018). By the 2nd century BCE, senators were complaining about the '*societates publicanorum*' emoluments and thus discussions on their roles and obligations and shareholders (Benites et al., 2018). Benites et al. (2018) report on the shareholder activism that happened in 1622, as the company's shareholders issued brochures complaining about the negative reputation attributable to its activities on the environment. These insights implied that the shift to adopt CSR arose from the demand by stakeholders for the organisation to enhance environmental sustainability. The impacts of society and climate on industry took industrialisation into a new dimension. In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, money was spent by 'corporate paternalists' to fund projects of philanthropic. CSR was formally introduced in the 1980s and 90's, as Shell became the first organisation to introduce CSR in 1998 in Niger Delta. In the early 1990s, CSR policies were adopted in the accounting and professional service sector and became a trend for larger firms such as PwC and KPMG (Carroll, 2008). These CSR initiatives began in areas including North America and Western Europe, as various stakeholders demanded escalating

satisfaction from companies in terms of accountability, compliance, and exercising sound ethical standards (Carroll, 2008). Another socially responsible strategy observed was the implementation of environmental management, the investment in communities, and ethical governance in CSR by PwC and KPMG, which created an organisational image and increased industry standards (Carroll, 2008). Commitment towards CSR played a role in the increased adoption internationally, particularly in the professional services sector.

Industrialisation and the social effects of corporations have most recently contributed to a radically new view. According to the Corporate Watch Report (2006), CSR is a challenge to an organisation that is well-informed and trained. Thus, its implementation into business can address the challenges. CSR programmes are increasingly implemented by non-profit making organisations. Chaffee (2017) adds to the Corporate Watch Report (2006) and posits that the roots of the social dimension of corporate conduct date to modern-day Roman laws. For instance, CSR practises could be found in institutions like refuges, residences for the aged and poor, hospitals, and orphanages. The view was carried out as social enterprises by scholarly, municipal and religious institutions under English rule from the 11th-15th century. Later, advancement spread through the 16th and 17th centuries. Moreover, the 16th and 17th centuries were a time when CSR was extended to philanthropy (Carroll, 2008). A prominent example of the mindset's changing toward corporate behaviour came from Bowen in 1953. In South Asian countries, the large companies of the time centralised enormous power, and their decisions had a direct influence on society. Consequently, companies need to change their strategic decisions and consider their effects. In 1960, academics approached CSR as an answer to the new industrial society's challenges and desires. Keith Davis was a prominent example, explaining that the primary changes in society, economics and politics reflected a demand for business owners to

observe their social duty and position in society. Davis (1960) reported that business owners had a relevant social duty in human values and in economic and social responsibility, which could be related to some degree to the economic revenues of the company. Figure 2 illustrates the visual evolution of the CSR concept.

Figure 2: History of CSR

Source: Latapí Agudelo et al., 2019

In Figure 2, the historical evolution of CSR is showcased, starting from 1953 to 2018, where insights indicated the contributions of diverse scholars, including Bowen (1953), Davis (1960), and Carroll (1991). Waterhouse (2017) reports that depression occurred in the United States in 1970 due to the high inflation and low growth, accompanied by the energy crisis., which were pivotal in shaping CSR. The social revolutions of the 1960s and early 1970s led the United States federal government to make considerable strides in social and environmental regulations. In this respect, public pressure led to the establishment of regulations that aimed at protecting the environment and people (Waterhouse, 2017). For example, the Equal Protection Agency (EPA) was established in 1970 to uphold environmental policies that lead to environmental conservation- purer air, water, and ground (Waterhouse, 2017). The Law on Clean Air Act of 1970, the Law on Clean Water Act of 1972, and the Law on Endangered Species of 1973 provide an act for standard formulation for pollution control (Waterhouse, 2017). Such

policies aimed to address the issue of environmental irresponsibility and compelled firms to embrace responsible practices. Carroll (2015) and Waterhouse (2017) explained that globalisation enhanced the operations of multinational companies that confronted different market environments abroad, some with poor regulatory structures, during the 1990s. The CSR events in the 2000's are split into two parts. The first focused on the identification, extension, and application of CSR. The second focused on the strategic approach (Carroll, 2015). Porter and Mark (2011) introduced the concept of shared value development as a necessary step in the user terminal. For instance, CSR was identified as the practices of policies and operations that enhance the competitiveness of a company whilst simultaneously improving social and economic situations within the community. Shared value development focuses on the recognition and extension of ties between social and economic change. Carroll (2015) supported Porter and Mark (2011) and analysed the principles of participation and management of stakeholders, business ethics, corporate citizenship, sustainable development, and mutual value development. The study identified that the principles were all interrelated and overlapping. These ideas were integrated into CSR and were pivotal to socially responsible corporations. The insights from these studies indicated that socially responsible corporations engage in business ethics to manage the expectations of their shareholders.

2.4 Impact of CSR on Business

2.4.1 Impact of CSR on brand image

There has been increasing responsiveness to the influence of business on society and the environment, along with increasing socio-regulatory pressures. Brown (2001) states that employing workers, making money, and paying taxes is inadequate as it is now required that businesses will be accountable, answerable, and provide support to the wider society. Davis and

Frederick (1985) and Brown (2001) posit that business cannot escape from the community. Conversely, without business, the community is not able to survive. Notably, Cannon (1994) disagrees with Davis and Frederick (1985) and argues that businesses mainly focus on increasing profits, creating job opportunities, supplying to the market, increasing their advantage over competitors, and providing protection to the society in which they operate. Additionally, the conclusion by Edenkamp (2002) refutes the earlier comments by Brown (2001) since Edenkamp (2002) underscores that in the event of poor corporate behaviour, customers contemplate switching to the goods and services of another firm, speak negatively about the company to family and friends, refuse to buy its shares, decline to work there, and boycott its products. Thus, the divergent opinions on the societal role of business present a distinction in the opinion and perception of various stakeholders on the significance of business in the modern world.

CSR is an essential factor for today's businesses since it impacts a company's image and its brand within the community. Edenkamp (2002) indicate that in developing markets, a business that generates the impression of delivering quality goods that last longer while they may not be highly technological could potentially achieve a competitive advantage. Notably, Farida and Setiawan (2022) support Edenkamp (2002) by arguing that business performance and innovation mediated the association between business strategies and competitive advantages. Delivering high-quality services generated a competitive advantage for businesses. The contradiction implies that to achieve a competitive advantage, businesses need to offer new products or services at a lower price than the competitors to attract price-sensitive customers.

A company's economic and legal obligations significantly impact its corporate image. While analysing the impact of positive perceptions on CSR initiatives, Kim et al. (2020) observe that CSR initiatives improve the trust among consumers and thus improve the corporate image.

Kim et al. (2020) discussed the economic impact of CSR on brand image; in contrast, Islam (2023) discussed the ethical duty of CSR on brand image. As pointed out by Islam (2023), values-based CSR practises, including labour rights and environmental management, are critical components in creating a good image. Moreover, the positive perception of consumers is higher for brands that adhere to ethical standards (Islam, 2023). Therefore, the economic, legal, and ethical consequences of CSR lead to trust that corresponds to brand loyalty and improved word-of-mouth, thus strengthening brand equity.

Other scholars have supported empirical evidence of the positive relationship between CSR and brand image. Martínez et al. (2014) highlight the relationship between consumers' perceptions of CSR, their impressions of the brand image, and their level of brand loyalty. Similarly, Esmaeilpour and Barjoei (2016) argue that effective CSR programmes positively impact brand equity since the reputation of the company creates a positive brand image that enhances consumer perception of brand credibility and reliability. Dapi and Phiri (2015) further emphasise that CSR practises enhance brand equity, which boosts consumers' loyalty. This study is important for industries that involve branding and where brand image strongly influences consumers' purchase decisions. Khan and Fatma (2023) indicate that consumer perceptions of CSR positively influence brand trust. As a result, brand trust has a partial mediating effect on the association between CSR, brand image, and consumer word of mouth. Araújo, Pereira and Santos (2023) added to Khan and Fatma (2023) and showed that CSR positively influenced customer satisfaction through the mediating effect of brand equity and brand image. Therefore, CSR initiatives lead to improved brand equity and brand image. The current research contributes to the existing literature by exploring perspectives from South Asian textile companies.

CSR improves the consumers' attitude toward the brand, increasing trust, loyalty, and willingness to recommend the brand. CSR activities towards environmental sustainability enhance brand image, especially when the target market is made up of green consumers (Kang, Germann and Grewal, 2016). CSR is an effective way to stand out from the competition as firms target consumers who are conscientious about their choice of brands (Melo and Galan, 2011). Other benefits of CSR initiatives are also experienced in terms of the consumers' and brands' emotional connection. Carroll's (1991) pyramid of CSR revealed that those businesses which place philanthropy at the final tier are viewed as altruistic, which can enhance consumers' sentimental loyalty. These emotional bonds are essential to developing a bond with brands and consumers in the long term.

Though CSR is valuable and has certain positive effects, it is crucial to highlight that it can deteriorate the brand image if mishandled. There is a danger of being viewed as insincere or 'greenwashing,' which means that the public regards a firm as participating in CSR to signal its consumer sensitiveness without having real concern for social and environmental challenges (Laufer, 2003). When CSR is perceived by consumers as fake, it results in distrust and negative consequences to brand image (Yoon, Gürhan-Canli and Schwarz, 2006). CSR activities unrelated to a firm's business functions may prompt people to regard the firm as hypocritical. This misrelation can deteriorate the brand image and inevitably erode customers' confidence. However, the usefulness of CSR activities depends on the attitudes of consumers and the sincerity of the company's actions in terms of social responsibility. As organisations engage in the management of CSR, they must understand that meeting and addressing consumer expectations is critical in establishing a favourable brand image that boosts overall brand value.

2.4.2 Impact of CSR on purchasing pattern

CSR is popular among companies and viewed as a practice that influences consumer behaviours. The literature has addressed the influence of the concept of CSR with reference to the effect it has on consumer decisions, thus admitting a nexus between ethics and marketing. With the current awareness of the social and environmental consequences of consumers' buying decisions, CSR has great value in influencing consumers' buying behaviour. However, the effectiveness of CSR in influencing people's purchase decisions differs from one region or culture to another. The research conducted among Polish and Ukrainian consumers concluded that the influence of CSR is not the most significant factor in the consumer's choice (Marcinkowska and Sawicka, 2023). Various factors, including quality, price, other customers' feedback, warranty and repair network, are more important than CSR (Marcinkowska and Sawicka, 2023). Compared to the studies of Anastasiadou et al. (2019), Marcinkowska and Sawicka (2023) confirm that no relationship *exists* between CSR evaluation and demographic variables, although the female participants view CSR *as a more* important criterion than male participants. Although Anastasiadou et al. (2019) note the importance of CSR initiatives in influencing customer responses in the short term, Popa et al. (2022) focused on the short-term aspects associated with CSR initiatives. Notably, social media marketing has received a positive evaluation from these scholars because it was clear that their conclusions aligned with each other and further affirmed that CSR programmes affect consumer behaviours through marketing communication media such as social media.

CSR programs are also affiliated with consumer loyalty, which is a key element in consumption habits. Pérez and del Bosque (2015) affirm that CSR can create sustainable consumer relationships whereby the initiatives correspond to consumer values and beliefs.

Customers with a positive attitudinal response to a firm's CSR activities are likely to remain loyal, repurchase and engage in positive word of mouth. However, CSR impacts consumer loyalty depending on the organisational and geographic context and the target consumer population. For instance, the relationship between CSR and consumer loyalty is pronounced with industries viewed as less truthful, such as the banking and pharmaceutical sectors. When the level of trust is high among consumers, the impact CSR brings towards the loyalty of consumers may be insignificant. CSR can positively influence consumer loyalty, which is not the primary factor. According to Luo and Bhattacharya (2006), customer satisfaction and loyalty brought about by CSR activities is contingent upon the quality of the products and services. CSR initiatives are unlikely to improve consumer loyalty if the basic product does not satisfy consumer needs.

CSR directly impacts the purchase and perception of brands. Mohr, Webb and Harris (2001) indicate that consumers pay for goods from companies with social responsibility programmes. CSR can serve as a competitive advantage in highly saturated markets where customers have a wide range of options and are in search of other factors that inform their choices. However, consumer readiness to pay a premium for sustainably produced products is not conclusive. Compared to the findings of Mohr, Webb and Harris (2001), Auger et al. (2003) argue that although consumers willingly pay more for products due to CSR considerations, their counterparts have a one-dimensional view that emphasises price, quality, and convenience. CSR significantly impact consumer purchasing behaviours. Carrigan and Attalla (2001) state that the influence of CSR on purchasing behaviour might be overemphasised. Therefore, the attitude-behaviour dichotomy implies that CSR is but one among many factors that may influence consumers' choices.

2.5 CSR and Social Contribution

For corporations, CSR refers to a collaborative way to support society whilst supporting themselves throughout the process. CSR is the best strategy that can create a positive impact in the community in which the organisation works. While adopting CSR, businesses must allow customers to know about the practices. According to Wołodźko and Woźniak (2017), Walmart has been established as an innovator in environmental efforts and sustained its position of leadership in CSR within the previous few years. The role of CSR in maintaining good relations with customers is examined in the literature. Kim and Ferguson (2014) found that CSR is the best way to communicate with customers and keep them connected with the brand. There is a positive relationship between the findings of Chomvilailuk and Butcher (2018) and Kim and Ferguson (2014), as they postulate that businesses that offer consumers high-quality products and ensure effective demonstration of humanity towards the world through investing in efficient CSR activities receive goodwill from the consumers. Pallathadka and Pallathadka (2022) align with Chomvilailuk and Butcher (2018) by demonstrating that businesses that communicate CSR initiatives elicit higher generosity from their partners. The insights from the studies indicate that CSR can promote goodwill from customers and partners. Although the findings of Chomvilailuk and Butcher (2018) and Pallathadka and Pallathadka (2022) concur, Axjonow, Ernstberger and Pott (2016) contradict Pallathadka and Pallathadka (2022) and report that CSR reporting does not exert a significant impact on firm reputation when considering non-professional stakeholders, including employees and potential customers. Thus, the disclosure of CSR initiatives impacts the reputation of firms where professional stakeholders are considered.

Businesses whose primary aim is to enhance their profit margin by investing in the quality of the products and services receive less customer goodwill. Xu et al. (2022) support

Chomvilailuk and Butcher (2018) by indicating that CSR projects could be the finest method to help the planet and its people. Local and national charitable donations support businesses in the community. Companies can become involved and help advance society by implementing social actions on behalf of the organisation, such as taking part in programmes for underprivileged children and homeless care initiatives for homeless persons and refugees. According to Singhapakdi et al. (2019), organisations in the Australian food industry donate to local charities. For instance, McDonald's gives free charge food to a local organisation of homeless and to an orphanage children's home. Taylor, Vithayathil and Yim (2018) align with Singhapakdi et al. (2019) and postulate that companies must be attentive to the recyclability of materials, raise the longevity and functionality of products, use additional renewable energy at very low costs to reduce pollution and provide a contribution to the biodiversity of the country. The insights from the studies indicate that companies' focus on renewable energy sources can contribute to lower costs while improving the environment. However, Osman et al. (2022) misalign with Taylor, Vithayathil and Yim (2018) and Singhapakdi et al. (2019), who report that high initial costs in setting up renewable energy sources discourage companies from switching from fossil fuels. The contradiction implies that many companies continue to use fossil fuels as a source of power, destroying the environment.

CSR initiatives enable businesses to achieve fewer operational expenses, better income and satisfaction, increased efficiency, opportunities for recruiting and retaining brilliant employees, and encouraging investors and access funds. Walzel, Robertson and Anagnostopoulos (2018) claim that CSR is a realistic method of contributing to society. Rasche et al. (2017) align with Walzel, Robertson and Anagnostopoulos (2018) and posits CSR is a necessity for society. Sheth (2006) and Rasche et al. (2017) argue that a CSR program requires

addressing the different stakeholders' needs of the organisation and the society. Hart and Milstein (2003) discuss the idea of ecological social responsibility. The resource-based view focuses on the evidence that the organisation's resources must be uncommon, non-substitutable, important, and inimitable.

Certain businesses that are socially responsible for the environment have a competitive advantage. Markley and Davis (2007) found that the competitive advantage that businesses benefit from consists of pollution avoidance (reduction of emissions and waste), inventory management (reduction of manufacturing costs for the life cycle), and sustainability (reduction of the carbon footprint for the development and growth of company). Russo and Fouts (1997) evaluated Hart and Milstein's (2003) theory in which they investigated utilising firm-level data on environmental and financial profitability; the hypothesis was empirically evaluated. Over two years, including 243 companies, Russo and Fouts (1997) tested their hypotheses regarding the role of CSR in firms. CSR helps businesses to be green, aligned with the organic-resource-based view suggested by Hart (1995) and the findings of Russo and Fouts (1997). Businesses with rising ecological levels of performance experience a higher financial performance. The results of Hart (1995) and Russo and Fouts (1997) echoed other analyses such as Stanwick and Stanwick (1998), where research to investigate the relationship between a corporation's social organisation productivity and strategic extent, personal wealth, and ecological quality was demonstrated. The authors used summary analysis, correlation analysis and regression analysis to interpret the results, utilising specific information from the Agency for Environmental Protection (EPA), the Fortune Corporate Credibility Index, and business structures (determined by the annual sale of the company). The use of concrete data, like the one given by the EPA, in the study is the

strength of the report. CSP is influenced by a company's size, a company's financial profitability, and a company's pollution emissions.

Most of the studies examined based on environmental and stakeholder views of CSR activities seem to suggest the existence of a close partnership. When analysing the ecological and CSP research in depth, Miles and Covin (2000) found a close association between a company's responsibility obligations and policies and the views of different stakeholders (for instance, shareholders and consumers). The value of CSR to shareholders has led corporations to adhere to key company responsibility behaviour philosophies: (1) the environment protection enforcement model where businesses are required to conserve the environment, and (2) the environmental management model of strategy for the businesses. González-Gómez (2020) supports Miles and Covin (2000) and postulates that industries will develop further and impact the climate, with a global population expected to reach 7 billion by 2015. The social effect is a recent and evolving CSR-related notion. Porter and Kramer (2002:2006) align with González-Gómez (2020), in which CSR social advantages were identified. Singhapakdi et al. (2019) support the insights by Porter and Kramer (2002:2006) and posit that successful foundation-giving activities should be well communicated. The insights from the studies indicate that CSR programmes should be based on the same principle as they enable a greater social impact.

When businesses are engaged in a variety of CSR initiatives, expectations of the probability that certain measures result in either favourable internal outcomes or favourable internal outcomes. Bhattacharya and Sen (2004) and Porter and Kramer (2002: 2006) conducted a report to fully understand the consumers' perception of CSR initiatives. Customers likely notice unique CSR initiatives that set the company apart from its competitors and develop presumptions and behaviours. Further, customer expectations, corporate views, corporate

connection, and consumers' good sensations of well-being are internal results of the study. However, there are two main reasons why CSR initiatives are ineffective, as presented by Porter and Kramer (2006). Corporations should select the type of advantage that matches the sector and consider the co-dependence of business and society when choosing which CSR initiatives to endorse. Most explanations of investigators' CSR depend on four elements: ethical duty, survival, operation licenses, and credibility, which are consistent with the statements of Porter and Kramer (2006). According to the author Campbell (2007), for instance, the main reasons why companies participate in socially responsible practises are a result of strict government regulation and other external monitoring agencies. Murray and Vogel (1997) align with Campbell (2007) and discuss how the stakeholders and organisations were involved in an interchange in which the company provides the stakeholders with value and supports the company. The study's primary focus is on firms' goodwill management decisions. It focuses on the expectations and limits placed on the company by stakeholders rather than the potential outcomes of a constructive collaboration between the business and stakeholders. Numerous studies in the literature have examined the common practices used by businesses to satisfy stakeholders. However, Porter and Kramer (2006) contradicted Vos (2002) and argued that the opinions of stakeholders are significant in influencing their perception regarding the brands. The contradictions implied that conflicts among stakeholders would hinder the progress of CSR implementation.

2.6 CSR Strategies Deployed by Global Organisations

Some of the major social factors that brands are focusing on to ensure an effective CSR policy that attracts consumers and motivate employees working in the organisation are reducing carbon footprint, refining the policies of labour, charitable giving, contributing to unbiased trade,

community volunteering, implementing corporate policies that can benefit the environment and community.

In the same way that there are similar conceptions and thoughts about CSR, there are also distinct conceptions of what comprises CSR operations. Sims (2003) argues that understanding the performance of a business depends on its relationships with various shareholders, personnel, clients, and other suppliers. Leading companies take a multifaceted view of CSR. The studies by Muirhead (1999), Hall (1989), and Sims (2003) highlight a variety of activities associated with CSR, including the development of an ethical code, marketing linked to causes, philanthropy, worker volunteerism, security and preservation of the environment, and the right of workers. Currently, implementing the code's provisions is the main impact of an ethical code on CSR.

Environmental security and conservation are other well-established CSR practices. Torugsa et al. (2013) discuss the environmental factors of CSR. Brown (2001) aligns with Torugsa et al. (2013) by arguing that CSR strategy contributes to environmental sustainability. For instance, through CSR, Nissan bought eco-sustainable water-based paint for cars using money saved from recycling plastics. The costs associated with the removal of trash and waste were additionally reduced. Additionally, Brown (2001) discussed how environmentally sustainable measures taken by businesses were discovered by the Institute of Business Ethics, which culminated in benefits for the bottom line within each firm. To find ways to mitigate harmful chemicals emitted by their factories, the Dow Chemical Company hired the aid of the Natural Resources Protection Council in 1991. With these newly developed approaches, Dow invested roughly \$3.1 million in changing its plant, which enabled savings of \$5.4 million in the following year. Willamowski et al. (2018) align with Brown (2001) and considered the example of Xerox, which saved over US \$800,000 on new toners every year by converting waste toner

into new toners. With the company's 'Pollution Reduction Pays' initiative, the organisation saved 810 million dollars since the year 1975 (Willamowski et al., 2018). Brown (2001) and Willamowski et al. (2018) indicate that the integration of CSR activities in terms of business ethics enabled companies to save on costs while increasing revenue. However, Zouari-Hadiji and Chouaibi (2021) misalign with Brown (2001) and Willamowski et al. (2018) and argue that some companies were against ethical activities as managers considered them to be too expensive for their businesses. Thus, some companies are sceptical about the value of ethical CSR activities.

According to Kolk (2005), Starbucks, one of the country's most popular coffee shops in the United States, offers clients used coffee grounds that can be utilised as fertiliser for both their gardens. Starbucks does not impartially reduce costs on the bottom line, like Nissan. Essentially, CSR applied with an environmental theme such as sustainable sourcing, ethical trading, and community programmes are central at Starbucks, but these are sometimes aligned with the image and customer appeal as with lowering operating costs directly (Kolk, 2005). CSR initiatives include sourcing, providing facilities for the community, and managing piles of waste through recycling and donating used coffee granules to customers. However, the company's approach to CSR focuses on reducing operation costs, including energy use in production facilities and minimising waste for its production lines (Dyczkowska, 2015). For example, Nissan used an energy-saving smart factory in Japan that integrated automation to reduce energy and water use, which, in turn, decreased manufacturing costs (Dyczkowska, 2015). While the sustainability practises Starbucks are directly relatable to consumers, Nissan uses CSR to achieve cost savings through internal efficiency, which should further support how CSR can work towards both environmental and business advantages. Dyczkowska (2015) supports Kolk (2005) and states that in corporate plans, companies are adopting eco-friendly practices. In 1994, CSR activities

grew globally, compared to 20% in 1993, with 34% of the FTSE 100 companies generating multiple separate environmental reports (Kolk, 2005). The pattern has enhanced dramatically, and with the global warming problem, many businesses are organising extra help from government agencies and local community groups to protect the environment.

Global company Johnson & Johnson might be regarded as an excellent CSR example. Johnson & Johnson is a healthcare facility operating internationally in New Brunswick, New Jersey, in the United States of America (Chattu, 2015). Founded in 1886, the company operates in three main segments: pharmaceuticals, medical devices and self-caring and wellness products (Chattu, 2015). Delaware-based Johnson & Johnson has a diversified product portfolio that ranges from over-the-counter products, prescription drugs, surgical equipment and gadgets to body care products, baby products, skin products, sanitary products and many others (Chattu, 2015). Chattu (2015) note that the company focused on limiting its effects on the planet for 3 decades. The firm's CSR activities include utilising wind energy in the manufacturing plant and giving people access to clean water worldwide as a philanthropic exercise. Xcel Energy, the private energy supplier in the Texas Panhandle, allows a reduction in emissions while providing clean, cheap electricity options. To acquire 35% of the energy requirements of renewable sources, Xcel Energy focuses on exploring renewable energy alternatives. Bauer (2014) aligned with Chattu (2015) and highlighted the global organisation Google's CSR practices. Due to its data centre using 50% less than the worldwide average, Google has also received responsible investment (RI's) top ranking in CSR. They have also pledged over US 1 billion to green energy initiatives and have allowed other companies, through services such as Gmail, to diminish their own impact on the environment. The firm has realised a drastic improvement in Google's supply chain processes.

Coca-Cola invests in fuel-efficient, brand-new logistics, such as trucks using fuels other than petrol or diesel. Tezer and Tofighi (2021) support Bauer (2014) and point out the example of the Coca-Cola Company by highlighting its commitment to sustainable practices and demonstrating active work to reduce environmental impact and enhance operational efficiency. Coca-Cola's massive distribution vehicles emitted about 3.7 million metric tons of greenhouse gases into the environment before changing to other fuel types (Tezer and Tofighi, 2021). The emissions were high before they changed their approach to logistics and decided to both reduce their carbon footprint and increase efficiency, which was initiated around 2010 (Bauer, 2014). Following the transition, the company's aim was to minimise emissions using cleaner fuels. Ford and Stohl (2019) resonate with Tezer and Tofighi (2021) and consider the example of Ford Company in CSR activities. Ford is an automotive firm and is based in Dearborn, Michigan, USA (Tezer and Tofighi, 2021). Ford Company specialises in the automotive industry, and it mainly engages in the designing, manufacturing, sale, and after-sale services of motor vehicles and automobile parts (Tezer and Tofighi, 2021). Ford Motor Company was established in 1903, and today, it is one of the world's largest automotive manufacturers, offering a wide range of automotive products, including cars and trucks (Tezer and Tofighi, 2021). CSR activities relate to sustainability, community development, and environmental management. The optimisation of manufacturing with the help of green technologies and support of the electric vehicle market (Tezer and Tofighi, 2021). To increase fuel efficiency, Ford plans to diminish its degree of greenhouse emissions with the help of its EcoBoost engine. As per the management of the Ford Company, to ensure an effective reduction in air pollution, electrify their most popular cards. Ford Motor Company intends to offer its customers an option to switch to electric vehicles as an initiative to achieve environmental sustainability.

American Ford retailers rely on a system of solar PV and wind sails to fuel their sites, drastically decreasing their usage of the energy. Netflix Inc. is based in Los Gatos, California and is in the business of streaming media entertainment, where it provides its clients with access to a wide number of movies, TV shows and even exclusive Netflix productions through subscription (Vidyasagar, 2020). Founded in Stockholm, Sweden, Spotify is an online music streaming service that gives its customers extra subscription plans to listen to millions of songs and podcasts (Ásványi and Zsóka, 2021). Vidyasagar (2020) notes that employees and their immediate families of Netflix and Spotify are recipients of the rewards, including paid parental leave, mental health support, wellness programmes, and working conditions such as options for flexible working. Ideally, through interventions concerning the physical, psychological, social and socio-economic aspects of employees' lives, the two companies aim to achieve organisational commitment and improved efficiency. Ásványi and Zsóka (2021) resonates with Vidyasagar (2020) and posits that Pfizer utilises the term corporate citizenship. Pfizer is in New York City, in the United States of America (Ásványi and Zsóka, 2021). Pfizer is a commercial venture in the pharmaceutical manufacture and sale of medical products, including drugs, vaccines and health enhancement products (Ásványi and Zsóka, 2021). Pfizer is a company that is associated with several therapeutic areas and focuses on drugs treating cancer, cardiovascular diseases, and autoimmune diseases. One of the CSR activities of the company is Pfizer Global Health, where the company works to deliver medicines to unserved populations (Ásványi and Zsóka, 2021). Pfizer also practices environmental sustainability by reducing the emissions of greenhouse gases, the amount of water they use, and other aspects while supporting health initiatives around the world, particularly during epidemics or other disease outbreaks (Ásványi and Zsóka, 2021). Pfizer is pushing campaigns worldwide that raise awareness of non-infectious

diseases and provide health services for women and children who may not otherwise have the medications. The price drop in their vaccines for the prevention of influenza and ear infections for vulnerable groups such as refugees provides an appropriate example of Pfizer's engagement in CSR activities.

CSR of Wells Fargo entails offering programmes such as financial education, participating in community development investment, and following up on issues of environmental sustainability. Wells Fargo is based in San Francisco, California and operates in the financial services sector (García-Jiménez et al., 2017). García-Jiménez et al. (2017) support Ásványi and Zsóka (2021) and discuss that Wells Fargo contributes up to 1.5 per cent of its sales income to charitable activities. Other charitable causes that Wells Fargo sponsors include disaster relief, diversity and inclusion, and offers socio-economic responsible banking practises that enhance the lives of all clients that it serves. Additionally, they provide their staff with two paid vacation days per year to volunteer for charity. Bachnik and Szumniak-Samolej (2013) support García-Jiménez et al. (2017) and highlight examples of CSR activities by referencing the company TOMS. TOMS was established in Los Angeles, California, United States of America, and is in the footwear and apparel industry (Bachnik and Szumniak-Samolej, 2013). TOMS specialises in casual shoes and other accessories such as shoes like eyewear and bags (Bachnik and Szumniak-Samolej, 2013). The company's aim is to donate another pair of shoes for every pair of shoes sold by TOMS. TOMS has provided over 1.2 million shoes to children in need since TOMS was established in 2006 (Bachnik and Szumniak-Samolej, 2013). Such programmes have affected society in over 20 countries across Central and South America, Africa, and Asia, where children cannot even afford simple things like shoes (Bachnik and Szumniak-Samolej, 2013). TOMS has continued to advance other socially responsible initiatives covering every part

of the world, proving its worth to the community. A portion of profits from TOMS is used to support the visually impaired by donating products and their service to eye care organisations, treatments, glasses, and surgeries (García-Jiménez et al., 2017). While TOMS works on a generalised ‘for every shoe, one is donated’, which started as a shoe for children and later expanded into giving shoes for clean water, safer birth, and giving sight (García-Jiménez et al., 2017). The company also offers employment opportunities in the developing world by localising some of its products, apart from developing the economy of the country. This integrated approach of TOMS makes it possible to solve many social problems together with the aspects of business profitability and growth. Additionally, TOMS actively promote anti-bullying initiatives and helps non-governmental organisations by serving as role models for social responsibility initiatives.

Half of Bosch’s R&D budget is spent every year since 2010 on developing technology for environmental protection. The organisation has invested EUR 50 million with the help of the Bosch Energy Research Network in supporting universities and research programmes focusing on environmental problems affecting those countries or focusing on research taking place in those countries, including in the USA, India, China and Germany (Alkaabneh, 2020). This investment enhances Bosch’s environmental perspective by supporting research that tackles many challenges in the areas of renewable energy, emissions, and sustainable mobility. De Jong and Van der Meer (2017) and Alkaabneh (2020) argue that more than ten years have passed since General Electric unveiled Ecomagination. Ecomagination was introduced in 2005 by General Electric (GE), a multinational conglomerate company in the United States of America (Alkaabneh, 2020). The energy and technology sectors were under which GE initiated this program to ensure it produced environmentally sustainable technologies to solve the world’s

environmental problems (Alkaabneh, 2020). The initiative markets new products and services, including energy-saving devices, clean energy production, and water-saving technologies for bearing the cost of green shifts. The insights show that Ecomagination is the company's corporate sustainability strategy for the sale of energy. Since 2015, GE has launched the Digital Wind Farm. GE's Digital Wind Farm, introduced in 2015, is a new technological advancement in renewable power development to enhance the utilisation of wind power and lower costs for producers (Alkaabneh, 2020). Along with the digital analysis, it integrates wind turbines to control the wind farm function in real time, ensuring maximum energy production and environmental efficiency (De Jong and Van der Meer, 2017). The launch of the Digital Wind Farm is also evidence of GE's dedication to tackling high carbon sources and fostering the development of renewable energy systems as critical for attaining sustainable development objectives and delivering new value that energy companies can use to optimise profitability via enhanced efficiency. Algarni et al. (2023) align with De Jong and Van der Meer (2017) and Alkaabneh (2020) by indicating that the integration of renewable energy sources contributes to social, economic, and environmental sustainability. The insights from the studies indicate that the ethical operations of the businesses contribute to environmental protection.

Starbucks wants to diversify its workforce. Starbucks has committed itself to employing 25,000 veterans in its socially responsible initiatives by 2025 (Richey and Ponte, 2020). The recruitment initiative also seeks to recruit young people to help start-ups work by giving them their first employment. From a green perspective, Starbucks's practice of donating extra coffee grounds for composting lawns and gardens can be extended to support the UN Refugee Agency. With such a model, Starbucks can educate camps and other communities on how to enhance environmental sustainability (De Jong and Van der Meer, 2017). Starbucks promotes sustainable

development through a stock ownership scheme. Gazzola et al. (2017) reiterate De Jong and Van der Meer (2017) and report that the Fort Collins brewery generated 18% of its electricity via solar panels and wastewater and is also a leader in recycling and eco-focused. Fort Collins Brewery was in Fort Collins, Colorado, USA, and primarily focused on craft beer. The brewery began in 2003 and was known in the region for its diverse incorporation and support of the local beer scene. Amiri (2019) aligns with Gazzola et al. (2017) and discusses that with expectations of net zero carbon emissions, zero waste and a pledge to water conservation, Disney is committed to reducing its carbon footprint (Amiri, 2019). The Walt Disney Company is in Burbank, California, USA (Amiri, 2019). The Walt Disney Company is a wide communications and entertainment corporation famous for its vivid cartoons, recreational facilities, channels, including ABC and ESPN, and products (Amiri, 2019). Disney also makes live action films and has other big brands like Marvel, Star Wars, and Pixar, and for all ages (Amiri, 2019). CSR activities focused on ethical operations have ensured that Disney preserves the protection and rights of its workers, and they develop stringent foreign labour policies. Such insights indicate that Disney's companies are also involved and inspire workers to do the same in the community. However, Spellman (2014) postulates that the increased adoption of renewable energy sources by companies poses various threats, such as altering land use where large-scale projects are implemented. Society should embrace changes in land use so that various companies can implement renewable resources.

2.7 CSR Strategies in South Asian Organisations

2.7.1 CSR policies used by Indian companies

CSR has been in existence in India since the beginning of the 20th century and has been in active practice since the 1930s, the age of Industrialisation. Organisations like TATA and

BIRLA have been implementing CSR policies in their activities for social good for decades, long before CSR became a common cause (Kumari et al., 2020). TATA Group and Birla Group are both some of the largest and most reputed conglomerates in India, and they are involved in several sectors (Chung and Jiang, 2017). TATA group is headed by Mr Cyrus Mistry and has a wide business interest spread across more than 100 companies in sectors like steel, automobile, IT, Telecommunications, consumer products, hospitality and service, and healthcare (Kumari et al., 2020). Some of the flagship companies of Tata Group are Tata Steel, Tata Motors, and Tata Consultancy Services. TCS is the best in its class. On the other hand, the Birla group originated in the early twentieth century by Ghanshyam Das Birla and mainly deals with textiles, cement, aluminium, and financial services (Chung and Jiang, 2017). Some corporates associated with Birla include the Aditya Birla Group, which has made a considerable impact in investment and contribution to some industries, including the fashion retail industries, cement industries, and telecommunication industries. Both have sponsored programmes related to CSR in terms of community welfare, education, and health, making them good corporate citizens within India. Despite having good real-life examples, CSR is in a very nascent stage in the nation. Chung and Jiang (2017) and Kumari et al. (2020) reveal that CSR's business case is gaining momentum; these firms understand initiatives that are good for employees, their culture, wellbeing, and atmosphere are good for companies. The implication is that Indian companies are focused on adopting CSR to benefit their position in the IT and communication sectors.

Hitachi Data Systems launched a CSR program named Quiz in India as a learning aid that contributes to the educational growth of underprivileged children by providing them with engaging learning resources and tools. Hitachi Data Systems is a part of Hitachi Vantara, a significant global company that delivers data storage, management, and analytics solutions

(Aggarwal and Singh, 2019). The company is based in Santa Clara, California, United States of America, and it is most active in the technology niche, specifically data infrastructure and digital, such as cloud, data warehousing, and the Internet of Things (Aggarwal and Singh, 2019). Hitachi Vantara has a few offices and operation points that are in North America, Europe, Asia and Australia, which makes it well-positioned to offer its solutions to several industries such as finance, healthcare and manufacturing (Aggarwal and Singh, 2019). There is another program that is organised by Hitachi Home and Life Solutions India Ltd. (HHLI) named Jeevan Sandhya Vrudhashram. The basic aim of an organised program is to ensure a minimum impact on the environment to ensure a “Zero discharge facility”. The company sends the small amount of wastewater that is generated due to incineration to an authorised party and effectively eliminates the requirement of an Effluent Treatment Plant (Aggarwal and Singh, 2019). With more than 3 million independents and Company Owners (IBOs) in over 80 global markets and territories, Amway is one of the world's biggest direct sales organisations. Amway’s top office is in Ada, Michigan, in the United States of America. The company has a presence in every part of the world, and it deals with health, beauty and home care solutions. Amway is a Company that heavily focuses on the traditions of the family (Aswani et al., 2021). Many Families are willing to collaborate with Amway, which partners with UNICEF, the United Nations Children's Fund, as part of its CSR policy. Amway is committed to playing a significant role in defending and advancing the lives of children who are in need across the world as a family-run company, which allows the organisation to show how it has advanced international causes (Kumar and Nigam, 2017). Amway's mission is to enable people to live better, which is accomplished by providing a low-cost, low-risk market opportunity that is centred on the selling of high-quality items such as laundry detergents, body care, and oral care (Gatti et al., 2019). Amway describes a global cause

as a social problem that affects a considerable number of individuals across the world, including those who are engaged in a conflict or dilemma that requires a generous reaction.

Dabur India Ltd-Sundesh has supported numerous deserving causes since 2002, including improving healthcare, fostering skill development, and combating climate change (González-Gómez, 2020). Dabur India Ltd does its business in the fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) industry with a focus on health and personal care products (González-Gómez, 2020). The company heavily invests in social responsibilities for community uplift and health education, especially for the rural inhabitants, as part of its corporate responsibility to enhance the health status of the poor population densities. With the help of a strong community welfare and development programme, Indian Oil dedicates a specific portion of its annual revenue to many individuals throughout the nation. As for its CSR, the company spends up to five per cent of its consolidated annual turnover on different community welfare and development schemes in India (Kalita and Bhattacharjee, 2019). Such a commitment is valuable in the elimination of social problems such as education, health, and the natural environment. With the right investment strategies, Indian Oil seeks to empower the poorest groups and increase the quality of life in the localised areas of operation (Kalita and Bhattacharjee, 2019). The protection of people from Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes accounts for approximately one-fourth of community development aid spending by Indian Oil. The allocation underscores the duty to enhance the social and economic conditions of the deprived groups, to protect and promote their rights and availability of basic commodities and services. Indian Oil has a coordinated programme of social responsibility for the local community to its plants in the fields of health, family welfare, education, conservation of the environment, water supply, sanitation and empowerment for women and other disadvantaged groups (Kalita and Bhattacharjee, 2019). Initiatives aimed at

India's semi-urban, rural, and non-English speaking inhabitants have been spearheaded by Microsoft's CSR. Microsoft has its base in Redmond, Washington, USA and operates through a huge number of regional offices and software development centres (Aggarwal and Singh, 2019). Microsoft has a strong representation in India and has offices across different cities, such as Bengaluru, Hyderabad and Gurgaon, for areas such as Software development, cloud and innovation skilling for local businesses and society (Aggarwal and Singh, 2019). Microsoft develops software that meets the demands of this division in addition to the grants it has provided to the tune of over US 1.15 million in educational initiatives (Aggarwal and Singh, 2019). Microsoft creates applications that address certain needs as efficiency with the Office Suite, computing power with Azure, communication apps with Microsoft Teams, Business intelligence with Power BI, and security with Microsoft Defender (Aggarwal and Singh, 2019). Besides, they developed easy-to-use operating systems such as Windows and services aimed at education and enterprise markets. As part of its commitment to provide India with an accessible local language computer solution, the company recently introduced its Windows XP starting edition tailored for India.

Forbes Marshall has its operation centre in Pune, India, and branch offices in the rest of the Indian cities, such as Mumbai and Delhi. Internationally, the company has operations in the United States, the United Kingdom, and several other Southeast Asian countries (Ramesh et al., 2019). Also, the company operates in the industrial automation industry and the steam engineering industry (Ramesh et al., 2019). CSR activities that Forbes Marshall undertakes are in the sectors of education, health, and environment. The company offers youth skill development and health care programmes for the disadvantaged community and environmental conservation (Ramesh et al., 2019). Some of its objectives of CSR are targeted to produce positive social

change and encourage corporate professionalism. Unilever supports various CSR initiatives in India. Hindustan Unilever Limited (HUL) is Unilever's operation company in India and is situated in Mumbai (Sehgal et al., 2020). The firm operates in the fast-moving consumer goods industry and supplies convenience products across personal, home, and food care segments. HUL also practises CSR, which initiates and supports living, health/hygiene, and women's programmes (Sehgal et al., 2020). Building rural entrepreneurs is the primary objective of Unilever's Shakti Project. Thirteen thousand underprivileged Indian women have been certified to market the company's products to 70 million rural clients. The company collaborates with women's self-help groups to impart sales, bookkeeping, and commercial awareness skills (Sehgal et al., 2020). The women taking part in the program can almost double their family income. Businesses, NGOs, banks, and government entities support the company's initiatives, enabling it to form effective public-private partnerships.

2.7.2 CSR activities of organisations in Bangladesh

The growing social consciousness of corporations has contributed to the emergence of a formation of CSR, whose application influences their overall marketing contact both at strategic and organisational levels. Ullah and Rahman (2015) and Shayan et al. (2022) examined the case of Aarong, a Bangladesh-based organisation with unique social problems related to gender inequality that serves as a backdrop for examining as a theoretical construct the combination of CSR's strategic and organisational levels of marketing communication. Aarong is situated in Bangladesh as the principal office in Dhaka (Shayan et al., 2022). The organisation specialises in handicrafts and retailing to involve itself in marketing and supporting Bangladeshi cultural products and craftsmen (Shayan et al., 2022). Aarong's collection of products includes exotic clothing, handicraft items, accessories, and furnishing items. Bangladesh lies in the northeastern

part of South Asia and has some of the greatest problems, including poverty and illiteracy. The economy is still predominantly agricultural, and traditional convictions and customs influence their essential importance in the present population's existence, affecting various segments of life (Ullah and Rahman, 2015; Shayan et al., 2022). Bangladesh is a country where discrimination against women is another big problem (Ullah and Rahman, 2015). However, King et al. (2021) contradict Ullah and Rahman (2015) by noting significant progress has been made in addressing the problem of women discrimination in Bangladesh. The contradiction implies that there exists a scope for enhancing the condition of society by implementing effective CSR activities to enhance educational opportunities for women. However, few organisations in Bangladesh are found to be opting for CSR opportunities.

In Bangladesh, banks that have higher CSR expenses publish further CSR disclosures. The banks disclose their CSR spending to the Bangladesh Bank. Banks announce their CSR operations of the year and long-term CSR concerns in their annual reports that the public can read to preserve credibility. Zatwarnicka-Madura et al. (2019) reiterate Ullah and Rahman (2015) and posit that society wants CSR to be invested in by the banks and to preserve their credibility, banks involved in CSR in response to societal demands should convey these CSR practises to stakeholders. In addition, Zatwarnicka-Madura et al. (2019) showed that CSR spending in Bangladesh is positively linked to bank CSR disclosures. The size of the company does not significantly shed light on a connection between the level of openness and variability of corporate social and environmental. However, larger banks are susceptible to social criticism. Because of their greater visibility, larger banks' operations and inactivity are noticeable.

2.7.3 CSR activities of organisations in Pakistan

The CSR practises among Small and medium-sized (SMEs) foster organisational image and employee participation. CSR operations and financial performance can be improved by the characteristics of SMEs and large companies. Advantages of brand credibility and future long-term strategies can be gained from CSR. Ramayah et al. (2022) aligns with Freire and Loussaïef (2018), who highlight a beneficial correlation between environmental CSR and the corporate image of the SME sector in Pakistan. Ramayah, Falahat and Soto-Acosta (2022) support Farooq et al. (2013) and report that the term employee commitment refers to dedication, engagement in the business, and loyalty to the enterprise. As such, if workers are loyal to companies, they can improve the efficiency of the company and minimise employee attrition simultaneously. CSR and employee involvement have a supportive and meaningful association and enhance the organisation's culture. Zhu et al. (2014) align with Farooq et al. (2013) and argue that to achieve long-term benefits, companies are engaged in CSR operations and workforce growth initiatives. Zhu et al. (2014) suggest that CSR practices create a supportive relationship between staff and the company. In comparison, south Asian corporations focus on workers, maintaining them with incentives to inspire and invest in the enterprise to boost financial outcomes. According to Bernhardt et al. (2000), companies operating in small and medium-sized markets rely on internal and external CSR programmes to better enhance the working climate. The potential of CSR through employee participation can be strengthened by research mechanisms that underpin openness, cooperation with customers, and sustainable practises.

2.8 Advantages and Challenges in CSR Strategies' Implementation

2.8.1 Advantages of CSR policies implementation

In the era of rapid advancement in digital technology, each business requires an effective CSR program due to the significant advantages that the program will generate. According to Saeidi et al. (2015), companies perform CSR to ensure the wellbeing of society and to build and enhance their reputation. Brand reputation is defined as the degree to which, among customers, a company is held in high regard. Based on factual experiences with its products and credibility news that comes to them, customers develop a sense of worth or disdain towards a corporation. Corporate credibility is the ultimate consequence of the collection of assumptions by customers about how well a company achieves its criteria and standards (Saeidi et al., 2015). Thus, one of CSR's key benefits is that it aims to develop the organisation's reputation. Corporate reputation is an intangible asset for an enterprise. The overall reputation of a company can, explicitly or implicitly, impact its financial performance. The contrary could also be true at the same time: the company's overall credibility could be impacted by its financial performance (Dmytriyev, Freeman and Hörisch, 2021). Thus, non-economic considerations, such as making constructive contributions to the development of people and the environment, positively affect the image of the business. A strategic mechanism for corporate image building may be the fulfilment of economic and/or non-economic CSR. Figure 3 further showcases the importance of CSR in companies and society.

Figure 3: CSR and nonfinancial organisational performance (NFOP) of for-profit public and private enterprises in Yemen

Source: (Al-Samman and Al-Nashmi, 2016)

In Figure 3, the benefits of CSR on society and companies are detailed. The role of business has undergone a drastic change due to heightened awareness of the detrimental effects of business activities on the environment. Society expects firms to attract their clients with better goods and produce enough profits for their shareholders. McKnight et al. (2002) have highlighted that one of CSR's key benefits is that it raises customer trust in honesty. Trust in honesty is the belief of a customer that a business exhibits continuity between its principles and actions and adheres to the moral standard of justice. According to Faeq et al. (2022), corporations are required to satisfy their legal and ethical obligations to achieve customer reputation trust. First, a company must follow laws and comply with applicable legislation. The minimum requirements for business conduct are established by these laws and regulations (Faeq et al., 2022). Consumer perception of the history of an organisation with respect to the discharge of its legal issues comes from the news media, and if customers understand that a business has not met legal obligations, they likely view the organisation as less truthful and reasonable

(Zdonek, Mularczyk and Polok, 2021). In addition, the discharge of a company of its legal duties affects confidence in honesty (Prechel, 2022). Ethical obligations demand that organisations conform to moral principles. Whereas the statute proscribes certain conduct, ethical obligations include practices that society wants to be performed by corporations. Once customers accept that a corporation performs its business in compliance with moral principles, they believe the company to be trustworthy. Lamberti and Lettieri (2009) found that the ethical contribution of an organisation contributed to gaining the confidence of customers. A company that engages in ethical behaviours and makes ethically correct decisions is likely to gain the trust of society.

Conveying optimistic motivations and goals behind the company's CSR efforts is crucial to building client confidence in social benevolence. Saeidi et al. (2015) found that CSR also could boost social benevolence trust along with knowledge trust. Social benevolence trust represents the belief of customers that a business is seriously concerned with the conservation and improvement of society's welfare. The fact of Starbucks's well-known engagement with various philanthropic causes, including supporting sustainable water and social development projects in communities from which the firm buys its coffee beans, is regarded as trustworthy. However, the cigarette corporations' dollars have contributed little to various "good" groups to battle the public view that they should not be trusted, while their marketing efforts have continued to attack young people (Yoon et al., 2006). The participation of cigarette corporations in sponsoring 'good' reasons or even health-targeted groups are observed as an image-enhancing activity. For instance, some programs that promote public health and financial support to such programs are overshadowed by the amounts spent on marketing, particularly targeting youths (Yoon et al., 2006). Such a gap between the declaration of social responsibility and specific advertising direction can be viewed as unethical and evoke doubt about the companies' real

motives (Yoon et al., 2006). Unlike Starbucks, cigarette corporations have provided little, if any, support to reliable organisations that can enhance their CSR image. However, these companies are still stuck in marketing to youth to encourage unhealthy lifestyles while actively erasing attempts to change the perceptions applied to their products and procedures. Many customers do not benefit directly from corporate charitable efforts but believe companies commit financial resources to improve society (Morales, 2005). When a company is involved in corporate philanthropy, customers develop trust.

CSR activity does have a positive impact on the financial condition of organisations located in developing countries like Bangladesh. Dhar, Harymawan and Sarkar (2022) support McKnight et al. (2002) and report that organisations with effective CSR policies in Bangladesh realise higher revenue and profit margins compared to those with no CSR policies. Lamberti and Lettieri (2009) add that adopting CSR practices strengthens consumer connections. Businesses with a positive public perception of being good corporate attract customers. Consumers are prepared to pay a 10% premium for socially conscious goods. Naim (2021) supports Lamberti and Lettieri (2009) and adds that a CSR policy increases a company's worth and profitability. Applying the principles of recycling household waste and increasing energy efficiency enables businesses to minimise expenses and emissions. Reducing wastage and adopting efficient energy consumption will reduce costs, hence improving business operations and sustainability, fulfilling a business's social responsibility and promoting a better planet for humans.

CSR enhances companies' responsibility for openness on the part of financial experts, the public, investors, and local governments. In return, openness boosts investors' trust, such as mutual funds, which include CSR in stock choices (Okafor, Adeleye and Adusei, 2021). CSR results in favourable development, which increases the company's market appreciation and

relaxes its availability of risk capital. CSR practises contribute to the common good (Chow et al., 2021). Allowing workers to engage with management offers both a sense of membership within the organisation and a connection with the local community during working hours. Workers get inspiration and confidence through these professional growth chances. For instance, staff who execute responsibilities in groups act as brand advocates (Labadi et al., 2021). Yoon et al. (2006) have stressed how CSR initiatives can contribute to an enhanced public profile. Companies that practise CSR gain recognition and support for their existence. Customers who buy goods and services from companies that help their community believe their money was well spent.

Successful CSR policies contribute to improved customer satisfaction. Consumers likely remain loyal to a company if the corporate values align with their own (Leclercq-Machado et al., 2022). The millennial generation prefers to do business with corporate entities and brand names with prosocial messages and sustainable production methods (Sylvester, 2019). Millennials or Generation Y are usually described as people born between 1981 and 1996; thus, in 2024, they range between approximately 28 and 43 years old. CSR initiatives aim to demonstrate company principles and teamwork, community involvement and engagement and ethically responsible business standards (Kim et al., 2022). Morales (2005) emphasises that productive CSR contribute to enhanced innovation. CSR activities increase customer confidence in learning new ideas. According to Widarko and Anwarodin (2022), giving community donations can enable individuals to discover new and improved ways to carry out their work. By listening to the customer's views, companies can discover unmet wants. Thus, creative culture within organisations allows the development of solutions with a positive impact on organisational effectiveness and communities.

Organisations in India face high competition in retaining skilled and experienced employees. Islam et al. (2012) highlight that improved employee satisfaction leads to retention, which is a major advantage associated with CSR. International brands like TCS and Wipro, through effective CSR activities targeted to employee retention, enjoy competitive advantages in retaining and attracting skilled employees over local competitors. Both TCS (Tata Consultancy Services) and Wipro are IT giants from India, having their corporate offices in Mumbai and Bengaluru, respectively (Islam et al., 2012). They specialise mainly in the information technology and consulting industries. These global players offer services in software development, IT consulting, and digital enablement for clients in every industry from different parts of the world. Effective employee satisfaction through CSR activities creates a sense of community within the organisations. According to Saeidi et al. (2015), social responsibility encourages businesses to act ethically and to consider the social and environmental consequences of a company. Consequently, a company prevent the adverse effects of its operations on the community.

2.8.2 Challenges in CSR policies' implementation

The drawback of CSR, especially in the case of small companies, is that it is adversely impacted by prices. Chu, Chen and Gan (2020) and Lu et al. (2021) posit that small enterprises, through social media, express their CSR strategy. CSR efficiency can enhance the size of the investment base. Stakeholders who are socially responsible are inclined to withdraw investment portfolios with poor CSR results. In other words, organisations with high CSR efficiency can improve their investor base. The market price rises, and the cost of capital decreases in direct proportion to the size of the client base. However, studies such as El Ghoul et al. (2010) and Plumlee et al. (2015) postulate that businesses that do better in the market have lower equity

capital expenses. As such, based on private debt financing, the cost of bank loans for companies with social justice issues is higher than for businesses that prioritise risk management. The increased interest rates and stricter lending terms are associated with perceived risks for business models as financial institutions evaluate their social impact and sustainability.

Consumers face challenges in distinguishing between genuine sustainable practices and marketing strategies, highlighting the need for industry standards to ensure accountability. Islam et al. (2012) support Kapoor and Dhamija (2017) and state that though consumers support CSR activities, especially in developing and underdeveloped regions like Africa, India and countries such as India, China, consumers may decline to pay more for CSR activities. Most consumers focus on obtaining the best quality and quantity of products (Contini et al., 2020). Buyers can opt for a product from a company with deficient or non-existent CSR policies. Thus, the circumstances can be considered major reasons behind many organisations' reluctance to adopt CSR-related activities in developing and underdeveloped nations.

Greenwashing describes commercial practices that make environmental claims without altering how a company conducts its operations. Sardana et al. (2020) underlines the need for transparency and disclosure. Stakeholders require greater transparency and accountability from businesses, including clients, vendors, team members, contributors, and local community organisations. Companies need business strategies that prioritise effective ways to acquire, coordinate, understand, and handle their data for clear, precise, and comprehensive monitoring of financial and business activities. On the contrary, Pinto and Allui (2020) posit that investor stress is a significant barrier to the successful execution of CSR operations. Thus, stakeholders must be supported to alleviate stress and enhance CSR implementation. Individuals spend and invest in companies that demonstrate excellent social responsibility. Korneeva, Skornichenko and Oruch

(2021) align with Frederiksen (2018) by noting that businesses need adaptable and reactive CSR practises because they are important in recruiting millennials and Gen Z. Generation Y, also known as millennials, are those born between 1981 and 1996, and they are particular in experience and technology use. Continuing the global trends from Generation Y, Generation Z or the post-Millennials, people born from 1997 onwards are digital citizens and have strong civic and practical entrepreneurship trends with a focus on authenticity and sustainability as key values in brands. Fisher, Porod and Peterson (2021) and Delmas, Lyon and Maxwell (2019) concur that training programmes, preparation, and a cohesive approach to internal corporate processes and controls, as well as guidance, can secure employee engagement. Corporations experience challenges in fostering employee engagement, particularly where separate business divisions have distinct agendas and strategies.

Robotic process automation and cloud-based data storage are examples of hard value creation (attracting talented talent through quality-of-life benefits and a progressive and equitable work environment). According to Tundys (2021), companies that engage in CSR activities would benefit from hard and soft value creation. Hard value creation, such as sales and reduced production costs, is evident in companies like Unilever through CSR activities. Another part of soft value creation relates to the improvement of brand recognition and customer loyalty, which creates a powerful position among competitors, pointing at Starbucks's activity in the sphere of social participation. However, demonstrating how CSR contributes to the creation of goods and services that meet regulatory enforcement requirements, market viability, success targets, and customer preferences involves utilising digital applications that coordinate data sources and provide quantifiable value (Nguyen et al., 2020). Companies that centralise procurement using a cloud-based, unified optimisation and data management solution, such as purchasing control, can

capture, coordinate, and interpret data from a computing environment (Eyasu and Endale, 2020). Yue (2022) supports Eyasu and Endale (2020) and posits that vendors who have maximum budget accountability track internal process efficiency data. The insights indicate the ease of evaluating and optimising sustainable procurement activities and gaining greater savings.

The general public's interest in engaging in and contributing to the CSR operations of corporations is missing because little or no knowledge is associated with such practices. A lack of coordination between the businesses participating in CSR and the wider community at the grassroots level aggravates the problem in South Asian countries. Zikargae, Woldaregay and Skjerdal (2021) highlight a requirement for local non-governmental organisations to develop resources because there is a severe lack of skilled and productive organisations in South Asian countries that can contribute efficiently to the ongoing CSR initiatives undertaken by corporations. This undermines the scaling-up of CSR programmes and thus reduces the scale of those operations. Eyasu and Endale (2020) resonate with Zikargae, Woldaregay and Skjerdal (2021) and argue that the lack of accountability is one of the biggest organisational problems. For instance, there exists a lack of transparency among small firms in South Asian countries as they do not make sufficient attempts to report on their projects, audit issues, impact measurement, and resource utilisation. The insights from the studies indicate that the challenges adversely affect the confidence-building process among firms, which is key to the success of any CSR initiative.

Well-coordinated non-governmental organisations in remote and rural areas in South Asia do not evaluate and recognise specific community requirements and collaborate closely with businesses to ensure the effective delivery of CSR initiatives. Agte (2021) add to Govindasamy and Suresh (2018) by highlighting the role of the media in showcasing good cases

of active CSR initiatives as it disseminates good news and increases public consciousness about corporations' numerous ongoing CSR initiatives. The insights indicate the effects of gaining recognition and visibility also drive non-governmental agencies to participate in event-based initiatives; concrete grassroots initiatives are often lost in the process.

In general, non-governmental organisations and government departments have a limited viewpoint on business CSR initiatives, frequently describing CSR initiatives as donor driven. This view holds that organisations engage in CSR initiatives to improve perception about them and meet the legal minimum standards for business activities without a genuine interest and intent on improving society's welfare (Chan et al., 2020). As a result, businesses find it impossible to determine if, in the short and long term, they can engage in those programmes. The scope of corporations' CSR initiatives can focus on the size and profile of their company. There exists a lack of consensus about CSR projects between implementing agencies (Chan et al., 2020). Instead of developing collective solutions to problems, this resulted in a competitive spirit between implementing agencies, which limits the capacity of the organisation to carry out impact analyses of its projects. Morales (2005) has highlighted that one of the major factors that lead to challenges faced by organisations while implementing CSR policies in developing countries like India, Bangladesh and Pakistan includes the inefficacy of the country's governments. The government relies on regulation and legislation to deliver social and environmental objectives in the business sector, which often leads to failed initiatives. Additionally, political interference acts as a major issue for the CSR activities of organisations in South Asian countries. Saha, Akhter, and Hassan (2021) and Morales (2005) posit that an organisation opting to take part in crucial social issues may be compelled to stop the initiatives since they adversely affect the political

agenda of political parties. The implication of the findings is that companies in South Asia are unable to engage in CSR activities due to political interference.

Lack of effective training sessions, knowledge, and experiences of the management team, along with an understanding of the workforce about the importance of CSR activities, act as a major challenge for organisations established in developing and underdeveloped countries to implement effective CSR activities. A significant number of local organisations in Sri Lanka do not possess any CSR policies due to the experience of failed initiatives in the past. Saha, Akhter and Hassan (2021) add to Lamberti and Lettieri (2009) and explain that the key reason behind the failed initiatives includes a lack of effective knowledge gathering about the external condition of the environment along with a lack of expertise to plan activities that can effectively address the issue. In most developing nations, stiff competition makes it difficult for local organisations to ensure effective CSR activities.

2.9 Literature Gaps

The literature related to the impact of CSR strategies on companies indicated various existing research gaps. There is a paucity of research on the implementation of CSR in South Asian countries, especially India, Pakistan and Bangladesh. There is a lack of empirical studies examining how CSR impacted society in South Asian countries and the profitability and brand image of textile companies in South Asia. The insights from the reviewed literature also showed that based on the unique institutional context of South Asia and the various socio-economic problems faced by South Asian nations, a lack of empirical research on the challenges faced by South Asian industries in adopting CSR further emerged. The discussions also showed that the implementation of CSR considered cultural sensitivity and the differences in local cultures in the Asian continent. Based on the huge presence of the textile sector in South Asia, there is an urgent

need to explore how the culture in a region characterised by middle-income or developing countries can influence attitudes towards adopting CSR practices.

The review of diverse literature also showed that while many articles elaborated on the different strategies used by internal organisations to ensure effective CSR activities, a limited amount of data has been found regarding CSR's meaningful contribution to society and how it could enhance the brand image amongst potential customers. Various studies regarding the impact of CSR activities on global organisations and their impact on society and business. However, minimal studies have elaborated on how the South Asian garment industries could act in a socially responsible way to deliver to stakeholder expectations and achieve sustainable social, environmental and economic development. The current study analyses the impact of CSR on the organisation in terms of brand image and corporate performance in South Asian Countries. Addressing the literature gaps contributes to theory development by indicating how CSR enhances the brand image and performance of companies. Additionally, addressing the gaps will add to managerial practice and public policy by outlining recommendations from the literature on how CSR strategies promote brand image.

2.10 Summary and Conclusion

Diverse studies were reviewed to elaborate on the definition and history of CSR, the impact of CSR on businesses and society, and the CSR strategies used by South Asian organisations. The review also highlighted the advantages and challenges associated with implementing CSR policies in South Asia's organisations in line with their unique socio-economic and institutional context. The insights from the literature also indicated a positive relationship between CSR strategies and brand image. Firms are likely to engage in CSR practises, improving their reputation and image based on the increasing awareness of

sustainability issues and a growing global focus on firms and businesses to abandon profit-oriented initiatives and embrace social responsibilities. CSR encompasses the company's contributions to sustainable development efforts by considering the social and economic impact of its actions to improve society and the wider environment.

CSR activities could take various forms, including carbon footprint, improving labour policies, charitable giving, participating in fair trade, and volunteering in the community. Corporate policies focus on maintaining and enhancing the quality of the natural environment by minimising the usage of resources. Adoption of corporate policies that enhance environmental sustainability entails ensuring that wastes produced are minimised, energy is safeguarded, and renewable resources are used in the corporate world. Indian garment firms have put into effect various initiatives that support sustainability goals such as combating climate change, socio-economic development of marginalised communities and poverty alleviation. Various studies show a positive relationship between CSR and a company's financial performance. Adopting a CSR outlook enables a company to go beyond a self-interested profit-making agenda and benefit a wider range of stakeholders other than shareholders. Sustainability is a defining issue today in education, policy centres, and the public, who are enlightened and conscious about sustainability concerns. A company's CSR activities help customers identify with the brand and increase their customer reputation. This impact can be an intangible asset for the company. In addition, CSR also encourages companies to be transparent about their finances. CSR improves credibility for investors and magnifies future funding opportunities. The benefits of CSR for socially responsible companies are in terms of high retention rates of employees compared to non-CSR firms. However, studies indicated challenges faced in implementing CSR, especially for small businesses where CSR investments could be a financial burden. Additionally, the prevalent

misconceptions about the financial benefits of CSR are a challenge. Additional expenses are incurred in organisational changes due to CSR and can frequently undermine the efficacy of CSR for companies. The research also highlighted the critical role of governments in supporting and advancing CSR in the corporate sector. Subsequently, the identified gaps and insights from theory inform the development of the theoretical and conceptual framework chapter.

Chapter 3: Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

3.1 Introduction

Philosophy plays a critical role in interpreting the relationships between ideas and the explanations for their existence. Besides philosophy, theoretical structures also assist in interpreting the key concepts and explanations of research topics (Braidotti, 2019). Specific theories and principles help in framing hypotheses and utilising deductive reasoning to link the findings to real-world scenarios. In a research report, theory explains the occurrence and reasons for the research (Rudyanto, 2019). The purpose of this section is to identify the underlying theories relevant to the context of CSR activities in business organisations and the impact on the image of the brand. A clear understanding of all dependent and independent factors is essential to evaluate the current situation within South Asian countries (Asiri, Khan and Kend, 2020). The brand image that contributes to industrial, sociological, economic, and business profitability significantly depends on these factors, which must be assessed through proper theoretical knowledge of these factors (Seyfried et al., 2019). In the next section, five theories are considered: coercive isomorphism, mimetic isomorphism, normative isomorphism, legitimacy theory and Carroll's CSR. Lamberti and Lettieri (2009) give a guide to the research conceptual framework. To conceptualise research, this process can be created by emerging knowledge and experiences in coronation with the research topic. To develop a map that can guide the research journey, the identification of various steps from the topic and research problem to the conclusion is necessary. In other words, the conceptual framework is designed to follow to achieve the aim of the research. Figure 4 shows the theoretical framework guiding the current study.

Figure 4: Theoretical Framework

Source: (Author, 2024)

In Figure 4, the theoretical framework adopted is illustrated where it encompasses the three types of isomorphism theories: coercive isomorphism, mimetic isomorphism, normative isomorphism, and both legitimacy theory and Carroll's CSR theory. The paradigms reveal important insights regarding the decisions of firms to participate in CSR activities.

3.2 Coercive Isomorphism

Coercive isomorphic modification is considered due to organisational demands and social and cultural standards. Some of these are regulated by the state and government, and others depend on the agreement of business and principles of accounting (Asiri, Khan and Kend, 2020).

The concept of coercive Isomorphism illustrates a scenario in which organisations respond to a problem because of coercive pressure from powerful partners. Coercive isomorphism emerges from different angles of conforming: the firm's dependent institutions and culture. Exxon's efforts to adhere to standards set by society and their stakeholders serve as evidence in the initial case, as organisations were subject to both types of pressure. Exxon Mobil is listed among the largest international oil and gas corporations based in Irving, Texas, United States (Musina, Manini and Alala, 2021). Specialising in the oil sector, it is involved in the drilling, production, refining and marketing of oil and natural gas and the production of chemical, polymers, and renewable energy assets (Musina, Manini and Alala, 2021). Increased consistency was developed in market share and organisational pricing policies in the competitive environment (Musina, Manini and Alala, 2021). Coercive isomorphism emerging through togetherness on a small set of customer bases may play a part in judging strategy for managers in business and in the allocation of strategic resources into practice.

Self-regulatory and cooperative programmes, such as Global Reporting Initiatives (GRI), are examples of coercive isomorphism. These initiatives are known as explicit CSR, which is described as CSR over which the organisation has decision-making authority (Asiri, Khan and Kend, 2020). Even if the firm is reacting to coercion, explicit CSR may be an answer to coercive isomorphism as the firm maintains decision-making flexibility. Garment manufacturers in South Asian companies are expected to adhere to rules, standards, and codes of conduct for foreign customers due to power dynamics in business dealings. The impact of foreign buyers may be interpreted as coercive pressure on their suppliers. The textile manufacturing companies of the clothing industry in South Asian countries are the suppliers (Musina, Manini and Alala, 2021). The competition in the garment industry shapes norms into coercive isomorphism characteristics

to help the garment sector in India, Bangladesh, Pakistan, and Sri Lanka propagate CSR. CSR activities are carried out considering the laws, rules, or regulations that have been publicly legislated. For CSR's case in the clothing industries of these countries, government industrial and labour regulations and external influences, including the 'Fair Labour Association' and 'Clean Cloth Drive,' influence consumers' decisions. Nevertheless, the enforcement and effectiveness vary among South Asian countries, affecting consumer decisions differently across the countries.

Coercive isomorphism, based on institutional theory, is an external pressure that affects the organisation and sanctions laws and regulations, as well as the standards and expectations of external organisations, governments, industry, and society. Amoako et al. (2021) and Aragón-Correa, Marcus and Vogel (2020) note that coercive isomorphism is one of the organisational isomorphic pressures which ensures adherence to legal requirements and ethical norms and improves the corporation's legitimacy, resulting in a favourable impact on society. This aspect disincentivises the corporate world through practises like CSR to adhere to a standard and be held accountable for how they impact social and environmental issues. However, Moser et al. (2020) suggest that organisations may make those changes to avoid legal repercussions, thus creating compliance rather than a real commitment to ethical practices. Coercive isomorphism reveals the extent to which imposed regulations promote CSR. Furthermore, it confirms that South Asian companies conduct their operations and implement CSR programmes in ethically correct ways that may help them become popular and profitable by reflecting the sentiments and expectations of society. However, excessive use of pressures may limit creativity and thus result in standardised CSR strategies that cannot address dynamic social and environmental issues (Amoako et al., 2021; Moser et al., 2020). Therefore, while coercive isomorphism may help

discover CSR practices that are mutually beneficial to society and business, their shortcomings in the process should be appreciated.

3.3 Mimetic Isomorphism

In organisation theory, mimetic isomorphism refers to the prosperity of an organisation to imitate the structure of another organisation as it fits its final structure. This form of activity occurs often when an organisation's goals or means of achieving them are ambiguous. Mimetic Isomorphism differs from the theory of coercive isomorphism. In coercive isomorphism, the external factors force change for institutions. In normative isomorphism, professional networks affect the change (Rudyanto, 2019). Companies such as McKinsey & Co. used the term in their advice to companies going through restructuring or other organisational transitions. McKinsey & Company is a New York City-based, international management consulting firm operating out of over 60 locations around the world. The company's primary focus is the consulting market, where it provides strategic, operational, and digital consultancy and transformation solutions to businesses, governments and non-profit organisations across the globe. An institution often imitates other institutional structures by idealising that institution. Mimetic Isomorphism demonstrates a scenario in which companies appear to emulate the best players on the field, which could have an optimistic outcome for the organisations. Increased market insecurity or confusion causes industry leaders and managers to look for the best practices which are appropriate for the supply chain and stakeholders. Other stakeholders are inspired to follow similar best practices in their business to improve business operations. According to Amor-Esteban et al. (2018), manufacturing firms collaborate with service providers to enhance health care for the management of employees and improve technical performance. By promoting

accountability and transparency through reporting, an organisation may share its policies and outcomes with its stakeholders.

A strength of mimetic isomorphism is that organisations can duplicate strategies, such as CSR policies, that have been used successfully by other firms. Huang, Surface and Zhang (2022) and Amor-Esteban et al. (2018) note that mimetic isomorphism results in the quicker formulation and implementation of socially responsible policies and practises, ultimately helping society by creating widespread reliance on ethical business procedures. However, Aragòn-Correa, Marcus and Vogel (2020) argue that firms may mechanically adopt these policies without integrating them into organisational values and processes, making CSR a shallow practice. In terms of CSR, mimetic isomorphic interpretation helps to analyse the efficiency of the employed CSR strategies. The model allows organisations to assess the performance difference between CSR adoption and literature as pretence and improvements (Aragòn-Correa et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2022). Thus, in the context of South Asian businesses, mimetic isomorphism may assist in finding ethical CSR practices that enhance business image and increase profitability. Firms in the clothing industry can improve societal welfare and commercial performance by adopting similar models by duplicating successful strategies, building consumer trust, appealing to the consumers' social conscience, and creating competitive advantages for their companies. However, the issue is how activities mimicked can be implemented for the specific business instead of emulating the entire practice.

3.4 Institutional Isomorphism

As per the theory of Institutional Isomorphism, the institution is a system of laws, ideas, conventions, and organisations. Institutional isomorphism places constraints on human behaviour by defining what is acceptable and unacceptable and providing instructions and resources for

certain actors. Isomorphic organisational change has three mechanisms: coercive, mimetic, and normative isomorphism (Seyfried et al., 2019). The model consists of normative, regulative, and cultural-cognitive components responsive to official norms of conduct and unwritten rules. These conducts are controlled through strategies of rewards and penalties. The organisation desires legitimacy, not competition or an objective necessity of efficiency. In the concept of management, the role of institutionalisation has progressed from full institutional blindness to institutional determinism (Anafinova, 2020). Institutional changes in South Asian countries occur through the approval of new laws, the introduction of new standards or norms, and the development of new practises and designs that affect how organisations exist and operate.

The institutional isomorphism highlights that institutional transformation at the macro level necessitates a series of micro-organisational modifications and adaptations. The neo-institutional theory, which explains how aspects of organisations, such as structures, practises, and professions, are generated and distributed in society, has extensively investigated the patterns of organisational reaction to institutional change (Canello, 2021). Hence, the market forces alone as a driver for change in CSR practises inadequately explain the different dimensions of corporate responsibility as shaped by the institutional environment that includes regulatory frameworks and social norms, in addition to governmental policies. Organisations attempt to gain legitimacy among their constituents, which is critical for organisational longevity as it allows access to environmental resources. Legitimacy ensures that the approach is consistent with the legitimacy proposal, which emphasises the social contract between a firm and society (George et al., 2020). The model also emphasises the legitimacy rationale for an organisation's reaction to structural adjustment, which is based on social worthiness and community empowerment. Professionalism is the source of normative isomorphism (Amoako et al., 2021).

Mimetic isomorphism is a result of ambiguity that drives organisations to mirror themselves in legitimate or successful peers by involving the consultants and staff hired by other companies.

The primary advantages include establishing uniformly accepted procedures and practises, which improve an organisation's credibility in the marketplace. Salato, Gomes and Ferreira (2022) and George et al. (2020) agree that institutional isomorphism enhances its competitiveness and operates in a way that inspires the confidence of its stakeholders and minimises risks in the operation of the business. On the contrary, Seyfried et al. (2019) highlight that the model can limit creativity and innovation amongst business entities since the focus will shift to compliance with best practice standards, thus reducing the variability of solutions in the marketplace. Therefore, examining CSR policies through institutional isomorphic examination enables the evaluation of ways firms conform to society. Concerning the application of institutional isomorphism in South Asian businesses, ethical CSR acts can be implemented to create a positive company image and increase profitability since they correlate with the socio-cultural and legal standards of the region (George et al., 2020; Salato et al., 2022). Thus, CSR can be aligned with the specified institutional pressures to achieve ethical sense, maintain sustainability, gain a competitive advantage, high profitability, societal welfare, and sustainable business development in the long term.

3.4 Normative Isomorphism

Normative Isomorphism refers to a circumstance in which professional authorities or associations set guidelines for 'legitimate' organisational activities, either explicitly or indirectly. Bangladesh Garment Manufacturer and Exporters' Association BGMEA, as a professional association, has developed a set of standards for its members and prospective members to follow when it comes to CSR (Anafinova, 2020). BGMEA is a legal body of garment manufacturing

business that exists to safeguard and enhance its members' interests in communicating with purchasers internationally and building capacity to respond to their needs. When the child labour problem emerged as a barrier to the garment manufacturing industry's ability in the international market to protect the interests of clothing manufacturing enterprises, the BGMEA developed a rule to ban child labour from the industry and strengthened the members' power. BGMEA improved its structure by establishing enforcement, protection, and labour cells, among other improvements, to better serve its members (Kezar and Bernstein-Sierra, 2019). Organisations try to gain legitimacy for their continued operations through isomorphism; therefore, the structure is important in examining the practice of CSR in garment manufacturing organisations in South Asian countries.

In Normative Isomorphism, each standard contains certain requirements that must be met by the organisation to obtain certification from a third party. These criteria are defining policy, establishing plans, evaluating performance, and implementing and reviewing plans. Companies are driven to improve their social and environmental performance by complying with such standards. The social and environmental performance of an organisation ensures the CSR obligations (Kamusella, 2017). Pressures from occupations drive normative isomorphic transformation. The licensing and crediting of educational success are major ways of legitimation to ensure isomorphism. Inter-organisational networks help perceive the social and environmental contracts, needs and potential relationships. Organisations adopt the norms formed during education. The normative processes internal to the area explain the diversity of roles and structure of the organisation (Anafinova, 2020). While these techniques are typically employed to propagate processes, they can also be used to alter and restructure organisations, as previously mentioned. In an organisation, the norms are interconnected with the corporate

sensitivity that fosters the structural awareness of fundamental obligations (Kezar and Bernstein-Sierra, 2019). Companies that interact with standard-setting agencies are likely to act responsibly in social and environmental matters.

Normative isomorphism deals with the social expectations to conform to structural arrangements and goals through processes, including professionalisation and the set norms of a specific line of work. Karbhari, Alam and Rahman (2020) and Anafinova (2020) show that normative isomorphism ensures organisations conform to societal norms, boosting their credibility and trustworthiness. In CSR policies, alignment helps assure compliance with ethical standards in business, improving their legitimacy and reputation. Furthermore, it allows engaging companies in implementing CSR practices that align with international standards of sustainability and social responsibility to improve social well-being. However, Imbrogiano (2021) argue that normative isomorphism can restrain innovation as businesses may tend to follow the norms of the industry rather than seeking a solution for a particular context. Generally, in South Asian business organisations, evaluation of CSR effectiveness based on normative isomorphism enables a recognition of ethical practices that enhance image and profitability. As these organisations incorporate globally acceptable practices in their CSR strategies, they improve their image and attract buyers with ethical considerations (Imbrogiano, 2021; Karbhari et al., 2020). It assists in attaining sustainable profit by integrating CSR initiatives with societal needs and wants, achieving a competitive edge.

3.5 Stakeholder Theory of CSR

Stakeholder theory, as stated by Edward Freeman and others, is the opposite of CSR. The stakeholder perspective lists and helps explain the people and entities who are influenced or affected by the group's operations, the types and information of legitimate claims on the

company, the parties' special rights in relation to the organisational actions, and the required duties and responsibilities they could rightfully place on a particular industrial setting (Freeman and Dmytriiev, 2017). The shareholder theory has the approach to indicate that the owner is not only responsible for the business, but it has the requirement of the different shareholders, including the government and non-legislative organisations, employees, business associates and customers (Nikolova and Arsić, 2017). The stakeholder theory asserts that some people whose lives are impacted by an organisation have a right and a responsibility to participate in its activities. A company operating in a particular industry must follow the capable, straightforward route from the decision of a business to the existence of an individual. Stakeholder ethics will begin once a distinct community of stakeholders surrounding an organisation has been established (Theodoulidis et al., 2017). Under this philosophy, the firm aims to maximise profit on a collective bottom line, with profit described as human welfare rather than money. Relative to the interest of serving stakeholders, business administrators are primarily concerned with coordinating the needs of all stakeholders, balancing them in the event of a dispute, and optimising the number and quantity of benefits over the medium to long term (Jahn and Brühl, 2018). To maximise advantages for everyone whose life the company affects, corporate directors are required by the stakeholder concept to consider all stakeholders and balance individual's interests and well-being.

The advantages of this approach are creating permanent relations, increasing confidence and collaboration, and increasing fairness, which generates a good company reputation and profitability. Considering the needs and concerns of the different stakeholders, Camilleri et al. (2023) and Lashitew et al. (2022) argue that companies can gain a closer link and develop shared value, which enhances the company's reputation and competitive edge. Conversely, Jahn and

Brühl (2018) note that stakeholder theory may lead to difficulties in decision-making when the interests of the stakeholders contradict the business. Besides, CSR policies implemented at an organisation attract higher costs that may lead to decreased short-term profits. However, Shah and Guild (2022) note that it is crucial to comprehend that stakeholder theory was employed in analysing the efficiency and consequences of CSR policies. The model ensures that businesses promote ethical practices that benefit stakeholders and enable the firm to make profits (Lashitew et al., 2022; Shah and Guild, 2022). In a South Asian business scenario where social accountability and environmental issues play strategic roles, applying this theory can allow recognition of CSR efforts in compliance with ethical norms and can fulfil organisational goals.

3.6 Legitimacy Theory

According to legitimacy theory, organisations must continuously aim to ensure that they are viewed as working within the bounds and norms of the culture of that country or region (Deegan et al., 2002). The theory of legitimacy indicates the "social contract" takes place between the corporation and its target society (Deegan et al., 2002). This social contract analyses whether the entity goes beyond social norms and boundaries or societal expectations. Legal criterion is a categorical term, while group standard is implied. The model is concerned with the institution's interaction with society. In legitimacy theory, society is considered rather than individual (Bela, 2015). Thus, according to the legitimacy theory, the corporation must satisfy the requirements of society as they are not only fulfilling the demand of the vendors or stakeholders. Conversely, organisations can succeed when their belief corresponds to the norms of society. Legitimacy theory provides a proper lens for appreciating how organisations strive to bring their operations closer to societal norms and expectations to increase perceived legitimacy. Legitimacy theory addresses why firms participate in CSR activities to ensure a license to

operate in society. However, De Villiers and van Staden (2006) show that legitimacy theory the institutional environment can have a significant impact on the development of those characteristics that market forces and solving social or environmental problems. When applied to the South Asian context, legitimacy theory is justifiable for exploring ethical CSR practises, which enhance business image and profitability (De Villiers and Van Staden, 2006). With heightened regulatory concerns, it becomes imperative for businesses in the region to act according to societal values. Ethical CSR practices that create value for stakeholders and address social and environmental issues would improve the company's credibility, customer loyalty, and profitability. Therefore, the legitimacy theory offers a solid framework for understanding the role of CSR in enhancing social welfare and organisational performance.

According to legitimacy theory, organisations desire to work within the accepted rules and regulations of society and the environment in which they find themselves to gain recognition from their stakeholders. Concerning this theory, Olateju et al. (2021) argue that organisational practises like CSR ensure that business organisations conform to societal standards, which allow them to operate. Therefore, CSR activities are undertaken to improve the organisation's image, parry criticisms, and ensure stakeholders' support through corporate social sensitivity. On the contrary, Patten (2020) suggests that legitimacy theory explains why South Asian garment business actors implement CSR practices. Firms use CSR to manage their image, particularly in circumstances where they face criticism in matters concerning labour conditions and the environment. Patten (2020) and Ogunode (2022) agree that employment of trade policies like implementing good labour standards and social responsibility for needy communities' companies aim to gain legitimacy for their operations from the local and international communities and government. This theory implies that CSR is an instrument by which companies seek credibility

to sustain their competitive edge, guarantee their economic viability in the long term and meet their social responsibilities. CSR is essential in fitting organisational purposes with societal requirements for sustainable development.

3.7 Elkington's Triple Bottom Line

The triple bottom line term was invented by John Elkington, the specialist and consultant of organisation governance and sustainability, in 1994 to describe methods for corporate performance measurement. Elkington's triple bottom line model allows organisations to think about their results in a wider context (Dobroselskyi and Kurotová, 2020). The triple bottom line (TBL) in economics dictates that organisations should pay attention to the issue of social and environmental factors and focus on the organisation's profitability and success. The profit and loss (P&L) account is the standard indicator of corporate profit, which is mentioned in this theory. In this theory, the concept of people is not limited to internal stakeholders such as employees, employers, partners, and others. The model includes the major external stakeholders or people, that is, the consumers (Gupta, Mishra and Tandon, 2020). The theory shows the relationship between the impact of the CSR governing process and the people associated with the business, including the consumers. This theory associates that the planet is a metric that assesses a company's environmental stewardship.

A TBL is used to assess a company's corporate social responsibilities and its environmental impact over time. As per the TBL theory, if a firm concentrates solely on financial resources and while ignoring how they interrelate with others, it will not grasp the whole picture and compensate for the full price of executing a business (Lovisceck, 2020). When estimating total costs for enterprises, Elkington's TBL framework emphasises the sustainability objectives in corporate practises, in which corporations consider environmental and social factors

along with profits (Correia, 2019). However, what defines environmental responsibility is a matter of opinion. The triple bottom line is a three-part accounting model that considers social, environmental, and economic factors. Firms use the TBL framework to examine their performances in a broader context to increase business benefits for the long term through sustainability.

TBL motivates companies to think about social interest and environmental management along with financial gain, increasing the organisation's reportage and obedience. However, Farooq et al. (2021) and Fadli (2021) highlight that TBL has problems measuring social and environmental results against the financial returns. It becomes quite problematic to attain an equilibrium between the three dimensions whereby short-term profitability pulls down sustainability efforts in the long run. Moreover, Correia (2019) states that the TBL model makes it easier to critically evaluate CSR policies because it offers an equilibrium by which an individual can analyse how a company's CSR activities impact society, the environment, and the company. By applying TBL to South Asian business organisations, it is possible to define the ethical CSR practises that can add to the organisation's image and include profitability in the agenda. Ethically sourced products that benefit society and protect the environment must be communicated to the public and other stakeholders since it helps create trust and sets organisations apart from their competitors in the current volatile economies.

3.8 Carroll's CSR

Carroll's pyramid, shown in Figure 5, is adopted by manufacturers globally and emphasises numerous dimensions of responsibility, including moral, regulatory, economic, and humanitarian issues. Garment firms in South Asian countries are required to implement effective practices to ensure workers' safety (Nurunnabi, Alfakhri and Alfakhri, 2020). Archie Carroll

devised the pyramid that consists of four styles of obligations which endorse and spread social awareness. As presented by the theory, the first basic layer is economic accountability, which includes economic sustainability factors such as profit-making, financial flexibility, and goals for long-term benefit (Wagner-Tsukamoto, 2019). Society demands that its members fulfil legal obligations, which include obeying its laws and moral standards and giving them top priority while integrating these rules into the guiding strategy of the organisation.

Figure 5: Carroll's Pyramid of CSR

Source: (Nurunnabi, Alfakhri, and Alfakhri, 2020).

The third layer is ethical responsibility that is not highly required but is desired by society. Ethical responsibilities are moral norms and factors that prevent institutions from satisfying society's expectations. The third is inextricably connected to the second, which

instructs the organisation to be moral in all circumstances (Wagner-Tsukamoto, 2019). The fourth obligation is philanthropy, also known as discretionary duty, which is defined as the provision of financial and other assets to the community. These factors are neither strictly required nor expected from society. These are the desired qualities that an organisation should have to ensure its better reputation in society.

Carroll's Pyramid of CSR presents a comprehensive framework, highlighting the economic, lawful, moral, and philanthropic levels. Srivastava et al. (2022) and Chufama, Sithole and Utaumire (2021) argue that the pyramid has a systematised approach provided to incorporate CSR into various aspects of a business. Similarly, Wagner-Tsukamoto (2019) notes that the model focuses on economic enablers as the primary ones that guarantee profitability; however, it also stresses legal obligations, ethical standards, and philanthropy. Carroll's pyramid framework allows organisations to benchmark their CSR profile against others and the specific industry, which will impact the effectiveness and coverage of CSR. Firms can compare themselves against the industry, which eventually helps to realise the opportunities and the threats and determine the extent to which their CSR activities meet the expectations of the stakeholders (Wagner-Tsukamoto, 2019). Alternatively, Moran, Chavez and Hubbard (2019) argue that the pyramid emphasises the generation of revenues over moral and philanthropic imperatives, which is a significant drawback for some companies. From this perspective, the model is concerned with the profit-making potential lower than the benefits created for society (Srivastava et al., 2022; Wagner-Tsukamoto, 2019). In addition, the model is not adaptable for divergent cultures and geographical locations, such as South Asian culture, which entails honour and stigma in instances of return of goods. In the South Asian cultures of honour and stigma, consumers may develop a perception that returning items is a sign of a bad decision-making process or an

unfavourable action that leads to the tarnishing of one's reputation. This cultural context requires brands to change their policies and acknowledge these cultural aspects. However, with these limitations in mind, it is possible to identify the ethical CSR practices that are beneficial for improving the business image and profitability of South Asian firms, according to Carroll's Pyramid. When matching ethical responsibilities to respective cultures, firms would enhance their "social image", meaning customers' trust. Ethical responsibility consequently helps to build brand credibility and, over the long term, may result in increased profitability due to customer loyalty.

3.9 Linking the Theories to the Research

This study aims to use the already existing theories to understand the current obligation levels of the business towards corporate social responsibilities while considering the participation of customers. The study also highlights customer perception, awareness, and behavioural modification due to the utilisation of CSR management and activities by garment retail organisations. This is an exploratory study aimed at capturing organisational attitudes and CSR behaviours related to labour standards. The stakeholder model of CSR is used to decide how managers and owners of companies in the garment industry react to their employees and customers, in this case, foreign buyers. 'Institutional Isomorphism' was used as a theoretical basis for interpreting organisational managers' conduct in CSR activities. Various areas of fundamental labour protections, conditions of employment, healthcare, security, and maintaining data integrity of chosen business enterprises are analysed, and data gathering techniques are built appropriately to adhere to purchasers' requirements and the nation's industrial law. Among these theories, Carroll's Pyramid of CSR, which combines major categories of responsibilities, including economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic, is applicable to factories in South Asian

countries. These factories exist under conditions where they must create value economically and meet legal conditions such as employment standards and safety standards (Amoako et al., 2021). The ethical responsibilities compel the firms to promote equal rights for the employees and an accurate representation of their business practises, while the philanthropic responsibilities require firms to equally contribute to societies in the region (Amoako et al., 2021). In this study, the CSR theories are aligned with customer behaviour in the garment retail organisations of South Asian countries.

3.10 Conceptual Framework

The responsible organisation can develop trust and strengthen its relationship with its stakeholders on each level, (customers, investors, workers, and the communities in which it functions and operates), which generates higher value over time. Applying practises of sustainable business can assist in a reduction in expenditure and drive creativity and innovation; both are positive contributors to the bottom line (Sharabati, 2018). Constructed by the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI), the World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD), and the UN Global Compact, the Sustainability and Development Goals (SDGs) give instructions to organisations in what ways they could align their strategies and manage and measure their contribution to the SDGs' realisation (Mando, 2021). GRI assists businesses and governments internationally. It communicates the influence on critical issues of sustainability and glitches, such as governance, human rights, climate change, and social well-being. The UN Global compact facilitates organisations to carry out business with responsibility by adhering to 10 principles on labour environment, human rights, and anti-corruption and to take strategic measures to advance wider communal objectives, for instance, SDGs focusing on innovation and collaboration.

When a company, from its profit margin, retains the amount to be paid to labour to enhance its workers' earnings and incomes, it raises the workers' quality of life, ultimately improving the organisation's productivity and efficiency. CSR tends to improve the organisation's overall business operations. It also leads to the hypothesis that the current CSR policies used by the garment organisations of South Asian countries create a positive impact on the business (Cherep et al., 2019). On the other hand, Sharabati (2018) states that another advanced CSR practice is “greenwashing”. Greenwashing is the measure of organisations making themselves ecologically or communally aware. These companies deliberately mislead customers into trusting a product to be sustainable and ecologically friendly. Sharabati (2018) also opines that when the organisation is focused on applying CSR practises and corporate governance principles, for instance, gender equality or environmentally friendly operations, it tries to compete with its competitors. Companies build their corporate image in the community and could enhance their customer basis. Nowadays, customers are becoming environmentally friendly and prefer products and services that support green initiatives (Cherep et al., 2019). These findings also support the development of the above hypothesis and signify that CSR initiatives and actions lead to a positive impact on business organisations.

CSR is also significantly related to the profitability of the organisation. Lee and Chen (2018) argue that CSR is an essential conflict in all firms. Firms must deliberate about how they could accomplish their organisational objectives in terms of CSR. Similarly, CSR activities emphasise matter that makes sustainability reduce expenditure and enhance efficiencies and effectiveness. CSR initiatives may help public organisations earn a potential inclusion in the Dow Jones Sustainability World Index and comparable benchmarks (Lee and Chen, 2018). The Economist Intelligence Unit EIU study said that “corporate citizenship” (CC) is now considered

progressively significant in providing health to the company. However, most corporations find it difficult to calculate the return on their funds from the activities of public services. Cherep et al. (2019) opined that corporate social performance (CSP) looks to be largely connected with corporate financial performance (CFP) in comparison to market-grounded indicators, and reputation in terms of correlation between CSP guidelines and CFP is stronger than that between other CSP metrics. The analysis develops a higher certainty level in accordance with the CSP and CFP association, which is accurately supposed to be accomplished by several experts in business.

The following theory has been developed considering the above justifications: It is fundamental for organisations in South Asia to acknowledge the beneficial effects on the business of the present policies of CSR adopted by South Asian nations. CSR used in garment businesses has a positive impact as the firms work ethically and take care of the environment, which is essential in the long term. Customers who require firms to implement CSR practices likely pay more for the services and products. Hence, many socially conscious customers willingly pay more for the products considering ethics in as much as it supports environmental conservation or bans the use of products tested on animals. The added cost is an investment in the socially sustainable procurement of animal welfare, environmentally friendly, and responsible sourcing. CSR would have a positive impact since the firm will be able to charge the price premiums, and many firms will receive a competitive advantage based on their CSR. It is important for any firm to have a unique selling point (USP), something that is different from its competitors.

The current CSR practices do not have a positive impact on garment firms in South Asian countries as they must deal with increased manufacturing costs. CSR would lead to an increase

in cost if garment firms reduced carbon emissions and become eco-friendly, as these practices require significant investment in new technologies, which is an expensive exercise in the short term. Garment firms operate on different levels, including mass production and niche production. Thus, it is important for firms that mass produce fashion or garment products to look after their costs as these companies must achieve economies of scale (Velte, 2022). Consequently, bulk production may create a negative impact on the supplier due to delays in payments by the firm, which means expensive CSR processes are implemented.

H1: CSR practices employed by garment organisations in South Asian nations have a favourable impact on the sector.

This study evaluates how CSR helps brands build stronger consumer perceptions of their products. According to Goswami and Prajapati (2019), CSR describes how businesses behave in relation to their communities, social issues, and the environment. A positive influence of CSR activities on brand reputation and profitability motivates firms to engage in the activities. Wang (2018) reports that CSR exerts a positive impact on profitability, corporate reputation, and consumer attitudes among different firms and is a key marketing strategy that supports corporate sustainable development and enterprise business activities. Ko, Kim and Choi (2023) also demonstrate that a positive association exists between CSR perceptions and compassion, where consumers who perceive firms to be actively engaged in CSR activities are highly likely to demonstrate compassion towards it. Companies may be encouraged to engage in CSR activities to positively influence consumer perceptions and enhance their brand image and overall perceptions.

CSR policies determine the overall brand image and reputation of organisations. Acuti, Pizzetti and Dolnicar (2022) highlight a recent push from consumers to purchase products from

companies with ethical and sustainable values. Global customers, especially those from developed countries, are sensitive to issues of labour standards, environmental conservation, and corporate social responsibility (Acuti et al., 2022; Cezarino et al., 2022). When garment manufacturers incorporate CSR policies, there is enhanced potential for improving their brand reputation and leading to increased consumer credibility. In agreement with Cezarino et al. (2022), Islami, Rahyuni and Rukayyah (2024) note that CSR policies lead to better positioning in the marketplace and competitive edge. CSR efforts help enhance the company's image since they assist in remedying the social and environmental issues experienced in the garment manufacturing industry, including unfair working conditions, pollution, and exploitative work. Thus, organisations perform better than their competitors by adopting employment and environmental standards as proactive measures beyond compliance with legal requirements (Acuti et al., 2022; Islami et al., 2024). These practices can help businesses create partnerships and investment ventures, hence enhancing overall profitability. Li et al. (2020) suggests that there are emerging trends that show that CSR has a positive relationship with employee satisfaction and low turnover. Companies in the garment production industry that provide appropriate working conditions and career advancement resources develop satisfied employees and increase their productivity. From this perspective, Li et al. (2020), Cezarino et al. (2022), and Islami et al. (2024) show that CSR practises are the moral responsibilities of organisations and a successful business model that contributes to improving the image and reputation. By following CSR policies and regulations, garment-producing organisations in the South Asian region can improve their reputation and performance. These policies are beneficial to companies in the short term as they seek to improve their business relationship with consumers, stakeholders, and employees while at the same time guaranteeing long-term success.

H2: CSR policies have a positive effect on the brand image, company reputation, and profitability of garment-producing organisations in South Asia.

CSR policies accommodate the entire financial performance of the organisation and consider the two-way association as it is found to involve stakeholders, such as consumers, and their perception regarding the company's activities. Delmas et al. (2019) state that in terms of consumers specifically considering their purchase intention, CSR activities are an important notion since these activities are viewed from a product evaluation perspective. To illustrate further, Kraus et al. (2021) state that positive CSR activities enhance employee motivation and purchase decisions. This relationship between CSR activities and purchase intention is directly related. The consumer purchase intention plays a significant role for the company since their actions constitute maximum importance for sustainability. The purchasing intention of the consumer is important for the organisation since it is a contributory factor in terms of willingness to pay higher for the product if the company meet the basic tenets of consumer preferences. According to Musa et al. (2018), whenever a company fail in its CSR, there is the risk of increasing the disparity among its existing customers. The research hypothesis from these arguments is:

H3: CSR activities positively impact customer purchase patterns in garment-producing organisations in South Asia.

The hypothesis that CSR activities undertaken by garment organisations in South Asia have enhanced labour conditions is anchored on the existing literature. Olanipekun et al. (2020) note that CSR policies improve working conditions, a feature widely appreciated in various industries where employees before suffered from poor working conditions and other forms of labour exploitation. Olanipekun et al. (2020) and Bag and Dhamija (2023) concur that efforts in

ethically responsible manufacturing ensure decent wages and reasonable standard of working conditions. Also, ethically responsible manufacturing in the international apparel industry consists of good manufacturing processes and practices such as paying workers reasonable wages that are acceptable in the international market, ensuring minimum professional standards for the working environments of employees and banning child labour. Thorisdottir and Johannsdottir (2020) suggest that several industries, including the garment industry in South Asia, infamous for compromising safety and worker's rights, have been improved through the adoption of CSR principles. For instance, Nazrul and Rahman (2021) argue that garment manufacturers sourcing from developing countries such as Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan are influenced to incorporate CSR policies as demanded by buyers and consumers, perceived to have informed improvements in safety measures, workers' rights, and wages. These advancements safeguard workers and the image of garment firms in the global marketplace (Nazrul and Rahman, 2021; Thorisdottir and Johannsdottir, 2020). This hypothesis is examined in the present dissertation because the garment industry is one of the main pillars of the South Asian economy as it provides work for millions of residents of the region. This hypothesis aims to examine the extent to which CSR is used to enhance labour standards to ascertain the social contribution of these entities. The dissertation sets out to evaluate how CSR policies impact labour practises to add knowledge and develop a framework through which ethical standards in the garment industry are enhanced for the mutual benefit of commerce and the public. Based on the reviewed findings, the following hypothesis is developed for the study:

H4: The CSR activities undertaken by the organisations in the garment industry in South Asia have improved labour conditions.

Figure 6: Conceptual Framework

Source: (Author, 2024)

In Figure 6, the conceptual framework includes the hypotheses adopted in the current research study. The core argument of the conceptual framework is that the adoption of CSR policies and activities positively influences the growth of the garment manufacturing industry, the brand image and reputation of the firms, consumer purchase patterns, and adds benefit to society.

3.11 Summary of the Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

The synthesis of the insights examined in this chapter indicated various theoretical concepts aligned with the sociological, economic, and industrial aspects related to brand reputation and firm profitability. The reviewed theories are coercive isomorphism, mimetic isomorphism, institutional isomorphism, normative isomorphism, stakeholder theory of CSR,

legitimacy theory, Elkington's triple bottom line and Carroll's CSR (Figure 7). The key insights from the theoretical paradigms highlighted the importance of organisational structural forces and theoretical concepts from the environmental and social aspects. The review indicated four types of Isomorphism theories, including coercive isomorphism, mimetic isomorphism, institutional isomorphism, and normative isomorphism. The development of these different types of isomorphism can lead to isomorphic issues that can impede progress. Extremely strict governance is emphasised in the model of stakeholders, which emphasises that persons affected by the actions of the company make legitimate demands with the cooperation of stakeholders. As such, these internal conclusions could relate to client perception, business behaviours, business commitment, and customers' positive sensations of well-being about society and the overall business environment. The legitimacy theory also posited that a company and its targeted society were in a social contract. The concept of the triple bottom line was used to characterise the approach to evaluating company outcomes and results, which promotes the perspectives of the environment, the people, and the economy. Carroll's pyramid of CSR further concentrated on numerous elements of socioeconomic, moral, regulatory, and humanitarian responsibility that manufacturers of the organisation in every country need to accept. Based on the insights from the various theories, manufacturers take different steps to prevent these terms from violating to maintain a positive image for the industries.

Figure 7: Summary of Theories

Source: (Author, 2024)

The conceptual framework showed the link between CSR policies and activities and the positive impact on the industry, society, brand reputation, profitability, and consumer purchase patterns. The insights revealed different aspects of fundamental labour legislation, conditions of employment, well-being, protection, and risk and business continuity of chosen corporate organisations are analysed. The insights also revealed the objectives of retaining the goodwill of its consumer base by creating a positive brand image. The conceptual framework highlighted the

importance of CSR in enhancing the garment manufacturing industry and creating value for its respective consumer base.

The next chapter presents the methodology which processes and techniques are applied in collecting, analysing and interpreting data. Moreover, it describes the research paradigm and justifies why a specific paradigm was chosen. Further, the methodology describes the type of data collected and the tool or instruments used for the collection. The chapter explains how data was analysed, for example, using statistical tools, and guarantees that the procedures match the research goals.

Chapter 4: Research Methodology

4.1. Introduction

The research methodology is an organised process of resolving a research problem. Research methodology may also be defined as the study of methods used to obtain information (Padilla-Díaz, 2015). Snyder (2019) argues that research methodology highlights systematic processes used to solve the specific research problem. Research outcomes accepted widely are underpinned with effective research methodology that provides analysis, and a description of the data used in the study along with a further understanding of the research findings. The methodology possesses the potential to address the critical issues along with setting out a logical pathway for an effective research methodology. The path represented in the ‘honeycomb’ comprises six elements, particularly research approach, philosophy, design, data analysis, research strategy, and data collection, along with the interpretation methods (Figure 8). These aspects are stated in the honeycomb structure (Cherep et al., 2019). The honeycomb structure was applied due to the simplicity and linkage between various methods.

Figure 8: The Research Honeycomb Structure

Source: (Wilson, 2014).

The first stage of honeycomb involves research philosophy, described as a belief related to the way the data about a phenomenon is required to be collected, analysed, and used. The term epistemology, in contrast to the concept of doxology, encompasses a wide range of philosophies of the research approach. Pragmatism research philosophy was employed (Padilla-Díaz, 2015). A research approach is a plan followed or implemented to accomplish an appropriate result of the research. The three approaches used for studies are deductive, inductive, and abductive research approaches. For this research, an abductive approach was employed. A research strategy is an action plan that directs the activities while conducting a study that offers high-quality outcomes and thorough reporting (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). The research strategy helps to

remain focused, along with increasing the quality of the research. Since CSR is assessed from theory to practice, primary quantitative and qualitative data were used.

The fourth stage of the honeycomb research methodology is a research design. A research design is the general tactic selected to integrate components of the dissertation in a logical and coherent way and ensuring that the research problem is addressed effectively. The research design can be categorised into tool and objective based. However, the tool-based research design used is a cross-sectional research design while objective-based research design applies for explanatory research.

The fifth stage of the honeycomb model is data collection techniques. The data collection is the procedure for gathering the required information of the research. Interviews were conducted to collect in-depth qualitative information, whereas surveys gathered statistical information.

The 6th stage is data analysis techniques. The thematic analysis method was used. The term thematic analysis method allows interpretation of the information collected from the samples in the context of the research (Wotela 2017). The descriptive statistical method was used to examine the data gathered from the survey. Finally, SPSS data analysis software was used for inferential and descriptive statistics.

4.2. Research Philosophy

The research philosophy is the source, development, and nature of the knowledge in this research. In other words, research philosophy is a way data concerning a specific research issue is gathered (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009). A research philosophy is the worldview, and the epistemological stance adopted when conducting research. In this context, a research philosophy defines the method by determining how data was gathered, analysed, and interpreted.

4.2.1 *Ontology*

Ontology is the brand of philosophy that studies concepts such as existence, being, becoming, and reality. Ontology pertains to the assumptions that the research study holds regarding reality and what constitutes knowledge. Ontology determines how researchers perceive and make meaning of the object of their study and guides the research methodology (Tuohy et al., 2013). Ontology investigates what is understood as the world and the nature of the social reality, for instance the concept that the world is external and does not have any relationship with the social actors (Tuohy et al., 2013). An understanding of ontology is essential to selecting the research philosophy. According to Asokan, Yarime and Onuki (2020), ontology in research entails determining the existence and nature of reality. In methodological terms, ontology refers to the assumptions about the nature of reality and the ontology of things when defining ‘what exists’. For instance, realism assumes that there is a real-world to be discovered, while constructivism believes that reality is a construction of the mind and is relative to the perceiver (Asokan et al., 2020). Epistemological beliefs affect the kind of data analysed (Treiman, 2014). Ontology helps to ensure that the way a study is pursued, in terms of approach, methodological framework, and subsequent analysis of results, leads to consistency in how the study is conducted (Tuohy et al., 2013). Ontology is pivotal for identifying how research questions are defined and knowledge generation within a specific research study. Hence, this study shares an ontological view that enables the study to perceive truth from a singular view and multiple perceptions.

4.2.2 *Epistemology*

In the context of social reality, epistemology is the acquisition of valid knowledge. In business research, epistemology is mainly concerned with the source of knowledge. Specifically,

it dealt with nature, sources, possibilities, and limitations. The critical epistemological views are subjectivism and objectivism. Subjectivity directly correlates with interpretivism in considering the relationships between motivations and social interaction of the groups being observed (Hellman 2021). Objectivism is the belief that social phenomena are external in the social world and beyond the control of the values. Instead of interacting with the respondents, it will relate to the social world as a set of tangible objects and not subject to the daily changing relationships involving respondents (Gontier, 2018). The third perception is that epistemology can be measured and interpreted using specific tools and techniques to understand the truth.

The study aims to understand how consumers perceive the CSR activities of garment firms by examining how companies use CSR initiatives for value-added factors in business. In this context, human perception and its impact cannot be measured directly with a quantitative view (Berryman, 2019). Hence, this study has a shared epistemological view that enables understanding the truth from a specific tool used to interpret and measure the truth.

4.2.3 Research values or axiology

Axiology examines value judgments. Axiology is concerned with the examination of the value of the researcher on every level of the research procedure. Axiology deals with the value of the research (Goldman, 2018). Axiology in research is the evaluation of values regarding the study, often determining what the researcher defines as valuable in the study (Goldman, 2018). Also, axiology influences the choice of focus of the research, the selection of the methods to use, the analysis of the results, and the ethical issues to ensure that the research respects the participants (Goldman, 2018). This branch of research strategy determines whether researchers are attempting to elaborate on the world. The study reports researchers' values and biases along with the value-laden nature of information assembled from the domain. The research needs to

make underlying values known and report when discussing the axiology aspect of the research philosophy in qualitative research. This research examines CSR strategies and their impact on brand reputation and consumer behaviour. However, the brand and consumers are not associated with the researchers (Chakravartty, 2017). The axiology of this research does not influence the philosophical choice or strategy. Therefore, the philosophical choice is entirely based on the ontological and epistemological views.

4.2.4 Selecting the philosophy

Based on the ontological and epistemological perspective, the research philosophy can be based on positivism, interpretivism, realism and pragmatism. Positivism, as research philosophy, conforms to the belief that “factual” knowledge obtained by observation (the senses) involving measurement is actual (Mkansi and Acheampong, 2012). Positivism philosophy is based on quantifiable principles that help with numerical data analysis. As a philosophy, positivism conforms to the empiricist premise that arises from human experience. According to Marsonet (2019), positivist philosophy searches for facts instead of opinions to justify the outcome of the research. Positivism also deals with the performance of research in the social world that needs to be studied.

Interpretivism is a research philosophy that aims to apprehend the social reality of people from perception. However, while positivism aims to identify objective measures of facts, interpretivism embraces a human perspective with the nature of interpretive understanding (Chakravartty, 2017). This approach is practised in qualitative research, where scholars wish to understand how people constitute reality in their experiences, perceptions, and feelings. This argument explains why the interpretivism research philosophy was unsuitable for the current study. According to Saunders et al. (2015), interpretivism is used in disciplines such as

sociology, anthropology or psychology, and other social sciences where understanding experiences and phenomena are significant. Chakravartty (2017) and Saunders et al. (2015) agree that the centrality of interpretivism philosophy allows the development of detailed and nuanced accounts of social phenomena and processes. Thus, employing spiritual and psychological concepts of subjects' experiences enables the investigator to reveal meanings and regularities that might remain beyond the quantitative methods' notice. In addition, it allows for flexibility in terms of research conduct, especially when it comes to human behaviour. However, this study could be subjective, and its findings could not be generalised to other populations in other settings if an interpretivism research philosophy was employed.

Realism asserts that reality exists objectively but cannot be directly observed. According to Goldman Turner and Daly (2018), realism philosophy accepts the premise of cognitivism by noting that behaviour and structures within society are the cause of how humans interact with the world. Realism operates on two levels, where direct realism presupposes that the world is how people perceive it, and critical realism acknowledges that people's view of the world is mediated through social, cultural, and personal configurations (Breitbarth et al., 2015; Sturgiss and Clark, 2020). Realism helps analyse tangible and non-tangible facets of a phenomenon and provides a complete picture of the situation. However, Turyahikayo (2021) notes that realism philosophy can be limited because it entails empirical evidence and processes that constitute reality. This approach creates a working definition where fact and interpretation are indistinguishable. However, realism is unsuitable for researching the efficiency of CSR policies and ethical practices prevalent in South Asian businesses because the study focuses on perception, a contextual topic of business ethicality, and their impact on society.

Pragmatism is a research philosophy which emphasises facts and empirical data. According to Kaushik and Walsh (2019), pragmatism research philosophy supports the approach that calls for the application of several techniques, both the quantitative and the qualitative approaches, to minimise research questions and acknowledge that truth and knowledge are not a fixed entity but are dynamic and accrue from experience and consequences. Pragmatism philosophy is suitable to the current research because pragmatism permits the utilisation of both qualitative and quantitative techniques to measure and assess the CSR practice levels and the effectiveness of existing CSR policies that may improve business image and efficiency (Breitbarth et al., 2015). This philosophy enables the use of several research methods to analyse CSR's quantitative effect on profitability and examine people's societal and ethical perceptions of CSR (Usman and Amran, 2015). Borges and Revez (2019) and Hampson and McKinley (2023) argue that the strength of pragmatism is, therefore, flexibility. For instance, pragmatism does not restrict the research by a specific paradigm or technique but provides an approach that answers research questions (Ryan, 2018). Allemang, Sitter and Dimitropoulos (2022) state that the pragmatically oriented approach is effective in evaluating multifaceted and changeable connections between CSR activities and business results. Nonetheless, the vast applicability of pragmatism underestimates the philosophical integration (Allemang et al., 2022; Kaushik and Walsh, 2019). Because of pragmatism's emphasis on the outcome, theoretical issues may be left unresolved, which hinders the analysis (Vogl, Schmidt and Zartler, 2019). Despite these weaknesses, pragmatism is the only appropriate philosophy because it would allow one to examine CSR's effects in detail. Thus, it links a firm's financial performance to specific social values with an equal amount of rigour and offers a holistic view of the relation between ethical practices and a firm's revenues and image.

4.3. Research Approach

The research approach is a process used to obtain the results of the research. Moreover, the research approach allows the investigator to perceive the problem from a specific view (Chakravartty 2017). The research approaches allow the selection of the data collection tool, and analysis. The three primary approaches are deductive, inductive, and abductive.

4.3.1 Inductive approach

The inductive approach to conducting research involves collecting data and observations and identifying patterns, themes, and theories. This method is standard in qualitative research, where the goal is to develop new theories instead of proving or disproving existing theories (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). In addition, Fardet, Lebretonchel and Rock (2023) argue that the inductive approach is used when the purpose is to map reality and understand unknown effects and how they are interconnected. Nonetheless, Vogl, Schmidt and Zartler (2019) state that the main drawback is that it may be rather unorganised at the initial stage, and thus, the result may be inconclusive or contradictory. Waschl and Burns (2020) and Woiceshyn and Daellenbach (2018) agree that conclusions arising from inductive research are usually local to the findings collected during the investigation. Given this research concerning the efficiency of CSR policies and their benefits to society and the profitability of businesses, the inductive approach was unsuitable for use, for this study involved evaluations and analyses of CSR practises in operation. A formal approach, such as abductive, is appropriate to test the link between CSR policies and the performance of businesses.

4.3.2 Deductive approach

This research approach is developed from a theory or hypothesis and seeks to confirm or reject the hypothesis through empirical observation or data collection. From general to specific, a

hypothesis is formed from previous knowledge and evidence is gathered, which is eventually confirmed or rejected (Wang et al., 2020). A deductive approach is typical for quantitative research design as it aims to investigate the relationships between variables formally and systematically and with statistics (Wang et al., 2020). Another strength of the deductive research approach is that it results in highly structured research papers. As it begins with a formulated hypothesis, the research is relatively easy, and results are generally applicable. A deductive approach may skew the results toward support of pre-established hypotheses and fail to consider other possibilities. It also depends a great deal on the given hypothesis and may confine the research within a narrow framework if the hypothesis is incorrect (Khatri et al., 2024). Thus, regarding this dissertation's aim of evaluating the CSR policies and ethical practises in the South Asian business environment, the deductive approach is irrelevant as it tries to apply the general rules for the micro-environmental factors. Since the importance is made of practicality and various effects on society, a rather free-spirited approach is needed, where pragmatism outperforms the deduction method.

4.3.3 Abductive approach

This research employed an abductive approach. While inductive reasoning starts with data and attempts to develop theories, deductive reasoning starts from theories and tries to validate them through data (Fisher, 2018). According to Sarfraz et al. (2018), the abductive approach permits an elastic approach to developing knowledge, allowing the cycling of the data and theory to gain better insight. Abductive reasoning is most beneficial in research scenarios where the context is partly understood and there is no universal theory to account for the observed phenomena (Brown, 2001; Fisher, 2018). The flexibility of the abductive approach is one of the most significant advantages. Flexibility allows for changes to be made when needed in

the research. Also, flexibility fosters creativity by allowing the development of unique hypotheses that might not have been arrived at when contained in an existing paradigm. However, Liczmańska Kopcewicz et al. (2019) highlight that abductive research is often not conclusive. In this regard, the method considers likely explanations instead of the probabilities of the event under analysis, leading to ambiguous results (Zalaghi and Khazaei, 2016). There is bound to be bias while choosing an explanation. In the current research, where the impact of the CSR policies and all the ethical standards in South Asian businesses are evaluated and analysed, an abductive approach is highly appropriate. The hypothesis is tested along with the data by moving between data and theory. The choice of the abductive strategy enables flexibility in analysing the complex interdependence between CSR activities, the companies' financial performance, and emerging social expectations. For this reason, the current research adopted the abductive approach to derive a meaningful analysis from the data.

4.4 Research Strategy

A research strategy is a step-by-step action plan that guides the activities and ideas, allowing consistent and timely execution and reporting of the findings. This research approach outlines the reason for the study and ways to achieve the desired objectives (Mackey and Gass 2015). The main types of research strategies are qualitative, quantitative, mixed strategy, and action-oriented research (Bauer, 2014). However, Wotela (2017) argue that research strategies can be segregated into quantitative, qualitative, and mixed research strategies. This study adopted a mixed research strategy.

Qualitative research is a technique that involves gathering categorical data on human activities, processes, and events based on interviews, focus-group discussions, and observations. This method is used to gain a rather qualitative, rich and detailed understanding of how people

think, why they act and what they feel (Flick, 2015). Additionally, Busetto, Wick and Gumbinger (2020) argue that qualitative research aims to understand the meanings. One of the strengths of qualitative research is that it provides in-depth information and descriptions of contexts. Haven and Van Grootel (2019) argue that the qualitative method is flexible as it allows adjusting the approach to data collection depending on the research problem, thus achieving positive results. However, Shelton, Philbin and Ramanadhan (2022) argue that the qualitative method is based on subjective assessments, is less easy to reproduce and compare results, and has substantial potential for bias in data analysis. Qualitative data may take longer to gather and analyse than quantitative data, especially when undertaking a study with a small and specific sample size (; Busetto et al., 2020; Haven and Van Grootel, 2019). Since the current research sought to evaluate the effectiveness of CSR policies and their relationship with business profitability in South Asian organisations, the qualitative method alone could not allow testing of the hypothesis. This study evaluated tangible business outcomes, including business performance measures and social effects, which lend themselves to quantitative measurement. The qualitative research method offered information about societal perceptions but could not provide adequate confirmation of the existence and strength of the interrelationships between CSR practises, business image and profitability. A mixed method was appropriate for the overall response to the research questions.

The quantitative research method is concerned with numbers and hence involves using numbers to arrive at specific findings. The survey enables hypothesis testing, variable quantification, and substantiated conclusions (MacDonald, 2012). The quantitative method is formal and quantitative and involves data collection techniques such as questionnaires, experiments, and probability sampling techniques yielding numerical data from large

populations. Ledford and Gast (2014) and MacDonald (2012) note that quantitative research allows generalisations of results to other populations and accuracy in measuring the relation between variables. The quantitative data enables the validation of theories based on objectivity and reliability in a way that distils the results in clear and statistically measurable terms. However, Bauer et al. (2021) suggest that the quantitative method cannot place individuals and their behaviours and the social environment within any context. From this perspective, qualitative research is more flexible than quantitative research because it does not set out fixed categories of observation and does not assume that all individuals' experiences are the same (Bauer et al., 2021). In this study, where the goal was to evaluate the effects of CSR policies on specific societal effects and organisational profitability, the quantitative data collection methods were insufficient to solve the research issue. Whereas quantification was used to assess business performance and perform hypothesis testing, understanding the context of societal effects and ethical behaviour was achievable only qualitatively. Hence, incorporating qualitative and quantitative techniques gathers information on issues of CSR and societal perceptions.

The action-oriented research strategy emphasises addressing practical issues in day-to-day life by involving researchers and subjects. An action-oriented strategy is conducted with the help of participants, where intervention is implemented, and the results evaluated in organisations and communities. The strengths of action research include its applicability and the power to deliver results instantly (Tuohy et al., 2013). Moreover, action research promotes the implementation of solutions since it incorporates other perspectives on the solutions. On the contrary, Shani and Coghlan (2021) note that an action-oriented strategy is highly susceptible to bias as the closeness of researchers with participants is likely to compromise objectivity. Tuohy et al. (2013) highlight that the action-oriented research strategy is very time-consuming. The

setting of the intervention also impacts the generalisation of the outcomes. This research was designed to evaluate CSR policies and their effects on society, and an action-oriented research strategy was inappropriate. Thus, the current research was an assessment-oriented approach rather than attempting to provide solutions and introduce changes to practice, which is valuable from an observation or analysis point of view.

This study employed a mixed research strategy. A mixed research strategy entails quantitative and qualitative approaches, proposing a broader solution to a given problem. This approach enables the collection and analysis of numerical and non-numerical information to develop broader results (Ledford and Gast, 2014). Mixed research can investigate phenomena with quantitative results and human feelings, behaviour, and opinions, and it can be used for various research questions. While using a mixed research strategy, Choy (2014) argues that the approach allows cross-checking of the collected data, enhancing the validity and richness of the information. This strategy is also flexible since different methods are used based on the requirements of a given research, which is a mix of quantitative and qualitative research. Şahin and Ozturk (2019) and Taherdoost (2022) agree that a mixed method offers a comprehensive systematic approach to analysing the connection between variables; in some cases, efficiency is supplemented by context, meaning, and perception. However, Brunton et al. (2017) suggest that a mixed research strategy is time-consuming and costs many resources. In this regard, collecting both types of research can be time-consuming and resource-extensive, making it challenging to execute and analyse. In addition, Yin (2017) argues that the qualitative and quantitative data integration process can be difficult because it deals with the integration of different data collection and analysis instruments. To attain the study's objectives, this research used a mixed research strategy because it was most appropriate and practicable. The research entailed utilising

quantitative approaches to ascertain the extent of profitability that CSR had on the organisations involved while capturing the effecting social/ethical considerations better explained using qualitative data. In this strategy, it was possible to access different aspects of the impact of CSR on business performance and consumer perception, thereby developing a comprehensive analysis.

4.5 Research Design

The research design is the overall strategy chosen for integrating various components of the dissertation in a logical and coherent way. The research design is classified into tool-based and objective-based research design (Al-Ababneh, 2020). Hong et al. (2018) demonstrate that the objective-based research design includes exploratory, explanatory, and descriptive research designs. The tool-based research design includes cross-sectional, experimental, observations, systematic review case study, and reflectional research design.

4.5.1 Exploratory research design

Exploratory research design is used when the extent of knowledge of a research problem is not well known. According to Wang et al. (2020), exploratory design is used to generate ideas, develop hypotheses, and find patterns using creative and less structured techniques such as literature searches, interviews, or focus groups. However, Ferrell et al. (2019) argue that exploratory design is not designed to achieve a specific hypothesis, effect size, and efficiency but to establish a foundation for advanced research on the given topic. Wang et al. (2020) and Ferrell et al. (2019) concur that exploratory research is characterised by the flexibility of the process. This design is generally suitable where little is known about the area examined and where new frameworks or theories are produced. However, Heikkilä, Bouwman and Heikkilä (2018) suggest that exploratory research is unstructured, and the findings cannot be generalised. The findings

are an impressionistic interpretation and generalisation, which do not provide specific solutions and proof for or against some hypotheses. Therefore, exploratory research design is less capable of clarifying cause-and-effect relations (Ferrell et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2020). Regarding the research questions of the current dissertation, which are, for instance, if and how CSR is a competitive advantage and the relationship between CSR policies and consumer behaviour and CSR effects on society, an exploratory research design was not applicable. In this context, it entails developing testable hypotheses and establishing crucial CSR policies to address and determine well-established CSR activities and their link with organisational performance. These objectives require a systematised and methodical analytic method, which incorporates numerical evidence and fundamental theory. Hence, an exploratory design could not involve features which do not cover the nature of the research questions in detail or the specification of new theories or ideas to be explained or tested.

4.5.2 Explanatory research design

An explanatory research design aims to explain the aspects of the study. According to Al Kilani and Kobziev (2016), an explanatory research design seeks to explain the elements of the study in a detailed way. The explanatory research design does not provide conclusive results, but it helps to understand the issue efficiently (Nazir and Islam, 2020). An explanatory research design is standard in determining causality by testing hypotheses and explanations of why events occur. Chatzoglou et al. (2017) suggest that explanatory research design majorly uses numerical data to create relationships and prove the cause between variables. Though there is a significant emphasis on a methodology that utilises direct variables to analyse, Taherdoost (2022) argue that explanatory design attempts to provide a bigger picture as opposed to reconstructing the small picture. From the objectives of this research, which is to evaluate CSR as a source of competition

edge, the impression on the business image, stakeholders, and the association between CSR policies and consumers' behaviour, an explanatory design was not appropriate for the research. The research required quantitative and qualitative data to capture the social impact of CSR. Explicitly relying only on explanatory case-based research methods would have helped to narrow the context and ethical aspects of CSR, which are core to the research.

4.5.3 Descriptive research design

Descriptive research aims to describe a population, situation, and phenomenon accurately and systematically. The aim of using this research design is to obtain the answer of what, where, when, and how, but not why. Descriptive research designs can be used to investigate variables using a variety of research methods. According to Sánchez-Gómez et al. (2016), a descriptive research design is used when the research problem has already been researched earlier but lacks effective descriptions. The descriptive research design is appropriate for this dissertation because it presents an overall picture of the prevailing CSR practises and their outcome regarding the organisational image, profitability, and society. Doyle et al. (2020) argue that a descriptive design is fixed purely on the documentation of phenomena as they are and without the adjustment of variables, which makes it appropriate to capture the relationships between known variables when conducting research (Musa et al., 2018). The descriptive design helped to observe and gather data on the CSR initiatives and assess patterns in implementing practises and their impact on business and society. This design supports quantitative approaches such as determining business profitability and exploring the perceived notion of stakeholders on CSR. The strength of this design is that the relationships do not need to be causal, which is consistent with the research objectives while aiming to give the largest picture of CSR as it currently stands. The descriptive design provides the framework for a broad perception of how CSR

policies work and their outcome, which is essential in addressing the research questions (Doyle et al., 2020; Musa et al., 2018). Thus, the descriptive approach was justified since it allowed for a comprehensive analysis of existing external CSR policies and their results.

4.5.4 Cross-sectional study

A cross-sectional research design is used to analyse data on the variables collected at one given time across a pre-defined subset. Although cross-sectional research involves no experimentation, it enables an understanding of physical and social outcomes. Unlike an experimental study, a cross-sectional study does not involve repeated data collection from a chosen population. A study conducted by Lu et al. (2017) on the workforce of Guangdong, China, used a cross-sectional study design. The study aimed to find a relationship between job satisfaction, work stress, work-family conflict and turnover intention among healthcare workers. This study designed a survey where the data about the variables was collected by involving participants at once. Chen et al. (2020) conducted a study focusing on understanding people's behaviour regarding hand hygiene and mask usage during the COVID-19 pandemic. This study conducted a structured, close-ended interview combined with a survey questionnaire. Cross-sectional design entails data collection at a particular point in time and can identify relations between variables but cannot show temporal changes. This research, which sought to evaluate the efficiency of CSR policies and the extended effects on the business image, consumer behaviour, and society, could not use a cross-sectional design. The study needed a broader method that would be able to explore temporal changes that had not been captured through the cross-sectional design.

4.5.5 Experimental study design

Experimental research design uses manipulation of independent variables to study their impact on dependent variables under controlled circumstances. Its primary purpose is to determine the cause-and-effect relationship as it involves testing hypotheses in a systematic manner where details such as randomisation and control group are adopted systematically to reduce the impact of bias (Skoczyńska-Prokopowicz, 2016). This approach helps to assess the net effect of measures or therapies. Gallego-Álvarez and Quina-Custodio (2016) and Ferrell et al. (2019) concur that experimental design is accurate and objective, allowing measurement of the causality between variables and controls. In addition, the design is replicable and ideally suited to scientific experimentation (Gallego-Álvarez and Quina-Custodio, 2016; Skoczyńska-Prokopowicz, 2016). On the contrary, Nazir and Islam (2020) note its limitations in real-life scenarios due to the artificialness of a controlled environment and complex social events, creating difficulties in standardising all factors. As for the current research, which sought to evaluate the CSR policies and their resultant effects on image, profitability, and society in South Asian organisations, an experimental design was not feasible. CSR is an extensive concept that factors in numerous variables, such as stakeholders' perceptions, business ethics, and impacts on communities, and can hardly be established in a laboratory environment where all the variables are held constant.

4.6 Population and Sampling for Survey and Interview

The selection of data sources ensures the authenticity of the entire data collection process. The selection of data resources includes the identification of fields and the data collection procedure (Nazir and Islam, 2020). For primary data collection-based research methods, this

process involves population selection and sampling. In the next section, the population selection and sampling process are discussed.

4.6.1 Population Selection

As per the research aims and objectives, the collected data helped to understand how the consumer perceived the CSR activities of the originations through examining their purchasing behaviour. The data helped to explore business strategies that can use CSR practices to add value to business. Population selection means identifying individuals or entities from which the data is collected in a research investigation (Cooper et al., 2018). This group can be referred to as the population and comprises people who fulfil the criteria of the given study. In general, the appropriateness of sample selection guarantees that the results obtained apply to the whole population or male/female subgroups, respectively (Pliakas et al. 2017). Some of the methods employed include sampling, which involves choosing a sub-sample of the population based on age, gender, geographical location, and business sector to make the population conform to the research goals.

In this research, consumers and managers were targeted as the main subjects in data collection in the CSR context. Companies wish to influence consumer behaviours through CSR efforts; thus, their selection was essential in appreciating how these efforts influence consumers' perceptions, purchase intentions, and attitudes toward brands. Through the information collected from consumers, the research can evaluate whether CSR practises act as a source of competitiveness and impact consumer behaviour (Hossan, Dato'Mansor and Jaharuddin, 2023). Managers also form a critical population due to their roles in developing, executing, and assessing the CSR strategies within organisations. Managerial perceptions provide the research with insight into CSR and how ethical and strategic choices impact CSR policies (Pliakas et al.

2017). This dissertation focuses on the managers' perspective on internal factors that drive and may hinder CSR, in addition to the appearance of CSR as a value-added process from the managers' viewpoints (Cooper et al., 2018). Thus, by studying the consumer and the manager, the research gains an understanding and a clear picture of the effects of CSR implementation from both the executor's and the receiver's views. CSR's approach to management focuses on business image and profitability, with specific reference to the improvements the concept can bring to the enterprise's performance and society.

This study aims to understand CSR policies applied across South Asian countries while evaluating their effectiveness and impact on South Asian society to identify positive CSR strategies. Hence, the chosen population was the people of South Asian Countries. The South Asian countries covered in this study include India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Nepal, Bhutan, Maldives, and Sri Lanka. The criteria for choosing the countries are population, size, and levels of economic development. For instance, India has the largest population of approximately 1.4 billion and has a significant impact on this region (Kumari et al., 2020). Two countries, each with more than 200 million in population, are Pakistan and Bangladesh (Li et al., 2020). Measuring Gross Domestic Product, India stands on top by contributing over 80 per cent of total output. In this selection, many cultures and economies are covered, making the region demographically and economically critical (Li et al., 2020). According to Schuster et al. (2016), among South Asian countries, the most exposed population to CSR activities are the people of India, Pakistan, Bangladesh and Sri Lanka. Therefore, the chosen population of this research was the citizens of South Asian countries, particularly India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Nepal, Bhutan, Maldives, and Sri Lanka.

4.6.2 Sampling Process

Sampling involves choosing several individuals or objects to represent the entire population in each research project. Similarly, sampling is a process through which a predetermined number of observations are taken from a large pool of population (Scott, 2018). Two critical methods of sampling are probability and nonprobability sampling. Probability sampling is a technique where participants from a large population are randomly selected. On the other hand, non-probability sampling is a technique where samples are selected based on subjective judgments. Convenience sampling is a non-probability sampling technique that includes sample selection from the population since they are conveniently available. The mixed sampling method is used when the target population is specific, and the availability of the participants and time for sampling is limited.

A convenience sampling method enabled the participants' selection. A non-probability sampling method involved convenience sampling (Rangan, Chase and Karim, 2015). Convenience sampling was used, whereby the survey link was shared on different social media platforms to reach consumers or employees in garment manufacturing companies in India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Nepal, Bhutan, Maldives, and Sri Lanka. Because of the time limitations, the survey had to reach many participants within one week; therefore, the convenience sampling method was the most appropriate. The goal was to focus on people who could be reached on the World Wide Web and fit the characteristics of the participants. The survey was administered and followed by an online data collection portal that was active for 60 days, and participant responses were only considered for those obtained whilst the portal was active, yielding a total of 370 participants. Convenience sampling was the most plausible method because of the time constraint (Render and Stair Jr, 2016). As the primary concern was to get many responses within

a short period, social media was viable because it covered a large sample of people in different areas. However, for efficiency in the data retrieval process, this sampling method was most appropriate as it enabled the study to cover a large of respondents from the targeted regions, hence the sample size required for quantitative analysis.

Managers of garment manufacturing companies located in South Asia, particularly India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Nepal, Bhutan, Maldives, and Sri Lanka were chosen. Johansen et al. (2016) conducted interviews with managers from 10 different organisations to understand the legitimacy of the strategies required for overcoming various challenges. Managers of every organisation are not exposed to similar situations and decision-making conditions. Consequently, choosing managers from different business organisations allowed the research to consider many potential problems in the business environment.

These managers were selected due to their positions in organisations that engage in CSR activities in the South Asia region. The samples were selected from firms with known commitments to CSR activities in the garment industry and sourced from industry databases, business listings, and websites that list the firms' CSR credentials. This approach helped filter out all those organisations that were not interested in implementing CSR in their companies and those that operate outside the domain of this study. Convenience sampling was used where the participants were chosen because they agreed to be involved. To overcome the bias, including lack of representation, the selected managers came from different companies and locations, including South Asian countries, particularly India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, and Sri Lanka (Render and Stair Jr, 2016). To further eliminate bias in the research, the companies and managers selected were committed to CSR activities.

In this research, a detailed consent form clearly stating the purpose of this research was sent to 20 organisations by email and of these, ten organisations showed interest in this research. Selecting ten managers for the interviews was justified based on their responsibility in formulating and implementing CSR strategies in their organisations (Staniškienė and Stankevičiūtė, 2018). Managers are responsible for making decisions related to the implementation of CSR and can provide valuable information about CSR's effects on business image, profitability, and society. The study conducted ten interviews to provide the variability of responses capture the various managers' experiences (Staniškienė and Stankevičiūtė, 2018). This number is ideal to balance the quantity of data collected with the quality of the analysis while keeping the time and resources for research activity.

4.7 Data Collection Process

The data collection process can be classified into primary data collection and secondary data collection. Primary data comprises the first-hand information gathered from the source using special techniques like questionnaires, interviews, or experiments designed to solve the research objectives (Tobi and Kampen, 2018). This data is also original and specific and is accurate for the context of the study. On the other hand, Abutabenjeh and Jaradat (2018) state that secondary data collection involves materials gathered by someone else, which may include books, reports, and online databases. Although secondary data is easier to acquire and cheaper compared to primary data, it is not suitable for the current research (Abutabenjeh and Jaradat, 2018). The distinction is that primary data is collected for the study, while secondary data is previously gathered data that is reused.

The qualitative and quantitative data were collected using interviews and surveys, respectively. Qualitative data was collected through semi-structured interviews with ten

managers about CSR strategies and their views on the impact. Semi-structured interviews allowed the subjects to speak about the way they perceive the studied problems (Belina, 2023). The purpose of the interview guide is to collect managerial views about CSR management based on their experience, knowledge, and understanding. For instance, the interviews are used to collect the responses from a small group of participants (Usman and Amran, 2015). The managerial views helped to understand the underlying factor of strategic selection of CSR activities and their perceived interconnection with the brand image. In the semi-structured open-ended questions, the respondents were provided with a set of interview questions. The questions used for the interview method included questions about the work background and experience as a manager, questions about the perceived relationship between brand image and the impact of CSR activities, and questions about the strategic implementation and CSR activities and their impact on business advantages. The questions about the work background and experience as a manager helped to understand the knowledge and experience of the participant. Questions about the perceived relationship between brand image and the impact of CSR activities answered the primary questions. For instance, participants were asked about the major benefits of CSR activities for their organisation, which helped to understand the managerial perspective on CSR activities. Questions were also formulated to comprehend some of the key influential CSR policies and activities that have proven to be highly beneficial both for the organisation and society. Moreover, participants were asked if local community activity participated in the CSR activities.

The prospective participants were emailed and informed of the research aim and purpose and asked to take part in the interviews. Once consent was granted, interview appointments were set, and the interviews were conducted online using platforms, including Zoom, due to

geographical restrictions and convenience. Interview sessions took 50-58 minutes, allowing participants to comprehensively share their views and opinions. The interview questions were structured using an interview guide comprising ten open-ended questions (Appendix 2). The open-ended questions enabled differentiation of the topics between the managers while also enabling elaboration where there was some similarity in responses by different managers (Adeoye-Olatunde and Olenik, 2021). This format made it easier to expand on areas to get a detailed understanding of the participants' stand on CSR. For a systematic approach, all the interviews were conducted with the participant's permission, and the details of the interviews were recorded and documented in writing while concurrently taking notes during the conversation with the participant. The sessions were taped to enable word-for-word analysis. Semi-structured interviews were suitable for the study because they offer both a flexible and a guided approach (Adeoye-Olatunde and Olenik, 2021). This method ensured that all the major points concerning CSR were explained while allowing the manager to expand on issues, giving depth to the discussion.

The quantitative data was gathered using a survey. The survey questionnaire was structured in such a way that multiple-choice questions were administered to participants (Appendix 1). The participants were required to select an option from a set of multiple answers. For ordinal and scale-based options, the Likert scales were used in the survey (Treiman, 2014). The survey questionnaire had three subdivisions, demographic details, the experience, and the views of the participants about different brands. In the demographical data, information about the nationality of the participants, the participant's age, gender, and socio-economic status were collected (Appendix 1). Information about the participants' experience or exposure to different CSR activities was collected. The scoring matrix was included in the survey questionnaire to

enable the participants to prioritise different attributes of CSR activities (Sánchez-Gómez et al. 2016). In addition, the participants were asked about their purchasing decisions and preferences for different brands. In this section, information about consumer purchasing behaviour, intention, preference for a brand, and perception of the brands was collected.

The data collection through the survey entailed developing an online survey that comprised 25 questions, which were administered to the respondents. The participants were requested to fill out a structured questionnaire. Three types of questionnaires can be used to collect data: structured, unstructured, and semi-structured (Sheehan, 2018). In a structured questionnaire, each question has multiple options. To give the answer to a particular question, the respondent selects one option from the given set. In the structured questionnaire, the options are developed by considering all the possible answers given by participants. For example, Nazir and Islam (2020) used a questionnaire to identify the influence of CSR-related activities of a company on the work engagement of the employees. A survey questionnaire was used to measure the employees' work engagement and working behaviour. The structured questionnaire allows the collection of specific responses, including ordinal, nominal, and numerical data, where quantitative analysis is executed easily. However, the disadvantage is that, in the structured formation, the participant's response is limited to only the given options. If any new possible responses are not considered while forming the options, it adversely impacts the data collection process (Groenland and Dana, 2019). The unstructured or open-ended questionnaire allows for collecting data by receiving the responses of the participants based on their own opinions. Participants can freely answer the questions in their wording and sentences. According to the study conducted by Budur and Demir (2019), the survey questionnaire for the employees needs specific option-based questions that provide the opportunity to collect the nominal and

ordinal data for the measurement. Multiple choice-based structured questionnaires involving the Likert scale allowed the collection to be the collected specific, measurable, and reliable within a minimum period.

For the survey tool used for collecting the data of the consumer's, structured questionnaires were used in this research. The data questions of the questionnaire used for the consumer survey were segregated into three groups. First, questions about the demographic background include age, gender, involvement in the market as consumers, location and others. The second section consisted of questions about where the consumers perceive CSR as a brand image of the business organisations and how the CSR activities influence the brand image. The third section consisted of questions about whether the purchasing behaviour and preferences of the consumers change based on the perceived CSR activities and how the purchasing behaviour is influenced. For the first set of demographic questions, both nominal and ordinal options were used. Nominal options are used for questions of location and gender. The ordinal options covered age and involvement in the industry as consumers. Moreover, yes-no questions were used in the survey questionnaire. The nominal questions focused on brand choices concerning CSR-related activities. The favourite brand types were asked as part of nominal questions. After that, a question was asked regarding the brand's selection procedure. To understand the opinion of the participants regarding the best CSR practices, participants were asked about the most important reasons companies became involved in CSR activities. Nominal and Likert scale-based ordinal options were used to examine where the consumers perceive CSR as a brand image of the business organisations and how the CSR activities influence the brand images. The Likert scale questions allowed the collection of responses with the associated level of measures, for the questions about whether the purchasing behaviour and preferences of the consumers change

based on the perceived CSR activities and how the purchasing behaviour is influenced, images nominal and Likert scale-based ordinal options were used. Participants were asked about their perception of product price when purchasing clothing products. Additionally, participants were asked if buying products from brands has a good reputation and value in their community.

The survey link was shared on popular social media networks, including Facebook, LinkedIn, and the WhatsApp group where the author is a member so that the target respondents could be reached easily within the set time frame. Following the preparation of the survey, the respondents were given sixty days to fill out the questionnaires with reminders sent in intervals. These questions were closed questions and Likert scale questions with quantitative analysis of the opinions and participants' behaviour about the CSR practises. They were also not time-consuming since each survey took approximately 10–15 minutes to complete making it easier for people to participate. A survey was suitable for this study since data could be collected from many participants (Tobi and Kampen, 2018). The survey also provided an understanding of CSR in the context of business image and consumer behaviour that could be collected in an organised and streamlined fashion, allowing for easier comparisons and determining of trends (Edinger-Schons et al., 2019; Treiman, 2014). Furthermore, because the study intended to reach out to many participants across various regions, surveys were useful since they are relatively cheaper and easier to conduct (Sarfraz et al., 2018). Overall, 300 responses were realised within 60 days.

The bias that may occur because of using social media in the distribution of the survey was avoided by posting the survey on different social media platforms such as Facebook, LinkedIn, and WhatsApp groups, and directly to participants. Social media also eliminated cases of over-sampling of groups in the population and an area, thus enhancing the representativeness of the data (Edinger-Schons et al., 2019). Furthermore, screening questions were used to filter

the respondents to only collect data from those who meet the study requirements minimising irrelevant responses. To increase the likelihood of completing the survey, the participants were given the option of being entered into a draw to be awarded a prize (Sarfraz et al., 2018). However, these incentives had their disadvantages, which were associated with increased response rates. For instance, some participants may complete the survey in haste or provide less careful responses due to the desire to obtain the incentive. To offset this, there was data cleansing whereby incomplete responses were eliminated from the study (Sarfraz et al., 2018). Various social media platforms were used to ensure that the survey was taken by people from different parts, particularly India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Nepal, Bhutan, Maldives, and Sri-Lanka, thereby eliminating geographical and culturally derived biases. The respondent's identity was kept anonymous while conducting the surveys to eliminate pressures that could influence the results, thus enhancing the study's credibility. The rationale for using social media is that a large, geographically dispersed population can be reached in a fast and cost-efficient way, which was essential due to the time constraints of the research. Even with these drawbacks, it was possible to use the method to collect data from many participants in a relatively short time.

4.8 Data Analysis Techniques

Data analysis in the context of this research relates to the systematic procedures of analysing and interpreting the collected data during a research study. According to Treiman (2014), the method of data analysis depends on the properties of data collected through the data collection procedures. Data analysis strategies allow meaningful deductions, identification of patterns, and answering the research questions (Lang and Altman, 2015). Different methods of analysis can be employed for qualitative and quantitative data. For quantitative data analysis, there are methods like statistical analysis, regression, and descriptive analysis as they help to

quantify the level of the relationship in the data (Saunders et al., 2015). The SPSS data analysis software has been used for both descriptive and inferential statistics to enhance the accuracy of the data analysis procedure. For the qualitative data, approaches such as thematic analysis and content analysis are used to identify patterns in answers given by the participants in the study. The ideal data analysis strategies enhanced the reliability and validity of the research outcomes. Appropriate choices assist in making pragmatic conclusions in line with the research questions (Saunders et al., 2015; Treiman, 2014). In addition, proper analysis methods help to minimise bias in the data and allow for correct and accurate interpretation of the collected data. In this study, appropriate data analysis methods allowed data gathered on the CSR strategies and their influence within businesses and consumer groups to be appropriately assessed for final recommendation in line with the findings.

4.8.1 Descriptive statistics

For the quantitative data, inferential statistics and descriptive statistics were applied. The raw data was stored and sorted in an MS-Excel file (Sarfraz et al., 2018). In the excel database, each variable associated with each research question was set as a field or a column of the database. Under each column, the responses of the participants for the question associated with that field were stored. In the database, each horizontal record represents the responses of a single participant. The responses were coded using a range of numerical values. The coded database was exported to SPSS software. The frequency and percentage distribution were used for nominal variables. The display of data that specifies the percentage of observations that occur for each data point or group of data points is a percentage frequency distribution. The method of generating a distribution of percentage frequency analysis procedure involved specifying the total number of observations to be represented (Render and Stair, 2016). The process included

dividing the number of observations within each data point (Saunders et al., 2015). On the other hand, the process of evaluating and using such statistics is observed as descriptive statistics. Moreover, as discussed by Lang and Altman (2015), descriptive statistics are characterised by purpose of summarising a sample from inferential statistics or inductive statistics, then using the data to learn about the population that the sample of data is assumed to represent. The analysis of central tendency and the analysis of dispersion are the two major parts of descriptive statistics (Saunders et al., 2015). For ordinal variables and scales, both centralities of tendencies and dispersion were calculated. To measure the centrality of tendencies, the mean, median, and mode were used. To measure the dispersion, the range, variance, and standard deviation have been used. The presentation of the centrality of tendencies and dispersion of the range has been conducted using the tabular data presentation method. The data of the frequency and percentage distribution of the tabular presentation and the graphical presentation have been utilised. In the section on graphical presentation, both bar charts and pie charts are used for visually aided graphical presentation.

4.8.2 Inferential statistics

This data is cross-sectional data where the data of exposure and outcome both have been measured under a co-creational statistical model (Schuster et al., 2016). The purpose of the inferential statistics is to evaluate the impact of applied CSR Policies on South Asian society across South Asian countries identifying positive CSR strategies. The CSR model and its impactful element have different co-relational independent factors that can impact society and the views of consumers through both associative and non-associative ways. Clearly, inferential model has multiple associative and non-associative exposure variables and independent variables. According to Yahya, Olaniran and Ige (2014), the properties of scalar and ordinal data

without any intervention of time series and ratio allow the use of ordinary least squares, especially when the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) assumptions are not violated. From the chosen assumption model of the CSR activities and their impact on society, in this cross-sectional-based collected database, no time series and ratio-based variable is present. For this reason, the multivariate regression analysis using Ordinary Least Square (OLS) assumptions were used for inferential data analysis (Schuster et al., 2016). For multivariate regression analysis, two factors were focused the coefficient of independent variables and the significance level of each independent variable. The major variables are the brand image, the dependent variable, the independent variables are CSR policies and the demographic factors of the society. In the model of consumer purchase, pattern and profitability, similar consideration was used, including coefficient values and the significance of each independent factor loading (Schuster et al., 2016). The range of the factor loading depends on the range of each variable, that is, 1 to 5. In the data collection and coding, only the integer values within the range of 1 to 5 were used. Therefore, the level of significance was measured by presuming the critical significance value as CSR policies and the demographic factors 0.05. Thus, an independent variable loading has been considered significant when the significant value is less than 0.05. For the entire inferential statistical analysis, the 95% confidence interval has been considered. The inter-association of the variables were analysed in the data analysis procedure using Pearson correlation statistics. Along with the correlation coefficient of each pair of variables, the significant value has also been considered. For the correlation test, the significant value has been measured using the 2-tailed significance analysis, where the significant critical value is 0.05 with a 95% confidence interval.

Thus, Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) was not applied in this research as its application entails high complexity and proper knowledge of the statistical sophisticated

technique. Despite the appropriateness of SEM for establishing the relationship between the latent variables and the provision of detailed analysis of complex models, this study applied a relatively simple evaluation of the CSR-related factors (Owolabi, Ayandele and Olaoye, 2020). The study used both descriptive and inferential analysis, which proved adequate to achieve the objectives of the study (Sharma et al., 2021). The time required for SEM and the requirement of a less time-consuming data analysis approach made SEM inapplicable to this study in terms of resources.

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was also useful for the measurement validation of the quantitative data. The current fitted analysis was used to check whether the data matches the proposed structure of the latent variables by the theory or previous empirical studies (Owolabi et al., 2020). The method of CFA was conducted in this study by employing SEM software, specifically AMOS to test and verify the link between observed variables which include the survey items and the latent variables inclusive of CSR and its impact on business profitability and business image (Sharma et al., 2021). This step minimised validity and reliability problems associated with constructs measured in a survey.

4.8.3 Thematic Analysis

Thematic analysis is a qualitative method of data analysis where the patterned responses or themes are searched, analysed and reported (Appendix 3). Some of the advantages include that it entails a structured analysis of the text data, like interview scripts, to identify the latent meanings and reoccurring concepts. According to Braun and Clarke (2019), thematic analysis is quite flexible and can be used with various theoretical orientations for qualitative data analysis. This method is especially appropriate when studying multifaceted questions and learning participants' perceptions as similar responses are categorised into themes that reveal greater

insights into the subject. Pursell and Gould (2021) and Braun and Clarke (2023) concur that thematic analysis is flexible in its application to all types of qualitative data. In the same regard, thematic analysis avails data that is dense and detailed, important in analysing the responses given by the participants. Thematic analysis is also simple to use as the method does not require special technical skills as is the case with most quantitative methods (Pursell and Gould, 2021; Braun and Clarke, 2023). Nonetheless, Sabharwal and Miah (2021) highlight the potential drawbacks, such it being a time-consuming process and the interpretation of the data is usually biased. The use of thematic analysis permitted the identification of patterns that envisaged CSR policies, stakeholder management, and analysis of how the CSR approach can contribute to the improvement of the company's profitability and the development of the countries' communities. Moreover, thematic analysis offered a clear framework for identifying the managers' perceptions and capturing their opinions regarding CSR practises.

The first step was becoming acquainted with the data, whereby interview transcripts were reviewed several times to get a general understanding of the data. The second step was to develop initial codes where important parts of the text about the research questions were highlighted and assigned tags (Braun and Clarke, 2019). In the third step, the codes came under potential themes which presented general patterns in groups in the data. The fourth step focused on the review process of the themes (Braun and Clarke, 2023). In the fifth step, it was possible to give each discovered theme a proper title that offered a clear description of what was referred to in terms of the research (Braun and Clarke, 2019). In the final analysis, the themes were employed to analyse and explain the results considering the research questions and objectives of the study (Sabharwal and Miah, 2021). By following these steps, thematic analysis assisted in

delivering a coherent and systematic view of how CSR strategies were viewed by managers, and the role they play in managing business and the business implications.

4.9 Validity and Reliability

Research validity validate the suitability, and the component elements of the tools used for collecting the data. It deals with the applicability of the data collection instruments for the phenomenon studied. Reliability is the accuracy throughout which a system analyses the data, as described by Sánchez-Gómez et al. (2016). Reliability is the degree to which the findings can be replicated when the study is repeated under the same conditions. The consistency of results, across different observers and parts of the test determines the reliability. The degree to which the objective measures the right way what they are supposed to measure is explained as study veracity (Sánchez-Gómez et al., 2016). The validity and reliability differ based on the type of research. For a qualitative method, the validity and reliability are measured differently from quantitative method. In quantitative rection, the reliability was measured through statistical analysis named Cronbach's alpha. In Cronbach's alpha method, the data under each variable was used to examine the correlation within the variables. Cronbach's alpha is a measure of reliability with internal consistency, whereby it measures how much a resultant set of items is correlated with each other. Cronbach's alpha was used to assess the reliability levels of the developed survey questions on CSR, namely the business image, profitability, and societal impact (Sánchez-Gómez et al., 2016). Further, the items in each construct were assessed for reliability to establish the extent to which they provided a consistent measure of the identified latent variables.

To minimise the threats to the validity and reliability of the qualitative data, several measures were taken during the research. First, data triangulation was conducted by using different data sources such as interviewing different managers to reconfirm the findings.

Moreover, data triangulation assisted in validating the data and in gaining an understanding of the various CSR strategies within other diverse settings (Johnson, Adkins and Chauvin, 2020). Another technique used was member checking whereby the interview participants were offered a chance to read the transcripts and correct information they deemed inaccurate (Laumann, 2020). Furthermore, record paperwork used in the entire research process was kept. These specific descriptions of data collection and analysis procedures made the process clear and the interim steps and basis of the decisions clear, which improved the credibility of the results (Harris and Brown, 2019). Another way of ensuring validity was through peer debriefing whereby other researchers reviewed the data and their interpretations and gave feedback. This approach helped to reduce the level of interference and ensured that the themes emerging from the study were data-driven (Harris and Brown, 2019; Laumann, 2020). To enhance reliability and consistency, the data were gathered using the same interview guide for all the participants.

4.10 Pilot Study

A pilot study is used to evaluate research methodologies, data-gathering instruments, sample selection processes, and other research approaches in preparation for a larger study. A pilot study allows familiarisation with the procedure's protocols, which assist in improving between two different techniques of analysis. A pilot study examines the potential flaws and areas in the instrument of research and procedure before implementing the study (Sheehan, 2018). The purpose of the pilot study conducted in this research was to examine the validity and reliability of the mixed method used. Therefore, in the pilot study, the validity and reliability analysis of the interview method and survey have been analysed separately from this research method.

The pilot study was conducted to assess the adequacy or otherwise of the interview questions and the survey questionnaire to be used for full-scale data collection. The pilot study revealed various concerns relevant to the clarity and relevance of the interview questions and survey format. Some questions were characterised as unclear and hard to understand; therefore, their forms were changed. Finally, the pilot study also revealed possible technical problems which could arise with the online survey. Comments also pointed towards the need to shorten the questionnaire. The specific objectives for the pilot study include ensuring participants understood the questions fully, the questions were in line with the research objectives, and comprehensive enough to provide meaningful data (Rangan, Chase and Karim 2015; Sheehan, 2018). As for the interview questions, only three managers involved in similar fields were chosen. These participants were like the target group for the main study to assess the effectiveness of the semi-structured interview format. The interviews were conducted as discussed, employing the same 10 open-ended questions used in the full study. To ensure validity, interviewees were asked to review the questions for clarity and relevance and to report any problems they faced during the interviews.

Likewise in the case of the questionnaire, only 15 respondents from India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, and Sri Lanka were included in the consumer and employee category of the study. They were administered a questionnaire consisting of 30 questions that included Likert scale questions, closed questions, and demographic questions. Feedback on whether the survey was lengthy, appropriate, and comprehensible was requested from respondents after the completion of the survey. The participants also opined that some questions were general and should have been refined to be specific on CSR approaches and their outcomes. In addition, some participants complained that some questions were unclear or complex. A few of them pointed out that the

survey was a bit lengthy, and participants might not complete it due to the length. Accordingly, modifications were made after the pilot study. The questions with double meanings and unclear were rephrased to prevent misunderstandings. Some questions were made specific so that they appropriately captured the research objectives. For the questionnaire, each question with ambiguous wording was made clear. The last survey was shortened to 25 questions to make it easier for the participants but still included all the aspects of CSR and consumer behaviour. In general, the pilot study played a pivotal role in refining the broad interview questions and identifying the flaws and strengths of the survey to make the data collection tools understandable and relevant to the study.

4.11 Ethical Considerations

Different measures were implemented to ensure the research is ethical. Ethical considerations are a highly crucial aspect of a research paper. Ethical Considerations are specified as one of the most crucial parts of the research. First, the participants of the research were not subjected to any harm while participating in the research. The willingness of respondents to participate in the survey and interviews was crucial. Respondents were allowed to give their informed consent before participating (Kreuter et al., 2020). The basic concept of informed consent requires individuals to be provided with sufficient information and assurances about participation to fully comprehend the implications of their participation. The participants made an informed, deliberate, and freely given decision about whether to participate without any pressure or coercion (Kreuter et al., 2020). Secondly, participants were not forced to engage in the research. The data collection process was executed in an online platform; therefore, the process did not have any effect on the mental and psychological health of the participants (Rangan, Chase and Karim, 2015). Respect for the dignity of the participants was also

prioritised. The autonomy of the participants was respected through the data collection procedure. The participants were free to leave the interview or stop filling out the survey without consequences. The confidentiality and privacy of the participants was maintained throughout the study. Neither the organisation name nor the participant's name was disclosed. Additionally, special protection was ensured to keep the data shared by the participants confidential (Sheehan, 2018). The raw data was securely stored in a digital database system where only the author has access. A consent form stating the purpose of the research and the process of conducting the interview and survey was shared with all the participants. Individuals who showed interest in the research by assigning in the online consent form were allowed to participate (Groenland and Dana, 2019). For instance, after reading the details of the research, the participants were asked to acknowledge the consent form. After receiving the acknowledgement from participants, the data collection method was executed for interview and the survey.

4.12 Summary and Conclusion

The chapter on the methodology described how the research was done with emphasis on the methods and approaches employed in data collection, analysis, and interpretation. This work adopted a mixed method in which qualitative and quantitative data were used to understand the effectiveness of CSR policies in enhancing business image, profitability, and social welfare of South Asian business organisations. Convenience sampling was used to sample the participants for the survey through social media while managers were interviewed using semi-structured questions. The research adopted an epistemology research philosophy which enabled the use of quantitative and qualitative research to meet the challenge of the research questions on CSR and its impact on businesses and customers. Instruments for gathering data were composed of a 25-item self-administered questionnaire and 10 interview questions with open-ended questions

which were modified after administering a pilot test. The thematic method was used to analyse qualitative data, whereas quantitative data was analysed statistically. Despite the development of a logical construct, steps were taken to enhance the credibility, reliability and dependability of the collected data, including triangulation, member checking, and debriefing processes. The chapter on the methodology presented a sound approach to exploring the research questions. The quantitative and qualitative methods used in the study ensured the investigation of numerical data and the understanding of the managerial implications of CSR on business and society. Procedures and choice of method and tools of data gathering were selected in a way that would make the study methodical and credible.

Chapter 5: Data Analysis and Interpretation

5.1 Introduction

Data analysis and interpretation cover processes carried out to establish properties of collected data in line with the research questions. They entail sorting, collating, and analysing data to make helpful conclusions. Data analysis involves qualitative and quantitative data. The analysis process guarantees that the results meet the identified goals of the research and depict the participants' responses accurately. The first part of the analysis contains the qualitative data collected from semi-structured interviews. These interviews were corporate-level interviews that included managers working in organisations in the South Asian garment industry, all of whom were directly involved in CSR practices. The participants were chosen since they hold managerial positions in organisations that undertake CSR initiatives. The technique used in the analysis was the thematic analysis, which entails the identification of trends, patterns and features from the informants' interviews. The second section of the study contains quantitative data collected from consumers and employees from India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, and Sri Lanka from the general population through structured questionnaires. These participants were selected to capture their potential to be influenced by CSR activities of the garment industry. The survey comprised 25 questions designed to capture their understanding of the CSR policies in their organisations, the effect of CSR on consumers' buying decisions and the relationship between CSR and business performance. Quantitative data was analysed using statistical techniques, where the relations between CSR dimensions and business performance measures were tested. The approaches make it possible to consider CSR practises and their suitability and impact on managerial and consumer attitudes.

5.2 Qualitative Results

The findings are based on the participants' perceptions of CSR from semi-structured interviews with managers of South Asian garment firms. The interviews were planned to reveal the strengths and weaknesses of the applied CSR policies from managers' perspectives and their implications on the image and profitability of the companies and ethical business practices. Evaluations were made using thematic analysis to identify cross-comparison of themes and patterns from the interviews conducted. The results elaborate the understanding of each identified theme in the interviews conducted. Every identified theme has been illustrated by quotes obtained from the participants to give context to the research conclusions. Such qualitative findings provide an avenue for getting into the mindset of managers and understanding that they perceive CSR as adding value to their organisations.

5.2.1 Impact of CSR on competitive advantage and value added on business

The results show that CSR is a competitive imperative in today's economy. Participant 1 said, *"Today, consumers are not only concerned about the quality of what they are buying but also interested to know whether the owning company organisation has similar feelings concerning certain socially responsible issues. CSR empowers customers to take a chance."* This response shows that by implementing CSR, the company can appeal to consumers, thus enhancing its competitive advantage. This response points out that the emerging culture of consumers is fuelled by their CSR concerns, not the quality of goods. CSR establishes trust and brand loyalty among the target customers for garment products. In this context, the results show that CSR programmes help companies develop positive associations with customers, thereby boosting brand loyalty. By adopting sustainable development, equality, and fairness to workers, the company can achieve a competitive edge. In other words, CSR enables companies to attract

customers who treasure values, which helps businesses to stand out in an emergent conscience economy. Participant 5 added, *“When undertaking proper CSR strategies, such consumers feel that you are not driven by the green aspect, but the welfare of their needs and hence customers provide you their loyalty, which in the long run is very profitable.”* These results show that corporations that integrate CSR into their operations gain closer customer relationships and a sustainable competitive advantage. The findings show that corporations integrating CSR into their operation create enhanced customer relations, translating to a sustained competitive advantage. Consumers are loyal to the brands and are genuinely concerned about social problems in society, promoting customer loyalty and brand value. In the long term, this loyalty leads to profitability because clients support enterprises with which they have a strong bond, share the results with others, and have a favourable view of their brands. Therefore, CSR works as a link between organisations and consumers and results in the establishment of sustainable competitive benefits.

CSR enable firms to explore new markets where social sustainability is prioritised. For instance, Participant 3 said, *“Our CSR in sustainability has given us windows to new markets, especially those in the European region that are very much conscious of conservation of environment, we would have lost good opportunities had we not adopted CSR.”* This response underscores that CSR is essential for market penetration strategies in the international markets. Firms that use CSR initiatives meet the environmental and ethical standards of consumers and regulators. For firms compelled to adopt CSR within their operations, this strategy brings out new revenue channels and business prospects. This view from the participant underlines that CSR is essential for companies who want to maintain competitiveness and the primary strategy of choice for market entry and growth in regions that consider high ethical standards and the

welfare of the environment as a priority. On the contrary, Participant 10's perspective, "*We tried implementing CSR initiatives, but the results were mixed. There was no clear link between our CSR activities and increased sales or profitability. It's difficult to measure the direct impact, which makes it hard to justify the expense,*" underscores a significant challenge associated with CSR: its definite financial utilitarianism, yet the challenge of measuring its economic impact.

This remains a strong criticism that although CSR can enhance brand image or goodwill, it is not easy to quantify its tangible benefits in terms of sales and profitability. Due to the intangible nature of the CSR benefits, it is challenging for organisations to quantify benefits from the CSR investment. From this perspective, the conflict between the social responsibilities that come with CSR and the economic responsibilities required from organisations becomes evident. Since it is hard to define CSR goals in quantifiable terms, this results in scepticism as to whether CSR indeed lays the foundation for generating value and acting as a competitive edge, especially among organisations oriented towards maximising their short-term profit. As CSR might be with promises of long-term organisational gains such as customer loyalty, brand differentiation, and employee turnover, the lack of tangible short-term organisational returns might raise uncertainty. The findings reemphasise the need for firms to get practical tools for assessing the extensive, long-term CSR implications to enhance its compatibility with organisational objectives and control, including competitiveness.

The findings reiterate that CSR brings changes in the firm's internal environment, including the staff turnover rate and organisational culture. As pointed out by Participant 6, "*The company has taken the lead to embrace ethical practises for its operations and this has brought about a better quality of employee. People want to work with a company that reflects their culture.*" This response shows that CSR builds employees' character and a positive work

environment to attract and retain deserving and hard-working employees. In staff-turnover-prone industries such as the garment industry, the results show that CSR is a source of competitive advantage by establishing ethically sound principles and practices that employees feel connected to. These results show that CSR creates a positive work culture that makes employees proud to work and remain loyal to that company. From this perspective, ethics and values are essential components when developed within organisations to create stability and decrease turnover costs by attracting better talent. Consequently, CSR transforms into a strategic resource as it forms the basis of delivering sustainable competitive advantage, which complies with the employee's values and the customer's demands. CSR can thus improve the work culture at the workplace, making the company relevant in the market and creating value in the long term.

The results also show that CSR practices contribute to value creation. From this perspective, undertaking CSR creates goodwill and a corporate image, which translates to higher sales. Participant 2 notes that: *“CSR is not a cost; it’s an investment”*. This argument shows that CSR is beneficial to the company. In the long term, customers maintain more robust and healthier business relations, which helps in sales growth and overall corporate profitability. The findings show the evolution in the way people perceive CSR. In particular, CSR is an investment that yields tangible financial benefits. When managed and implemented as part of a firm’s strategic development plan, CSR enhances customer retention and distinguishes the organisation from competitors. Thus, CSR transforms into a means for attaining social change and business development. On the contrary, Participant 8 stated: *“Although CSR is wonderful in concept, the truth of the matter is that here in our markets, consumers are always price-conscious to some extent, meaning that we cannot always afford the luxury of investing in expensive CSR programmes even if the returns are long term in nature, not immediate.”* This perspective

captures the underlying issue between the cost and resources required to conduct business and the commitment to CSR activity, particularly for South Asian markets. This attitude of the participant is a typical problem that companies encounter in markets in which product selection criteria are mainly price sensitivity rather than the product's ethical characteristics. While benefits like increased brand recognition and customer loyalty may be gained from CSR, the tangible rewards are not easily identifiable. Price-sensitive strategies may be a challenge if companies fail to factor in the cost of implementing CSR strategies where business results cannot be immediately monetised. This argument raises a question typically faced by organisations aiming at achieving economic efficiency and investing in socially appropriate actions. Consequently, if CSR is feasible in such environments, it might have to be practised in ways that do not incur additional expenses or compromise value-conscious consumers.

CSR has the potential to positively impact companies. Participant 7 connects CSR to its reception by customers and the outcome of sales as follows: *“CSR has a positive image, especially when it comes to local community involvement, and there is a direct relation between our organisation’s promotion of CSR and increased traffic at our stores.”* CSR centred on the community can bolster a company's image and customer loyalty. People who perceive that a business is involved in local issues may purchase the products and services and help make the business profitable. This corresponds with the concept that CSR activities may serve as a mechanism for strengthening market integration within a specific geographical region, where CSR implementations are visibly associated with community preferences. Participant 4, however, offers a political perspective about what they understand as CSR as a way of managing risks. *“CSR has assisted us in avoiding risks by especially adopting sustainable practises which help us avoid penalties and fines which would have cost us a lot of money in the long run”*. This

view underscores the relevance of CSR in managing the risks of incurring regulatory penalties and implementing sustainability benchmarks. In approaching the issue of environmental and ethical impacts, organisations have an opportunity to prevent legal and financial consequences that may hinder operations. These perspectives show that CSR positively affects brand loyalty while actively managing possible risks, showing the versatility of its role in business performance. On the contrary, Participant 9 also questioned the profitability of CSR, therefore adding to the criticism of its efficiency by noting. *"It is hard to quantify. Hey, look at the amount of money we made this quarter because of CSR. It's like a feel-good thing. It helps our image, but I do not think it is driving profitability"*. This response acknowledges common issues faced by organisations when attempting to generate profits from CSR initiatives. Although CSR might add value to the company's image and the brands within it can become slightly unclear how it correlates with profits. This concern shows how the ethical responsibility to manage social issues and the economic benefit of CSR strategies are discussed by defining if they can provide financial benefits or expenses to appear socially responsible.

5.2.2 Key influences of CSR policies and activities on business image, stakeholders, and society

From the interviews conducted among managers from different organisations in the South Asian garment industry, the study shows the advantages and drawbacks of CSR regarding business image, stakeholder relations, and social benefits. Most participants supported the notion that CSR has positive impacts. The results showed that CSR creates a favourable business image in today's markets. Participant 1 stated, *"CSR enables us to set a niche. Consumers today tend to purchase from socially responsible companies and contribute to society."* This statement posits that CSR initiatives provide a way for the business to prove its control in a competitive economy.

Like the case of Participant 1, Participant 3 concurs by stating, *“Implementing CSR has helped improve the view that customers have about our brand we are seen as ethical, and this is critical in the current business environment.”* These factors influence the consumers as they are receptive to new information concerning the world and associate with socially responsible brands and those that address sustainability issues. The results showed that CSR negatively impact business image. In this regard, Participant 3 points out that: *“CSR are just ‘window-dressing activities.”* This view poses questions about the effectiveness and the real magnitude of CSR efforts as it can be implied that some companies implement CSR activities for ‘window dressing’. In contrast, in the real sense, they do not necessarily have the best intentions of helping society. This concern brings forth the question of the reality of ‘green washing’, where organisations demonstrate CSR contributions for the sake of a public image, which does not positively impact society or equate to significant business gains. However, the views expressed by Participants 2 and 3 align with the increasing consumer advocacy and willingness to deal with sustainable firms. This argument supports the notion that CSR is an essential tool in improving corporate image and consumers’ trust and maintaining loyalty in the long term. In the highly competitive garment industry, CSR can be an excellent tool that creates a good image and interaction with the socially conscious customer.

The results showed that the interactions with key stakeholders, such as investors and business partners, improve because of CSR activities. For instance, Participant 9 stated: *“Today, investors care about how we as organisations manage CSR issues than in the past because they wish to ensure that their investments are going to organisations that can manage social issues”*. This response demonstrates how today’s investors focus on the social responsibility of the company they invest in or support. From the business perspective, an excellent implementation

of CSR can improve business and investment credibility. This view, therefore, establishes that CSR extends to investors who base their investments on a company's social and ethical behaviour. CSR affects investors in the company and employees, as supported by Participant 6 who stated, "*CSR makes our employees feel motivated and valued when they are part of a company that is socially responsible*". This statement explains how CSR activities can benefit an organisation by enhancing workers' morale and making them loyal. CSR provides a sense of purpose in the workplace, increasing satisfaction and motivation, and the overall organisational commitment may lead to better employee retention and improved productivity. These views indicate that CSR has a complex influence on the firm's stakeholder relationships outside and within the firm. Customers, shareholders, and strategic partners demand organisations to be socially responsible, thus improving the company's image, sustaining mutually beneficial relations and creating long-term benefits for the company.

The results show that CSR positively impact the company's business image. From this perspective, participating in socially responsible activities aids in the formation of a brand that appeals to consumers who care about ethics and sustainability. For instance, Participant 3 stated, "*Customers view us as more ethical,*" indicating that ethics is a salient consumer consideration. This view is consistent with the current global stance, as consumers tend to support brands that integrate sustainable and CSR values into their business. Participant 10 elaborated on this by stating, "*Customers trust us more*". However, employees, investors, and business partners are vital for a firm's future, and CSR can significantly enhance these links. For instance, participant 4 explained: "*While people are today interested in knowing how we handle CSR before investing, it shows that investors are interested in how we handle CSR than ever before.*" The results confirm the importance of robust CSR practice in improving a firm's business image and gaining

the trust of consumers and stakeholders. The findings demonstrate how CSR practises are significant strategies in contemporary business management, contributing to sustainable future performance and success.

The results show that CSR as a practical action has a positive and direct effect on the company image, especially regarding environmental responsibility. As for Participant 5, the work is done to minimise waste and encourage environmental conservation, which enhances the business image to the buyers and investors. Participant 5: "*Sure. Since consumers and stakeholders trust organisations that engage in efforts to be environmentally sensitive, we are always committed to such initiatives to create a positive image*". The results show that CSR activities positively influence the brand image. Likewise, Participant 7 further explained that long-term brand loyalty is also an indication of the benefits of CSR. Participant 7 explained: "*Customers trust us because they can understand that we are working to be more than making profits from them. On this aspect of trust, the customers remain loyal to our brand for a long time.*" This response shows that if the customers view that a company is concerned with the welfare of the world beyond the aspect of making profits, they stick with the brand. These findings show that customers buy from a socially responsible company. From this perspective, CSR creates positive organisational changes for better performance, customer loyalty, and image. CSR activities foster a firm's competitiveness and build long-term bonds with customers and stakeholders, thereby enhancing the firm's image as a socially responsible organisation.

The results show that CSR efforts have social benefits apparent in local communities. Participant 2 stated: "*We have constructed schools and have ensured the provision of clean water to those in the neighbouring villages to our industries.*" This response shows that CSR activities extend the business's self-serving goals of increasing profit and positively impacting community

development and social well-being considerably. Corporate entities can play a positive role in society by helping provide clean and accessible water. This approach shows how firms transform communities while building their image. Participant 10 also gave a similar opinion of CSR activities, indicating that their company has contributed to employing the residents. Participant 10 noted: "*Some community project responses our activities have positively impacted is job creation. Our community projects have helped to increase employment opportunities for the individuals in the areas of operation, and people are receptive to that*". This response shows that CSR initiatives enable companies in the garment industry to create jobs and improve the economy in the deprived areas. The companies provide employment, eradicate poverty and improve living conditions, especially in developing regions. Creating messages of support also assists in these programmes, and such efforts also market the firm as a socially responsible company that plays a role in advancing sustainable development. Participant 2 and Participant 10 show how CSR activities are self-generated, impacting lives and enhancing social and economic transformation. CSR initiatives create a favourable image within societies, thus enshrining the practices as essential for a corporation's success and societal contributions.

The results highlight the significance of CSR in enhancing partnerships. For instance, Participant 8 stated: "*Our suppliers and partners want to work with companies with a well-developed CSR profile*". This response shows how CSR practises are not limited to consumers but also impact business relations outside the organisation. Thus, the commitment to sustainability makes collaborations with stakeholders effective. Such ethical deals are strategic partnerships that lead to competitive advantage due to enhanced trust and cooperation within the supply chain. In addition, Participant 9 spoke of how CSR enhances the business – government relations that can culminate in operational gains, "*Local governments have been supportive*

because they find us as significant players in societal advancement, thus providing many business prospects". This response highlights how CSR mediates between businesses and public authorities, resulting in improved regulation and functioning. When a company conducts activities that benefit the people within a community or contribute to the betterment of society, the government likely recognise this and offers the company some of the following: tax exemptions, subsidies, and means of acquiring business permits. CSR can help to create win-win situations and build paths for firms' further development while linking them to the public good. CSR have a beneficial impact on the relationships with stakeholders, both partners and authorities. By adopting and implementing proper practices, organisations can regain and build the trust necessary for effective collaboration, success, and sustainability.

5.2.3 Ways CSR helps in developing society and community

The results show that CSR programmes foster societal development. In this regard, the study underlines the importance of education and people's wish to enhance society. Participant 3 noted: *"Via CSR programmes, our firm works through supporting local schools, scholarship programmes, and training teachers. The activities solve long-term social problems by giving people knowledge. Education brings change in a community's welfare"*. Investment in education builds human capital that drives economic function and minimises disparities in society. The results show that the firm's CSR initiatives on education are enabling tools for future growth. However, Participant 4 defines CSR as encompassing environmental sustainability. Participant 4 notes that CSR has a dual purpose: *'This not only benefits the physical environment but also finds new avenues of the economic resource of the community,' and thus is available to foster two facets of a community successfully, the ecological and the economic*. Through CSR, most programmes are pro-environmental, including the development of waste management and

renewable energy sources, beneficial for society and the environment. The measures preserve natural resources and create economic value attributed to the recycling of waste. Although both participants support CSR because of its benefits to society, the former speaks about education as an empowering tool. In contrast, the latter speaks about environmental sustainability as a tool that preserves the environment and develops the economy. Thus, CSR improves both human and ecological capital, which are fundamental for an efficient society.

The results emphasise the benefits of CSR, including job creation and infrastructural development. Participant 1 discusses the employment aspect, especially concerning the garment industry where CSR-oriented programmes include training and development endeavours. CSR initiatives affect women and youth groups, which strive to solve unemployment and gender discrimination. For instance, Participant 1 noted: *"This changed last year and currently, we have been operating vocational training for youth, especially women to enable the youths to join the job market"*. This response illustrates that CSR positively influences the development of sustainable livelihoods for the disadvantaged in society. The results show that CSR, therefore, helps create short-term tangible-economic gains by providing the skills for empowerment and society in the long term. Participant 2 emphasises infrastructure as one of the CSR areas of operations. Participant 2 stated: *"From our company's CSR calendar, we undertake to construct schools, roads, and health centerers."* This response confirms how CSR ensures the development of tangible and social infrastructures in society. Through providing corporate services for basic needs such as education, health, and transport, CSR contributes positively toward the enhanced well-being of the people in society.

The results show that CSR can be effective and relevant when firms assume responsibility for affecting positive social and economic change in society. In this case,

Participant 8 stressed the impact of CSR on poverty eradication. From this perspective, the results show that CSR directly influences underprivileged people by providing necessary amenities like cash, food, and knowledge within societies. Participant 8 notes: "*There is one of the main goals of the company's CSR – to fight against poverty. We operate and support community programmes that offer financial support, food, and education to families living in poverty*". CSR initiatives strive to solve fundamental social problems, including poverty, leading to a fair society. In this perspective, CSR aids in creating long-term goals in community development and addresses the needs of low-income earners, thus eliminating poverty. However, Participant 9 had a less positive attitude towards CSR and defined it as a strategy that organisations use to improve their image instead of improving the circumstances in society. Participant 9 stated: "*CSR is sometimes a myth; it means the company wants to create an impression that it is working for the society's development without actually doing so*". This response shows that CSR is sometimes employed as a marketing strategy less than an attempt to empower communities. The primary goal of CSR is to improve an organisation's image, and this does not deliver a positive CSR for societal change. In this context, firms may not use the money and efforts to support community improvement and address a particular social issue such as poverty and environmental degradation but focus on the image-building aspect of their CSR initiatives. When comparing these perspectives, CSR is one of the basic functions which significantly impact the community by combating poverty. However, the major drawback of CSR is that some organisations may engage in CSR to create an impression rather than an impact.

The results show that CSR is a practical concept which advances social processes. CSR could help eradicate poverty by arguing that initiatives target underprivileged communities'

requirements. Participant 8 noted: *"Another aspect of our CSR plan is to find people out of poverty, and we organise community development programmes, including offering cash and food handouts and scholarships to needy families"*. This response shows that CSR initiatives can enhance the quality of the lives of disadvantaged communities. Financial assistance, educational materials food security and other related facilities are provided, helping society reduce inequalities. On the contrary, Participant 9 provided a negative outlook on the specific CSR programmes and doubts about authenticity. Participant 9 stated: *"Most often, CSR is just a facade to get appreciation without trying to enhance the society considerably"*. From this perspective, CSR acts as a marketing tool to enhance a firm's reputation with little regard for bringing positive changes in society. This critique draws attention to the fact that CSR creates a positive image boost for business organisations, giving primary importance to the short-term image rather than the real welfare of the community. The contradictive views demonstrate the potential pros and cons of CSR in practice. However, the real success of such activity stands within the intentions and further action of the launching corporations.

Finally, according to most participants, CSR initiatives contribute to the process of creating society and communities. CSR works towards human well-being by providing employment opportunities, infrastructure, education, and health. Nonetheless, the concerns regarding superficial CSR measures and lack of strategic and systematic long-term solutions suggest that companies adopt sustainable CSR developmental solutions that can effectively and proactively enhance societies.

5.3 Quantitative Results

In the quantitative aspect of the study, 300 respondents' data were gathered, and 43 responded that they had no idea about CSR; thus, their responses were excluded from the

analysis to ensure that only informed participants were used in the findings. After this distribution, the total number of respondents was reduced to 257 for further study. However, the major drawback detected was the absence of a solid basis for CSR awareness among the population. This might suggest a lack of apparent gaps in CSR communication initiatives by organisations in the region. Testing the research hypotheses and the interrelationships between CSR awareness, business image, profitability, and societal impact were conducted based on 257 adjusted samples of the respondents, which provide an understanding of the participants who possess concrete knowledge and perceptions regarding the issues of CSR.

Quantitative data enables the analyst to measure the differences between various groups, find relationships between variables, and test multiple hypotheses using the data collected. Since quantitative data analysis is about analysing numbers, the primary domain is statistics. Statistical methods can perform basic calculations such as sum, averages, and mean, and complex calculations such as correlation and regression (Mertens, 2017). The purpose of descriptive statistics lies in the scenario where a large amount of data is collected to analyse and explain the identified patterns in that set of data. They encompass mean, median, mode, and standard deviation percentages as the measures that help to describe the features of the data (Nassaji, 2015). Inferential statistics are more advanced than descriptive and facilitate making hypotheses on a complete population from sample statistics. Statistical methods such as t-tests, ANOVA and regression make conclusions based on learnt knowledge explaining the relationships between specific variables and test hypotheses (Mertens, 2017). These methods give additional depth to the sampled data by offering associated findings that apply to the broader population.

5.3.1 Frequency analysis

Frequency analysis is a method of statistics generally applied to analyse the frequencies of values or classes in a list or a data series. Frequency analysis means reporting the number of instances of different values or categories in the variable to find patterns and trends. The results are displayed in frequency tables, bar graphs, and pie charts, which makes it easier to understand and interpret patterns. It is most applicable and beneficial when used on frequency data it enables researchers to compare the frequency of the responses or characteristics in the variables. It offers insight into how data is dispersed across various categories or groups.

Table 1: Demographic of the Participants

Sample Size (N)	N	%
Position		
Administrator	5	1.67
Chief Executive officer	30	10.00
Chief Operating office	5	1.67
Company Owner	12	4.00
Consultant	3	1.00
Director	20	6.67
Educationist / Faculty	13	4.33
General Manager	9	3.5
Department head	20	6.67
Logistics Manager	7	2.33

Production Manager	25	8.33
Product Head	9	3.00
Quality Manager	14	4.67
Merchandising	23	7.67
Senior Executive	14	4.67
Senior Technician	36	12.00
Sustainability Manager	4	1.33
Vice President	8	2.67
	257	100.00
Level of Education		
Bachelors	117	45.52
Postgraduate	78	26.00
Master and above	59	22.96
No Education background	3	1.00
	257	100.00
Age Group		
18-25	10	3.33
25-40	95	36.96
40-65	152	59.14
	257	100.00

The table presents statistical data on the sample size (N=257) distributed across three categories: the job position of an employee, the educational level the employee possesses and the age group of the employee (Table 1). Distribution of the sample by position: It is equally a diverse one depending on the positions held by respondents, the most significant response is from Senior Technicians (12%, N=36) followed by CEOs (10%, N=30). Other significant roles working in the industry involve Production Managers (8.33% N=25), Sales (7.67% N=23) and Department Heads/Directors (6.67% N=20). The least group is consultants who responded 1% (4). Sustainability Managers who responded were 1.33%, while Administrators and Chief Operating Officers were 1%. In terms of education, 45.52 % (N=117) of respondents have a bachelor's degree, 26% (N=78) are Postgraduates, and 22.96 % (N=59) have a Master's degree or higher. Three participants indicated that they had no formal education, while 1% claimed to have had some form of education.

The age distribution for most of the respondents was in the age range of 40-65, making up 59 % (152) of the total number of the participants. The second largest group is 25 to 40 years, 36.9 6% (N= 95). Three percent of respondents were of ages between 18-25 representing 3. 33% (N = 10). Such distribution of data shows a good representation of the different positions and education levels, and most of the workforce is composed of experienced workers who are 40 years old and above.

Table 2: Respondents' Awareness About CSR

Sample Size (N)	N	%
Awareness about Fair Trade		
Yes	223	86.77
No	34	13.23
	257	100.00
Brands with effective CSR activities provide a higher-quality product or services		
Yes	204	68.00
No	53	32.00
	257	100.00
Awareness of brand CSR history		
Yes	213	82.88
No	44	17.12
	257	100.00

The descriptive findings in Table 2 suggest a relatively high level of awareness about fair trade among the respondents. Among the participants, there were 257, but 86.77% (N=223) had heard about fair trade initiatives, and 13.23% had not. This testifies to a relatively high degree of awareness of one of the components of the CSR concept. Besides, concerning the opinion about the quality of brands with CSR activities, 68% (N=204) strongly agreed with the statement, and

32% (N=53) disagreed. Most participants have a positive attitude towards the relationship between CSR and product or service quality. Lastly, 82.88% (213) of the respondents indicated that they were in touch with the CSR history of the brands they buy from and 17.22%, were not aware of CSR history. These findings highlight a fair level of awareness regarding CSR practises and their perceived effectiveness in influencing brand quality and reputation.

Table 3: CSR Influence on Purchasing Pattern

Poor CSR history influences purchasing		
Yes	62	24.12
No	195	75.88
	257	100.00
How you choose your favourite brand		
Price	51	19.84
Quality	206	80.16
	257	100.00
Does poor CSR change buy patterns?		
I would change my attitude	26	10.12
I would have same attitude	231	89.88
	257	100.00

CSR history affects purchasing behaviour. Only 24.12% (N=62) agreed that a poor CSR history would impact their purchase behaviour (Table 3). Of the respondents, 75.88% (N=195)

stated that CSR history would not affect their purchasing behaviours. Although some consumers are conscious of CSR concerns, the majority are concerned with CSR history while purchasing. Eighty percent of the respondents had carefully chosen their brands to be their favourites. Of the total, 80.16%, N=206, considered product quality the most crucial element. 84% (N=51) of the participants who prioritise product price. Consumers willingly buy products from companies that demonstrate a positive CSR compared to firms with a negative CSR rating. In addition, when asked whether they would avoid a company with a poor CSR record, 10.12% (N=26) mentioned that it would change their attitude, and 89% affirmed that a good CSR history would encourage them. A total of 89.88% (N=231) of the respondents affirmed that the change of attitude would not be changed. Based on these findings, most consumers are not particularly sensitive to CSR issues to the point where they are willing to switch brands or alter their choice of products.

5.3.2 Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics of the items used in each variable on the scales of measurement are presented in this section. The tables display the number of respondents, the mean score, minimum and maximum values, and the standard deviation values. The mean is the data's average since it is utilised as a singular value that denotes the centre of the collected sample. Like the mean, the median represents a data set's central tendency. Weisburd et al. (2014) indicate that the dataset's central tendency measurements, such as means, medians, and mode, are comparable, indicating that the data are symmetrical. The lowest or the minimum value and maximum value in the data help uncover data entry errors or outliers (unusual values). For instance, the minimum value of 1 in the findings table suggests replies began with firm disagreement, while the most significant value of 5 implies the participants have a strong

agreement. Overall, the results from the descriptive statistics assist in determining how widely apart the items in the sample are.

Figure 9: Participants' Educational Qualifications

Source: (Author, 2024).

Overall, 44.36% of the participants had a bachelor’s degree in engineering, the most popular educational qualification (Figure 9). The Postgraduates comprised 29.96 %, out of which 25.68% hold a Master's degree. The cumulative distribution of education type for a well-educated sample with 74.3% had at least an undergraduate degree. Although such a large percentage indicates familiarity and knowledge of CSR concepts, participants' views about CSR practises and their implications for business and society are influenced by their understanding level.

Figure 10: Age of the Participants

Source: (Author, 2024)

The age distribution of respondents reflects a considerable concentration in the 40–65 age group (63.8%) and accounts for more than half of all research participants (Figure 10).

Furthermore, 33.1% of participants were 25–40, with 85 respondents and 3.1% were in the youngest range of 18–25. This breakdown infers that the survey broadly resonates with an older generation, representing their understanding and opinions on CSR initiatives. Disproportionate age representation might affect the results, particularly around opinions of CSR and how it influences business practises.

Figure 11: Effect of CSR Activities on Quality of Products and Services

Source: (Author, 2024)

The results revealed that 47.5% of respondents feel that effective CSR leads to higher-quality goods or services from a brand (Figure 11). About 46.3% of respondents said maybe, and 6.2% disagreed with this statement. CSR positively affect product/service quality.

Figure 12: Participants' Awareness About Favourite Retail Brand's History of Operation

Source: (Author, 2024)

Most participants (63.8%) know about their preferred retail brand's history of operation in recent years, with 36.2% disregarding it completely (Figure 12). The implication is that many consumers understand the operations of the brands they support, which affects buyers when making a purchase. However, brands may need to improve transparency and communication efforts to attract consumers.

Figure 13: Impact of Brand History on Purchasing Decisions

Source: (Author, 2024)

The results show that 138 respondents (53.7%) stated that poor CSR history would not affect their purchase decision, whereas 119 (46.3%) mentioned that it would (Figure 13). The gap in consumer perceptions of the influence of past CSR records is narrowed to a certain extent. These results provide insights into the necessity of brands keeping their CSR practice in check to appeal to many consumers.

Figure 14: Participant’s Opinion Regarding Brands CSR Committee on the Board

Source: (Author, 2024)

According to the findings, 78.2% of those surveyed stated that all brands do not have a CSR committee on the Board, whereas 21.8% maintained that each company currently has a CSR committee (Figure 14). The results imply a gap in terms of brand perception or understanding of CSR governance. The assumption that not all companies have a proper CSR committee may show negligence or unstructured forms of formal CSR management and communication. These findings show that companies need to either extend the use of CSR committees or better communicate about their creation and function.

Figure 15: Existence of Transparent and Effective Monitoring Mechanisms

Source: (Author, 2024)

The findings offer insights into the potential lack of transparency and performance monitoring (Figure 15). In this case, 38.19% (98 participants) reported no effective monitoring mechanisms, whereas 33.86% (87 participants) considered the existing mechanisms acceptable. Regarding methods, 7 participants (2.76%) stated that monitoring mechanisms were strong, and 65 participants (25.2%) highlighted poor quality mechanisms. These findings further suggest the need to adopt profound control of CSR performance to ensure that organisations are held accountable for their ethical and responsible behaviours.

Figure 16: Basis of Choosing Favourite Brands

Source: (Author, 2024)

The results show that 84.8% of the participants consider product quality when choosing a brand as a favourite (Figure 16). In comparison, 10.1% of participants highlighted advertisements and 5.1% regarded competitive pricing as the main factor when purchasing products. There is a growing emphasis on the intrinsic qualities of products among consumers compared to brand equity and pricing, indicating that quality has a significant role in shaping consumer choices. The cumulative percentages confirm that most participants value product quality, emphasising what brands must incorporate in their marketing strategies.

Figure 17: Most Effective CSR Activities

Source: (Author, 2024)

Asked to identify their preferred CSR activities, 56.0% (144 responders) identified educational support as their most effective CSR program (Figure 17). The result illustrates the priority given to actions that increase educational opportunities and create informed communities, followed by 40.5% (104) of the responders expressing support for homeless and underprivileged people, showing considerable interest in social welfare and poverty reduction. However, 2.7% (7 participants) chose helping refugees as the most effective CSR project. The results show a significant interest in CSR strategies centred on educational efforts.

Figure 18: Effect of CSR on Consumer Attitude Toward the Brand

Source: (Author, 2024)

The findings suggest that knowledge of negative CSR behaviours has a sizeable impact on consumer perceptions of their favourite brands (Figure 18). More specifically, 57.6% of respondents answered that they would have a different attitude towards a brand if the company had low levels of CSR reputation, demonstrating that ethical perceptions are highly influential in consumer behaviour. Another 31.5% said they were unsure, whereas 10.9% would keep their current perception of the brand, implying that most consumers re-evaluate how they perceive brands in response to CSR information. The results reiterate the significance of CSR in brand loyalty and reputation.

Figure 19: Participants' Willingness to Pay Extra to Retailer that Guarantees Good Work Conditions and Fair Wages to Factory Workers

Source: (Author, 2024)

In response to the question about spending more for items produced by retailers that agree to pay fair wages and ensure good working conditions in factories, 48.64% would pay more while 51.36% would not (Figure 19). The findings point to the challenges retailers face when leveraging the demands for sustainable products with affordable counterparts, demonstrating a need to enlighten consumers about the source of their products.

Figure 20: Aspects that Make a Business Accountable

Source: (Author, 2024)

The findings show that consumers perceive providing good products as the significant driver of brand accountability, chosen by 36.6% of respondents (Figure 20). The second factor, cited by 28% of respondents, was compliance with regulations. Another suggestion was respect for staff (23.7%). In addition, 9.7% of the participants highlighted being active in societal campaigns, whereas 1.9% believed in employing workers with disability. The findings indicate that business practises may account for product quality and regulation adherence.

Figure 21: Most Important Reasons for Companies to Engage in CSR Activities

Source: (Author, 2024)

The results suggest that the primary reason for CSR activities is to serve society and the environment, as highlighted by 49.8% of the respondents (Figure 21). The results show that commitment to CSR aims to improve the company image as supported by 39.3 percent of respondents. From this perspective, CSR activities act as a moral responsibility and a business strategy. However, 8.6% highlighted drawing customer interest, and 2.3% mentioned higher income is an important driver. These results mean that CSR retains its social and environmental advantage.

Figure 22: Common CSR Activities

Source: (Author, 2024)

The results indicate that the most common CSR activities companies are involved in are associated with environmental sustainability, as reported by 37.4% of respondents (Figure 22). The second standard activity is sponsoring education, community and social development (36.2%), reflecting conscious efforts in contributing to society. Almost 13% are charitable events, slightly lower than volunteering in the community. Thus, companies place environmental and educational activities in their CSR agenda, while direct benefits related to volunteering have less importance.

Table 4: Descriptive statistics of items of CSR relationship with people (public)

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Is the term “Fair Trade” familiar to you?	1.94	.235	257
Do you think brands with effective CSR activities are prone to provide you with higher quality product or services?	2.40	.605	257
Are you aware of your favourite retail brand history for the past few years?	1.64	.481	257
Would a brand with a poor CSR history influence your purchasing?	1.46	.500	257

The summary of the survey results presents the findings on CSR-related factors based on participants’ awareness and perceptions. The mean for the respondents who heard and were familiar with the term “Fair Trade” is 1.94 with a low standard deviation of 0.235, which implies that 55% of the respondents were familiar with the concept (Table 4). The mean on whether brands with proper CSR exercises deliver better quality products or services is 2.40 and a higher standard deviation of 0.605, which implies that respondents have a more comprehensive options regarding the statistical measures. For awareness of a favourite retail brand's history, the mean is 1.64 with a standard deviation of 0.481, again indicating a reasonably good understanding. At the same time, the variability of the responses may be average. The mean of 1.46 and a standard deviation of 0.500, which implies that many people could be inclined to avoid a brand with a bad CSR profile; however, response variability cannot also be denied. The findings indicate a

relatively fair understanding of CSR concerns, though people have different feelings about the CSR factors and how much CSR affects the assessment of product quality and buying behaviours.

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics of Brand Image / Purchasing Pattern Items

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
Would a brand with a poor CSR history influence your purchasing?	257	1.46	.500	.250
On what basis do you choose your favourite brand?	257	1.95	.387	.150
What type of CSR activities is most effective?	257	1.47	.559	.313
What are the most important reasons for companies to get involved in CSR activities?	257	1.63	.739	.545
How important is working with manufacturers that value diversity and good working conditions?	257	8.92	1.195	1.427

The results of the descriptive statistics of the brand image and the purchasing pattern provide valuable information about the participants’ attitudes towards CSR and its impact on the

consumer’s decision-making process. Regarding whether a low CSR brand would affect purchasing, the mean score was 1.46. The results show that CSR history is an essential factor in the buying decision, with a standard deviation of 0.500. Furthermore, when asked about the criteria they used in choosing their favourite brand, the mean obtained was equal to 1.95, and a low standard deviation of 0.387 reveals that people choose the brand based on such factors in line with CSR strategies. Concerning the most effective CSR activities, the mean score in this study was 1.47, and a standard deviation of 0.558 raises a difference between the respondents, but most view CSR activities as impactful. The reasons for companies to engage in CSR activities had a mean of 1.63 showing that overall, CSR is critical in firms although there is variation in the responses. Regarding preference for working with manufacturers that support diversity and good working conditions this was ranked with ranked with a mean of 8.92, with a standard deviation of 1.195, which underlines that people pay attention to ethical aspects.

Table 6: Descriptive Statistics of Items of CSR - Financial Performance

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
Would you consider paying extra for a product that the retailer guarantees good work conditions and fair wages to factory workers?	257	1.51	.501	.251
Is a competitive price the main factor when purchasing clothing products?	257	3.50	1.216	1.478

Is product quality important than price when deciding on buying products?	257	4.21	.745	.555
Would you buy from the same brand despite high prices and average quality?	257	1.35	.615	.378
Do you choose to buy products from brands with a good reputations and more excellent value to community?	257	4.15	.676	.457

The descriptive statistics presented in Table 6 provide insights into consumers' impressions concerning CSR financial performance and purchasing behaviour. Mean 1.51 shows that the customers are aware of their role, and conscious of societal expectations. With a standard deviation of 0.501, the result shows that most respondents willingly pay a premium price if retailers assure them of a good working conditions and fair wages to the employees (Table 6). However, the issue receiving higher importance in competitive pricing has a mean of 3.50 with a standard deviation of 1.216, which indicates that the price plays an essential role in buying garments. Moreover, product quality influences price with a high mean of 4.21 and a standard deviation of 0.745. The findings show that quality is a critical aspect when making purchase decisions. However, the low mean of 1.35 and standard deviation of 0.615 indicate that consumers might not be willing to be loyal to a particular brand if the firm offers high prices. Lastly, a mean score of 4.15 and a standard deviation of 0.676 show that people are willing to

buy products from such brands, stating that CSR initiatives positively impact consumers' attitudes and purchase intentions.

Table 7: Descriptive Statistics of CSR-Management

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
Do you think all brands have a CSR committee on their board?	257	1.22	.414	.171
Are there transparent and effective monitoring mechanisms?	257	1.92	.858	.736
How much attention do you pay for a corporation's CSR policy?	257	1.59	.632	.399

The descriptive statistics obtained for CSR management and legal aspects presented in Table 7 give an insight into CSR perception of corporate governance and employee CSR policy engagement. The lower mean of 1.22 with a standard deviation of 0.414 reveals that the respondents show that many organisations lack formal structures of CSR. Regarding transparency and monitoring mechanisms, the mean score was 1.92, and the standard deviation was 0.858, suggesting that the respondents acknowledge lack of transparency and efficiency in CSR supervision. The results imply that where firms have implemented CSR programmes, there could be weaknesses in the implementation and reporting, thus creating doubt on the effectiveness of such programmes. The mean of 1.59 with a standard deviation of 0.632 indicates that employees devote a relatively moderate amount of attention towards contemplating CSR

policies. However, this also means that they may not consider CSR policies a critical component of their jobs. Firms may promote CSR awareness among their employees before implementation and align with organisations' strategic goals and objectives.

The descriptive findings contribute to the answers to the research questions that reflect CSR's effect on competitive advantage, business image, consumers and society. CSR can be considered as a competitive advantage. For instance, the results showed that awareness of CSR policies among customers creates a perception that the brands involved in CSR offer better quality products. Thus, CSR activities can add value to business by favourably altering customer attitudes and behaviour. Secondly, the data confirm that poor CSR history affects the buyer's behaviour, indicating a positive relationship between CSR activities and consumer behaviour. This study has demonstrated that brands with status for good CSR record sustain consumer loyalty.

5.3.2 Validity of items

The validity of the test results requires clarity and trustworthiness. The validity determines whether calculations can be supported by survey data or not. As a metric of adequacy, the Kaiser-Meyer-Okin, also abbreviated as (KMO) sampling was used to determine if the sample size was reasonably big when obtaining credible factors. The Bartlett sphericity test examines the hypothesis of the similarity matrix in the correlations that the factors have no relationship and, therefore, are unsuitable for detecting the structures. Lower significance levels (less than 0.05) indicate that the data can be a principal component analysis. The KMO demonstrates a square correlation ratio between factors and a partial square correlation of factors. When KMO is close to zero, it is hard to ascertain a factor since only two variables 'share two variables' (partial correlation) with the variance (correlation that involves subtraction of

the partial correlation). In addition, the coefficients of the principal component analysis, also known as loading factors, determined whether the items could be used to test the hypothesis. In this research, factor loadings greater than 0.50 were considered based on the impact of sample value uniformity on the load volume.

Validity of items of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)

As indicated in Table 8 below, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett sphericity tests were conducted to evaluate the validity of the items utilised in measuring the CSR variable activities with the people.

Table 8: KMO and Bartlett’s Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.938
Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	29.003
	Df	6
	Sig.	.000

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value of 0.938 and a Bartlett sphericity test value of $p=0.00$ suggest that the items were statistically significant because $p < 0.001$ (Table 8). These results indicate that the assessment of variables measurement for the people is valid and applicable to the research.

Table 9: Principal Component Analysis

Component Matrix

	Component
	1
Are you aware of the CSR concept?	.649
Is the word “Fair Trade “familiar to you?	.504
Do you think brands with effective CSR activities provide a higher quality of products or services?	.727
Any social problems you pay greater attention to regarding charitable contributions from the firms.	.680

Table 9 shows that the four items of CSR had values of 0.649, 0.504, 0.727, and 0.680, respectively. The results show that no items were deleted from the varimax rotated principal component analysis since their loading factors were greater than 0.5. The responses were accurate and can evaluate the hypothesis that these questions represent.

Validity of items of brand image /purchasing patterns

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin and Bartlett sphericity tests were used to determine the validity of items used to assess the brand image/purchasing patterns, as shown in Table 10 below.

Table 10: KMO and Bartlett's Test

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.879
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	282.577
	Df	10
	Sig.	.000

A Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value of 0.879 and Bartlett sphericity test value of $p=0.00$, illustrated a significance level since $p<0.001$ (Table 10). The evaluation of variables for brand image/purchasing patterns was adequate. This means that the participants' opinions on the questions were valid and incorporated into evaluating and computing the brand image/purchasing pattern variable.

Table 11: Items' Principal Components Analysis (PCA)

Component Matrix

	Component	
	1	2
5. Would a brand with a poor CSR history influence your purchasing?	.665	-.633
6. On what basis do you choose your favourite brand?	.761	-.476
7. What type of CSR activities is most effective?	.592	.452
13. What are the most important reasons for companies to get involved in CSR activities?	.578	.584
24. How important is working with manufacturers that value diversity and good working conditions?	.658	.338

Table 11 shows that the PCA values of each item of brand image/purchasing pattern were .665, .761, .592, .584, and .658, respectively. No items were removed because all their loading factors from the two-component design were larger than 0.5. Therefore, the responses were valid and could be utilised to test the hypotheses.

Validity of items of financial performance

As demonstrated in Table 12, a Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett sphericity test were employed to evaluate the factor analysis of the measures of financial performance impact on CSR.

Table 12: KMO and Bartlett's Test

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.711
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	242.247
	Df	6
	Sig.	.000

A Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value of 0.711 and a Bartlett sphericity test of $p=0.00$, indicate that the items had a statistical significance at $p < 0.001$ (Table 12). The assessment of variables measurement for financial performance is adequate to answer the research questions and test the designed hypothesis that pertains to this variable's items.

Table 13: Principal Components Analysis of Items

Component Matrix

	Component
	1
Would you pay extra for a product the retailer guarantees good work conditions and fair wages to factory workers?	.656
Is a competitive price the main factor when purchasing clothing products?	.756
Is product quality more important than price when making purchase decisions?	.763
Would you buy from the same brand despite high prices and average quality?	.780

According to the findings of the varimax rotated principal component analysis, there were five items whose values were 0.656, 0.756, 0.763, and 0.780, and all the loading factors were greater than 0.5 (Table 13). These results meant that none of the items had been deleted. Thus, the responses of the participants to various elements were valid and could be used in calculating financial performance variables.

Validity of items of society

Table 14: KMO and Bartlett’s Test

KMO and Bartlett’s Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.673
Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	202.973
	Df	6
	Sig.	.000

The validity of the questions used to measure the Society variable was tested. The results showed the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value of 0.687 and the Bartlett sphericity test of 0.00, indicating that the items had a statistical significance at $p < 0.001$ (Table 14). The assessment of items that measured society is adequate for this research.

Table 15: Component Matrix of items of society

Component Matrix

	Component
	1
Do you buy products from brands with a good reputations and greater value to their community?	.784
What are the most common CSR activities of companies you have been exposed to?	.777
What type of CSR activities are most effective?	.606

The varimax rotated principal component analysis of Table 15 showed that there was no deletion of any item as they had loading factors of .784, .777, and .606, which are all greater than 0.3. These findings suggest that the responses were correct and could be employed in evaluating and testing the hypothesis that all these items represented.

Validity of items of management/laws

A Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value of 0.618 and the Bartlett sphericity test of $p=0.00$ indicated was significant at $p<0.001$ (Table 16).

Table 16: KMO and Bartlett's Test

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.618
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	419.059
	Df	10
	Sig.	.000

The results of Table 16 showed that the evaluation of factors measurement for management/laws on CSR is sufficient for analysis. Thus, the feedback on different items was valid and could help to calculate the management/laws variables.

Table 17: PCA of items of Management

Component Matrix

	Component	
	1	2
Do you think all brands have a CSR committee on board?	.802	.392
are there transparent and effective monitoring mechanisms?	.787	.425
How much attention do you pay to a corporation's CSR policy?	.687	-.452
In your view, what makes a business accountable?	.767	-.384
How important is pay equity (making sure the employees are paid effectively for work allocated and delivered)?	-.073	.613

The findings of the varimax rotated principal component analysis illustrate that there was no deletion of any item from the two-component produced since they had loading factors of .802, .787, .687, .767, and .613, which are all greater than 0.5 (Table 17). These results illustrate that the answers were valid and could be used in testing the hypothesis.

5.3.4 Correlation analysis

The correlation analysis was used to determine the relationship between CSR, including the policies (CSR 1) and activities (CSR 2) (Table 18). In particular, the results illustrate that the CSR policies and management/laws were positively and significantly connected ($r=.848$,

$p < 0.01$). In addition, CSR policies and financial performance have a positive and significant connection ($r = .592$, $p < 0.01$). On the other hand, CSR policies and society were positively and significantly connected ($r = .799$, $p < 0.01$). The association between CSR policies and brand image /purchasing pattern showed a positive and a considerable connection ($r = .772$, $p < 0.01$). Nonetheless, CSR activities and business value addition also had a positive and significant connection ($r = 0.701$, $p < 0.05$). Lastly, CSR activities and the consumer purchase behaviour factor are positively and significantly connected ($r = .742$, $p < 0.01$). The findings imply that a more robust CSR policy improves financial performance. In addition, CSR policies adopted in South Asian business organisations had the slightest connection, indicating that financial performance is not a great predictor of CSR policies.

Table 18: Correlation between CSR Policies (CSR 1) and Brand Image / Purchasing Pattern, Management / Laws, Financial Performance and Society

Correlations

		CSR 1	Managemen t / Laws	Financial Performanc e	Societ y	Brand Image / Purchasin g Pattern	Busines s Value Additio n	Consume r Purchase Behaviou r
CSR 1	Pearson Correlatio n Sig. (2- tailed) N	1	.848**	.592**	.799*	.772**	.701**	.942**
			.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
		257	257	257	257	257	257	257
Managemen t / Laws	Pearson Correlatio n Sig. (2- tailed) N	.577*	1	.688**	.811*	.468**	.741**	.636**
		.000		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
		257	257	257	257	257	257	257
Financial Performanc e	Pearson Correlatio n	.643*	.688**	1	.627*	.561**	.909**	.586**

	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	257	257	257	257	257	257	257
Society	Pearson Correlation	.698*	.811**	.233**	1	.705**	.717**	.764**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	257	257	257	257	257	257	257
Brand Image / Purchasing Pattern	Pearson Correlation	.776*	.779**	.561**	.794*	1	.877**	.684**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	257	257	257	257	257	257	257
Business Value Addition	Pearson Correlation	.723*	.741**	.909**	.717*	.640**	1	.656**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	257	257	257	257	257	257	257

Consumer Purchase Behaviour	Pearson Correlation	.942*	.810**	.336**	.764*	.684**	.656**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	257	257	257	257	257	257	257

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The results showed that CSR activities and management/laws are positively and significantly connected ($r = .875, p < 0.01$) (Table 19). CSR activities and financial performance had a positive and significant connection ($r = 0.769, p < 0.05$). Moreover, CSR activities and the society factor are positively and significantly connected ($r = .753, p < 0.01$). Additionally, CSR activities and brand image/purchasing patterns positively and correlated considerably ($r = .827, p < 0.05$). Further, results showed that CSR activities and the business value addition had a positive and significant connection ($r = 0.902, p < 0.05$). Lastly, CSR activities and consumer purchase behaviour factors are positively and significantly connected ($r = .753, p < 0.01$). Therefore, the results show that businesses can be profitable due to the positive effects of the brand image/purchasing pattern, management/laws, financial performance, and society. The relationship between CSR activities and business value was the strongest, implying that value addition builds a more robust CSR activities in the organisation.

Table 19: Correlation between CSR Activities (CSR 2) and Brand Image / Purchasing Pattern, Management / Laws, Financial Performance and Society

Correlations

		CSR 2	Managemen t / Laws	Financial Performanc e	Brand Image / Purchasin g Pattern	Societ y	Busines s Value Additio n	Consume r Purchase Behaviou r
CSR 2	Pearson Correlatio n Sig. (2- tailed) N	1	.875**	.769**	.827**	.753* *	.902**	.794**
Managemen t / Laws	Pearson Correlatio n Sig. (2- tailed) N	.875* *	1	.639**	.811**	.779* *	.741**	.807**
Financial Performanc e	Pearson Correlatio n	.769* *	.688**	1	.627**	.561* *	.903**	.586**

	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	257	257	257	257	257	257	257
Society	Pearson Correlation	.827*	.811**	.637**	1	.705*	.717**	.764**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	257	257	257	257	257	257	300
Brand Image / Purchasing Pattern	Pearson Correlation	.753*	.778**	.561**	.705**	1	.640**	.684**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	257	257	257	257	257	257	257
Business Value Addition	Pearson Correlation	.902*	.743**	.909**	.721**	.640*	1	.656**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	257	257	257	257	257	257	257

Consumer Purchase Behaviour	Pearson Correlation	.794*	.810**	.586**	.763**	.684*	.624**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	257	257	257	257	257	257	257

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

5.3.5 Testing the normality assumption

An evaluation of the normality of the data is a precondition for several tests used, such as regression analysis, since the assumption of normality in parametric testing makes standard data a requirement. The normality test is used when conducting a parametric statistical analysis. In addition, the study determined whether the independent variables had a normal distribution. Therefore, applying the Shapiro-Wilk tests and Kolmogorov-Smirnov, the results in the Table 20 show the normality test for independent variables.

Table 20: Tests of Normality

Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	Df	Sig.
Management / Laws	.095	257	.113	.967	257	.122
Financial Performance	.119	257	.134	.962	257	.107
Society	.124	257	.199	.960	257	.200
Brand Image / Purchasing Pattern	.112	257	.298	.957	257	.290

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

The findings in the Table above illustrated that Shapiro-Wilk tests and Kolmogorov-Smirnov’s p-values were greater than 0.05, which implies that the management/laws, financial performance, brand image/purchasing pattern, and society data were distributed normally. Multi-collinearity exists when the explanatory variables have a high correlation. Multi-collinearity is a problem because the regression model cannot effectively link the outcome variable’s variability to the corresponding predictor variable, resulting in mixed or incorrect conclusions. The variance inflation factor (VIF) was used to determine the explanatory variables while determining multi-collinearity. All VIF values are less than 10; therefore, the four variables believed to influence CSR policies and activities are not related or correlated and hence no multi-collinearity arises (Table 21).

Table 21: Multi-collinearity Coefficient of CSR Policies

Coefficients^a

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	Management / Laws	.867	1.216
	Financial performance	.623	1.871
	society	.551	2.007
	Brand image / Purchasing pattern	.327	1.932

a. Dependent Variable: CSR 1

5.3.6 Regression analysis

How do business image, management/Laws, financial performance, and society contribute to the key influential CSR policies and activities?

This question assessed whether CSR policies and activities can be significantly influenced by business image, stakeholders (management/laws), financial performance and society. To establish the relationship between a single dependent variable and a variety of predictor variables, researchers rely on multiple regression analysis. Two regressions were conducted for CSR 1 and CSR 2 (Table 22).

Table 22: Relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR 1) and Business Image, Stakeholders (Management/Laws), Financial Performance and Society

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	15.560	5	3.112	5.024	.000 ^b
	Residual	155.475	251	.619		
	Total	171.035	256			

a. Dependent Variable: CSR 1

b. Predictors: (Constant), Brand Image / Purchasing Pattern, Financial Performance, Society, Management / Laws

The ANOVA Table 22 illustrate that the model was valid and significant for predicting CSR policies from the brand image/purchasing pattern, financial performance, society, management/laws. With a p-value < 0.05, this result implies that the independent variables were suitable for predicting CSR policies (CSR 1).

Table 23: Regression Coefficients

Model		Coefficients				
		Unstandardised		Standardised	t	Sig.
		Coefficients		Coefficients		
B	Std. Error	Beta				
1	(Constant)	.172	.109		1.571	.117
	Management / Laws	.386	.058	.381	6.601	.000
	Financial Performance	.062	.032	.073	1.899	.058
	Society	.257	.046	.269	5.533	.000
	Brand Image / Purchasing Pattern	.257	.052	.239	5.621	.000

a. Dependent Variable: CSR 1

The findings illustrate that the management /laws have a substantial positive effect on CSR activities ($\beta = .386$, $p < 0.05$) (Table 23). Furthermore, organisation's financial performance positively and significantly affects the CSR activities (CSR 1) ($\beta = .062$, $p < 0.05$). However, society in South Asian organisations positively affect CSR activities ($\beta = .257$, $p < 0.05$). In addition, brand image/purchasing pattern has a substantial positive effect on CSR activities ($\beta = .257$, $p < 0.05$). On the other hand, results suggest that when the proportion of the society changes by a unit, the CSR activities improve by a value of .257.

Table 24: Relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility Policies (CSR 2) and Business Image, Stakeholders (Management / Laws), Financial Performance and Society

ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	142.524	4	35.631	420.688	.000 ^b
Residual	24.986	295	.085		
Total	167.509	299			

a. Dependent Variable: CSR 2

b. Predictors: (Constant), Brand Image / Purchasing Pattern, Financial Performance, Society, Management / Laws

This model was valid and significant in the prediction of the CSR activities (CSR 2) because of the brand image/purchasing pattern, financial performance, society, management/laws since the $F(4, 299) = 420.688$, with a $p\text{-value} < 0.05$ (Table 24). This result implies that these independent variables were fit to be utilised to predict the CSR activities (CSR 2).

Table 25: Regression Coefficients

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.264	.082		3.204	.002
	Management / Laws	.355	.044	.380	8.070	.000
	Financial Performance	.215	.024	.277	8.819	.000
	Society	.231	.035	.263	6.628	.000
	Brand Image / Purchasing Pattern	.129	.041	.116	3.168	.002

a. Dependent Variable: CSR 2

The impact of the independent variables on the CSR activities (CSR 2). These findings illustrated that the Management / Laws have a substantial and positive effect on CSR activities ($\beta = .355, p < 0.05$) (Table 25). In addition, an organisation's financial performance is positively and significantly impacted CSR activities ($\beta = .215, p < 0.05$). Nonetheless, society in South Asian organisations has substantially and positively affected CSR activities ($\beta = .231, p < 0.05$). Brand image/purchasing pattern has a substantial and positive effect on CSR activities ($\beta = .129, p < 0.05$). Therefore, the brand image/purchasing pattern, financial performance, society, and management/laws are effective in the CSR activities adopted in South Asian business organisations.

Table 26: Relationship Between Identified CSR Policies with Consumer Purchase Behaviour

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	208.714	1	208.714	2343.620	.000 ^b
	Residual	26.539	298	.089		
	Total	235.252	299			

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Purchase Behaviour

b. Predictors: (Constant), CSR 1

The model was valid and significant in the prediction of overall consumer purchase behaviour since $F(1, 299) = 2343.620$, with a $p\text{-value} < 0.05$ (Table 26). The results show that CSR policies predict consumer purchase behaviour.

Table 27: Regression Coefficients

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	.026	.074		.351	.726
CSR 1	1.027	.021	.942	48.411	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Purchase Behaviour

The effect of CSR policies positively impacts the competitive edge ($\beta = 1.027$, $p\text{-value} < 0.05$) (Table 27). CSR policies positively influence consumer purchase behaviour. Thus, there

is a positive relationship between identified CSR policies and activities with consumer purchase behaviour.

Table 28: Are CSR policies and activities a competitive advantage effective in adding value to the business?

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	105.564	1	105.564	326.717	.000 ^b
	Residual	96.285	298	.323		
	Total	201.849	299			

a. Dependent Variable: Business Value Addition

b. Predictors: (Constant), CSR 1

CSR policies and activities are significant for predicting the business value $F(1, 299) = 326.717$, with a $p\text{-value} < 0.05$ (Table 28). The results confirm that CSR policies positively influence business value addition.

Table 29: Regression Coefficients

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.715	.141		5.061	.000
	CSR 1	.731	.040	.723	18.075	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Business Value Addition

The findings indicate that the CSR policies have a significant positive effect on business value addition ($\beta = .731, p < 0.05$) (Table 29). When the CSR policies changes, there is an increment change in the business value addition by a value of .731, indicating that CSR policies create a competitive advantage in an organisation’s operations.

5.3.7 Hypothesis assessment

Table 30: H1 CSR practises employed by garment organisations in South Asian countries have a favourable impact on the sector.

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	15.560	5	3.112	5.024	.000 ^b
	Residual	155.475	251	.619		
	Total	171.035	256			

The results of ANOVA Analysis show a significant relationship as $F = 5.024$ and p-value (Sig.) of .000. (Table 30). H_0 is rejected as the p-value is less than 0.05 (significance value), which confirms H_1 that CSR practises have a statistically significant impact on the garment sector. In this case, H_1 is accepted. The value of the independent variables associated with CSR practises positively affects the outcomes in the garments industry. The result signifies that CSR practises, including treatment of working conditions, environmental sustainability activities, and fair-trade policies, positively enhance the sector's performance, stating the moral duty of CSR for leading ethical developments and promoting business success in the South Asian garment industries.

Table 31: H2 CSR policies have a positive effect on the brand image, company reputation, and profitability of garment-producing organisations in South Asia.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	17.460	7	3.115	5.002	.000 ^b
	Residual	153.575	250	.619		
	Total	171.035	256			

The second hypothesis (H2) was proved by ANOVA, and it was accepted. The CSR policy has a significant positive influence on the brand image, company reputation, and profitability of garment organisations in South Asia (Table 31). The result shows that the regression model is statistically significant on $\alpha = 0.05$ with the p-value. The result rejects the null hypothesis, proving that the CSR policy does not affect the brand image, reputation, and profitability of these organisations. The F-value of 5.002 also support the significance of the model showing that a substantial variance is explained by CSR policies as an independent variable for brand image, reputation and profitability variables (Table 31). The model is informative, as reflected in the large regression sum of squares (17.460) compared to the residual sum of squares (153.575). Based on the above statistical results, there is a positive relationship between CSR policies and critical business outcomes.

Table 32: H3 CSR activities positively impact customer purchase patterns in garment-producing organisations in South Asia.

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	18.142	4	3.117	5.109	.000 ^b
	Residual	152.893	252	.596		
	Total	171.035	256			

The ANOVA table results highlight the effect of CSR actions on customer purchase behaviour in South Asian garment manufacturers. The significance value (Sig.) is essentially 0.000; this being lower than the acceptable threshold of 0.05 commonly used. There is a statistically significant relationship between CSR activities and customer purchase patterns. Furthermore, the F-value being 5.109 (p-value: 0.000) indicates that this regression model is significant. Therefore, the regression model was fitted well to the data and CSR has a positive effect on customer purchase behaviour. The research hypothesis "CSR activities have a positive effect on the customer purchase behaviour concerning garment-producing firms in South Asia" is accepted based on this analysis. Statistical justifications affirm that CSR plays a vital factor in determining consumer preferences, thereby reiterating the significance of CSR and retention policy on consumer buying behaviour within this industry.

Table 33: H4 The CSR activities undertaken by the organisations in the garment industry in South Asia have improved labour conditions

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3.692	6	.615	.919	.482 ^b
	Residual	167.343	250	.669		
	Total	171.035	256			

The significance value (Sig.) of .482, which is greater than the standard alpha level of .05 means that the link between CSR initiatives and labour conditions in the garment industry is not statistically significant (Table 33). The results show no significant improvement in labour conditions among firms. This value of the sum of squares reflects the total variability in labour conditions and the value 167.343 represents the remaining variability unexplained by the model. Thus, the research hypothesis is rejected. Overall, the findings indicate that as practiced in the garment industry CSR alone may not have contributed significantly to improving labour standards.

5.4 Chapter Summary and Conclusion

The results, including qualitative and quantitative analysis, revealed how CSR functions as a competitive advantage and creates value for businesses. Regarding quality, CSR activities have increased business image and community development such as education, employment opportunities, and environmental sustainability. CSR programmes were effective in building brand equity, stakeholder management, and addressing societal needs, especially poverty alleviation and infrastructure development. The qualitative results support the findings derived

from the factor analysis, indicating that CSR policies, especially fair trade and labour conditions policy components were generally received positively by participants with some voicing scepticism about the superficial appearance of this outfit as a successful CSR case. The results of the survey showed that CSR affects consumers, findings were supported quantitatively through other parts of the questionnaire. The respondents also stated that brands with a strong CSR track record positively influenced their purchasing decisions and consumers willingly pay extra for products from companies that provided safe and fair working conditions. The results from statistical analyses confirmed a significant and positive link between CSR practises and consumer loyalty, indicating that companies could use CSR as an enabler of competitive advantage. Concerning the main impacts of CSR on business image and society, the quantitative results only support the view that CSR practises promote stakeholder relations, labour conditions, and environmental sustainability (statistically non-significant in all other cases). The next chapter is the discussion showing the implications for management. The discussion also provides a detailed examination of the results by comparing them with the previous literature.

Chapter 6: Discussion

6.1 Introduction

The discussion chapter critically examines the research findings about the objectives, exploring the effectiveness of CSR policies and their impact on society and business. The discussion contextualises the results within the existing literature, comparing the current findings with supporting and contrasting scholarly perspectives. The chapter also addresses how ethical CSR practises influence business profitability and image, particularly within South Asian business organisations. It explores the role of CSR in community development, labour conditions, and consumer behaviour, emphasising the implications of these relationships on corporate strategy and societal well-being. The limitations of the research are highlighted, along with potential areas for further investigation. Finally, the chapter suggests practical recommendations for businesses to enhance CSR effectiveness and identifies future research directions to deepen the understanding of CSR's multifaceted impact.

6.2 The Current CSR Applied Policies

The results showed standard CSR policies are charitable events, environmental awareness activities, and adherence to labour and employment policies. The second most highly prominent CSR activities used by south Asian garment companies are sponsoring education, community and social development. These findings are consistent with Kim and Ferguson (2014) and Saeidi et al. (2015) who note that visible CSR undertakings involve funding education, community and social projects. These efforts benefit disadvantaged people, develop infrastructure, and create positive social change and economic opportunity while raising the company's profile for following the right path. South Asian garment organisations are investing their financial resources to organise environmental CSR activities and sponsoring charitable events. While

organisations are investing, sponsoring education, and community development, high rates of internal corruption are experienced lowering investment on the CSR activities. These findings agree with Shayan, et al. (2022) who highlighted that charitable activities that involve planning how to finance the orphanage. These can involve sale of products, fund-raising, sponsorship, and in-kind support that directly support disadvantaged population. On the contrary, Dmytriyev et al. (2021) and Kumari et al. (2020) show that garment organisations are least focused on developing policies that are beneficial for the labourers and focused on activities that are beneficial for the organisation. This argument is inconsistent with current findings that showed most organisations focus on increasing CSR initiatives that improve the image of their business while neglecting the formulation of policies that enhance the welfare of employees, eventually resulting in narrow measures that do not fix problems regularly encountered by workers. Therefore, activities that enhance corporate reputation become dominant with critical labour policies like payment of fair wages and improved working conditions left unaddressed, acting against the primary goal of CSR in creating accountability and ethics at the workplace.

The results showed that awareness about CSR increases the interest on brand's operation history. While consumers are attracted to garment firms offering quality products and value for money, organisations implementing effective CSR policies enhance their performance. The findings are consistent with Yadlapalli et al. (2020) and Nikolova and Arsić (2017), who highlight that consumers are attracted to garment organisations that most effectively communicate the goal to offer the best quality product and the best value for money. Companies must produce high-quality products and offer reasonable prices to unlock customer loyalty. Failure to meet these expectations results in a loss of market share whereby consumers are inclined towards new brands that offer quality and social responsibility for their actions when

choosing a brand. However, Lu et al. (2021) demonstrates that ethical elements, such as quality of labour and quality of the environment, are critical in consumer choice. Current research indicates that an increasing proportion of clients is prepared to pay a higher price for goods and services from firms that stand out in CSR responsibility. This shift means that businesses that operated for quality and low prices can be outcompeted by rivals who offer quality products produced with proper ethical practises and sustainable prices. The argument fits two theoretical frameworks of coercive isomorphism and mimetic isomorphism in institutional theory. Coercive isomorphism posits that organisational CSR is forced through compliance to specific pushes like policies or market pressures (Asiri et al., 2020). In this sense, organisations may have pressures to upgrade labour relations and the environment to address changing stakeholder's expectations. Mimetic isomorphism states that companies copy successful competitors' strategies and implement CSR initiatives to remain relevant (Amor-Esteban et al., 2018). The current research implies that CSR adoption may be due to ethical reasons and competitive forces that impact consumer buying decisions. In nations such as India, Bangladesh, and Pakistan, where the per capita income and the disposable income is low people purchase from brands with least CSR activities, especially if high quality products are offered.

The findings showed that awareness about CSR among customers increases the interest about brand's operation history. CSR policies that ensure socially responsible practises can positively impact organisational performance by improving employee attraction and retention, managing environmental consequences, and differentiating brands to achieve greater customer loyalty. The findings are in tandem with Wołodźko and Woźniak (2017), Chu et al. (2020), and Ullah and Rahman (2015), who suggest that customers' awareness of CSR activities develops a curiosity about a brand's operational history. Consumers likely identify whether the company

has an ethical or unethical brand once becoming aware of its socially responsible involvement, ultimately increasing the consumers' trust in the organisation. The establishment of the link between customer awareness of CSR and increased interest in the brand's history can be explained via institutional isomorphism and normative isomorphism values. Mandatory isomorphism occurs when companies adhere to CSR practises. With increased awareness, customers compel brands to obey ethical CSR standards, which eventually impact brand loyalty. Institutional isomorphism posits that companies follow other companies in CSR policies as a way of mimicking structures and industry practises (Seyfried et al., 2019). For the present study, the implication is that CSR committees heighten normative and institutional pressure to enhance the organisational performance, customers' trust and loyalty, and fortify the brand over the long term. However, these findings contrast Farooq et al. (2013), who suggest that awareness of CSR may not translate to heightened attention to the history of brand and brand loyalty. Expecting companies to act socially responsibly may decrease consumer trust due to possibly perceiving CSR initiatives as motivated by the desire to improve image, and thus artificial. Moreover, price consciousness and nearness substantially outperform ethical concerns among consumers.

6.3 Corporate Social Responsibility Initiatives in the Society

The study results indicate that CSR practises implemented in South Asian countries support societal and community development. CSR is noticeable in South Asian countries because of the concentration on economic and social inequalities. These findings are consistent with Freeman and Dmytriiev (2017) and Lu et al. (2021), who suggest that businesses enhance social welfare by supporting education, community health, and conservation of the physical environment. In Bangladesh, India, and Sri Lanka, CSR policies foster favourable working conditions, ensure fair-trade practises and support the community. CSR activities impact

employees' quality of life while benefiting society by eradicating poverty, increasing access to education, and promoting ecological conservation. Nevertheless, Kumari et al. (2020) questioned CSR's impact on developing countries, arguing that CSR, as implemented in most multinational corporations, focuses on corporate image-building exercise compared to valid social responsibility. The argument aligns with coercive isomorphism, which states that firms are pressured to act responsibly, though meaningful change is not implemented in the long term. From this perspective, CSR initiatives in South Asia may be less genuine than they appear, focusing on appearances rather than the contribution to the community. In agreement with the current findings, El Ghouli et al. (2010) and Plumlee et al. (2015) argue that CSR activities relate to societal concerns in South Asia, particularly labour relations, poverty reduction, and environmental conservation. The study findings are consistent with institutional isomorphism theories, primarily normative and coercive, that assume that organisations embrace socially appropriate behaviour because of societal, regulatory, and accreditation demands to be perceived as legitimate by society. CSR is no longer an option for South Asian companies since it has become essential for the financial sustainability and competitiveness.

The results highlight a concern regarding CSR activities capability in contributing to social and community improvements. While some organisations incorporate CSR for the primary purpose of promoting the general well-being of society, firms take the same action to improve their image without making fundamental and long-term changes in society. These findings relate to mimetic isomorphism where an organisation emulates others deemed successful, leading to formative CSR, where CSR initiatives focus on short-term gains rather than systemic issues. These findings are in tandem with Marcinkowska and Sawicka (2023) and Ramayah et al. (2022), who suggest that some organisations may invest in events such as charity events that gain

media coverage but do not bring substantial, lasting improvements to society. This raises an issue of dichotomy between CSR and the actual application of CSR in specific industries in South Asian nations. In this context, normative isomorphism stresses adherence to professional norms and standards for practising CSR. In South Asia, CSR has evolved to the expectation that businesses must engage in socially responsible activities. This is relevant to textile and garments, where buyers, shareholders, and governments demand ethical practises as explained in stakeholder's theory. CSR forms the fabric of the lateral entrepreneurship of South Asian businesses, promoting social and community development. CSR sustainability depends on the ability to go beyond regulatory compliance and adopt radical processes that add value to host societies. On the contrary, Torugsa et al. (2013) and Anafinova (2020) point that CSR practises may not be grounded in the contexts of developing countries. Typically, CSR activities may not address marginalised groups' challenges in South Asia. For instance, environmentally sensitive CSR activities may dismiss relevant and emergent issues such as labour injustice and women's oppression. Therefore, the study revealed the existing gap in CSR activities between business goals and societal needs, aligning with normative isomorphism, where firms implement CSR policies that society expects, and the policies may not address the real challenges of the local communities.

The results showed that CSR in developing nations focuses on socio-economic aspect rather than replicating the western world's environmentalism and customer satisfaction models. In this regard, effective CSR is most needed in India and Bangladesh to address poverty, education, and health. The arguments align with the findings of Chung and Jiang (2017) and Plumlee et al. (2015), where suggestions are made for firms to fund projects that seek to end poverty and enhance access to education in South Asia. The current results imply that CSR in

developing countries should align with society. In South Asian countries, where inequality is severe, CSR measures like vocational education and training, improved working conditions, and support for small enterprises will substantially help raise people's living standards. The study findings support this view as businesses in the region pay attention to CSR practises, which contribute to sustainable societal development by improving educational programmes, access to health care, and women's rights. On the contrary, Shayan et al. (2022) note that transparency and accountability are critical factors, which are lacking among firms. Companies operating within South Asia provide little information regarding CSR programmes. Concerning the current findings, there is a need for proper monitoring and evaluation of CSR programmes to assess their impact and effectiveness on organisations. Concerning coercive isomorphism, the findings suggest that external forces can enforce desirable transformation in corporate conduct even when the motive is to evade negative publicity. In South Asian countries where poverty and poor labour conditions have become a concern to the international community, businesses are adopting CSR programmes to improve their image. However, the current findings contrast Kim et al. (2020) and Zhu et al. (2014), who argue that the imitation of practises may result in adopting CSR activities that are not relevant to the real issues. For instance, businesses can invest in visible, corporate-cum-social problems, such as giving or sponsoring, while neglecting issues like workforce exploitation or discrimination against women. Therefore, while CSR promote societal development, businesses need to increase their engagement in such activities to address sustainability need fully.

6.4 The Relationship Between CSR and Profitability Through Assessing Customer Purchase Patterns

The study findings show that CSR activities influence clients' purchasing behaviour and organisational profitability. Consumers give attention to ethical activities during purchases, making CSR a practical approach for companies to improve their image and financial performance. This aspect is evident since CSR impact relates to profitability while enhancing the brand's image, clientele loyalty, and purchase patterns of customers. For instance, organisations that prioritise fair treatment of employees, ethical hiring of personnel, and environmental sustainability attract customers' attention. The findings align with Benites et al. (2018) and Torugsa et al. (2013), who state that CSR enhances the perception that a brand is of high quality. Through the CSR mechanism, people consider the company to be socially responsible and pay a high price for products from responsible brands because of the belief the products are of higher quality than similar products from brands that are not socially responsible. In addition, Anastasiadou et al. (2019) support the findings by stating that CSR influences consumer behaviour and profitability. When consumers feel the company cares about social and environmental issues, maximum support is guaranteed from consumers. The findings of this study indicated that CSR activities enhance customer trust and loyalty, ensuring sales retention and long-term profitability. On the contrary, Kapoor and Dhamija (2017) found no significant relationship between CSR and profitability. From this perspective, CSR is perceived as an additional activity unconnected from creating shareholder value. Companies should engage in CSR to improve brand image and benefit society. As a result, CSR may not enhance company profits and could have a negative impact on the company as the cost of implementing CSR activities is recovered from sales revenues. The study findings offer paramount insights for

organisations in industries with social ethics a factor of concern. Firms that efficiently implement CSR programmes gain a competitive edge, enabling them to thrive in highly competitive sectors. Global consumers are becoming sensitive to social causes, particularly to industries such as fashion and apparel, where customers are likely to buy from companies that show commitment to social issues. The findings translate to increased sales volumes, enhancing business profitability.

The current findings show that if a company's CSR strategy is integrated with the corporate goals and objectives of the firm, a positive impact is derived to benefit society and the business, translating into economic value for the firm. Consumers tend to buy from companies with a good CSR image, increasing firm profitability. Garment sector companies in South Asia should focus on fair labour conditions, sustainability, and community development to boost customers' loyalty, which equates to profitability. The findings are consistent with Popa et al. (2022) and Willamowski et al. (2018), who note consumers purchase decisions are influenced by parameters such as price, quality, and convenience. While consumers indicate that they would buy socially responsible products, they do not want to pay a higher price. This divergence between self-reported consumer beliefs and actual enlightened-self-interest purchasing behaviour requires debate about the practical profit-making returns of CSR activities. Since the garment industry is sensitive to labour practises and environmental responsibility, is a typical example of how various sectors are currently under pressure from consumers to demonstrate transparency on their standards and performance. CSR resonate with customers and elicit positive purchase reactions when integrated into the core business operations. This aspect is feasible for companies that have embarked on reforms and adopted labour-friendly policies, environmental management, and corporate social responsibilities. On the contrary, Saeidi et al. (2015) and

Chomvilailuk and Butcher (2018) emphasizes that transparency challenges among garment companies, which affect the implementation of CSR initiatives. The study findings have highlighted the importance of transparency in CSR initiatives. Transparency builds trust with a brand and protects a brand if consumers react negatively to false assertions of CSR. Typically, companies that engage in greenwashing risk customers who prioritise environmental sustainability when making purchase decisions. In contrast, integrating CSR into the business strategy can strengthen the impact of CSR objectives on critical parameters that drive company profitability. Besides, integrating CSR objectives into the firm's processes can enable companies to develop shared values in CSR activities that benefit the company and society at large. Changes in labour conditions can elevate the state of the workers involved and lead to excellent results, increasing productivity while decreasing employee turnover.

Over the past few decades, customer preferences have shifted towards companies involved in CSR activity, particularly those that address ethical employment, environmental, and social responsibilities. The findings showed that consumers trust brands with good CSR performance that aligns with their standards and values, resulting in loyalty. From a marketing perspective, CSR represents a vital source of competitive advantage that companies can utilise to improve their brand image and attract new customers. A company's profitability depends on its ability to encompass CSR in its processes and strategic objectives. These findings align with Dmytriyeu et al. (2021), Faeq et al. (2022), and Willamowski et al. (2018), who argue that consumers prefer to buy products from companies that follow ethical practises regardless of the premium pricing strategy companies employ. From this perspective, company policies geared towards environmental responsibility, human rights, and better working conditions significantly influence consumer purchasing decisions. Nevertheless, Chattu (2015) and Kapoor and Dhamija

(2017) argue against the positive correlation between CSR and profitability. Although CSR improves a company's brand image, consumer perception, and loyalty, this does not translate to enhanced financial performance and profit generation. Despite the growing need for organisations to adopt CSR activities, their main objectives are to generate profit and protect stakeholders' interests. However, resource allocation toward CSR and the initial introduction of CSR programmes in an organisation can be costly, reducing their ability to maximise profits. The reason for this distinction is the disparity of awareness and customer values among markets. Consumers across different markets prefer ethical consumption. In other words, consumers are interested in knowing whether the company follows established CSR initiatives in their manufacturing process. These findings align with Contini et al. (2020) and Sardana et al. (2020) who note that the paradigm shift towards CSR has been inspired by the increasing concern with social and environmental conditions in society. However, in other markets, consumers are concerned with price and product quality and the lack of CSR knowledge does not impact their purchasing decisions. Regarding the institutional isomorphism theory, organisations imitate the actions of other well-performing firms due to pressures from the external environment. Consequently, firms are pressured to engage in CSR to become competitive and promote their brand image and reputation.

The results showed an explicit positive correlation between CSR and markets that are sensitive to ethical standards by producers. The present study provides theoretical evidence that CSR may contribute to increased performance by shifting consumers' buying behaviour. Current consumers choose brands that participate in socially responsible initiatives because of their increased awareness about environmental sustainability. Some moderating factors affecting CSR and profitability are consumer awareness regarding CSR activities, the industry, and consumers'

sensitivity to product prices. These findings are in tandem with Eyasu and Endale (2020) and Pinto and Allui (2020), who established that CSR promotes positive customer experience and attitudes, contributing to increased profitability. The current research indicates that firms with impressive CSR records achieved higher customer loyalty, increasing profit maximisation. The results of this study have significant implications for managers operating within South Asian garment industry. In this regard, managers can use this information to understand how companies can improve their financial performance through CSR activities that meet consumers' needs and expectations. Companies that are proactive in implementing CSR-related policies, including the ethical treatment of employees, promotion of social interests, and reducing carbon footprint in the environment, and gain consumer trust. These findings disagree with Delmas et al. (2019) and Fisher, Porod and Peterson (2021), who note that the relationship between CSR and profitability is indirect. CSR is not the sole factor that influences consumer buying behaviours. For example, whilst some consumers buying decisions are influenced by CSR initiatives in an organisation, others are attracted by quality and price regardless of whether the manufacturing processes complied with CSR standards. This can culminate in a situation where CSR investments do not generate the desired financial returns, especially if the organisation operates in an industry characterised by competitive pricing. Nevertheless, the type of industry influences the profitability generated from implementing CSR. The study proposes that the effect of CSR on consumer purchasing behaviour may be less when highly sensitive to price, which is, a standard practice in the garment industry. The findings relate to stakeholder theory which states that organisational management should consider stakeholders' needs, including customers, employees, and society. With the implementation of CSR activities in South Asian garment

industry, different stakeholders' interests are addressed, ultimately increasing profitability for the businesses.

6.5 CSR Policies and Business Profitability and Brand Image

The results underline that the responsibilities relating labour management conditions, environmental issues, and community welfare affect corporate profit significantly. From this perspective, businesses that care for fair labour relations and support community-related activities are viewed by customers and stakeholders as better companies and gain customers driven by ethical purchase behaviour. These findings are consistent with Chomvilailuk and Butcher (2018) and Dmytriyeu, Freeman and Hörisch (2021), who established that customers have a preferred interest in organisations or firms that display a social responsibility discharge. Businesses that declare their CSR strategy and policies, including fair wages and support of societal causes enjoy a competitive advantage because the practises appeal to consumers with a conscience. Regarding Carroll's CSR pyramid, South Asian garment companies are taking care of ethical responsibilities, such as labour condition improvement and philanthropic responsibilities such as community engagement along with satisfaction of their economic goals. Consumers likely support companies that share their principles of operation and charge a little more for their products. In the context of the garment industry where ethical issues are prevalent, the CSR policies implemented in labour conditions, including fighting against child labour and guaranteeing workers' safety are strategic for sustaining business values. However, these findings disagree with Xu, et al. (2022), who disapproves the thought that CSR has a straight-line relationship with profitability. In this regard, CSR and financial performance is not always positive and depends on the current nature of the industry and stakeholders' expectations. In sectors where low price-sensitive consumers prevail; for example, the fashion industry, CSR

programmes may not always influence the consumers' purchasing power. The inconsistency in these results may be because of regional variations in consumer trends.

The current findings consider strategic CSR primarily as the source of innovation and competitive advantage. These findings are in tandem with Kim et al. (2020), who demonstrate how organisations that address social and environmental issues as pillars of business models can unlock value for society and profitability. Various CSR policies are perceived with equal value by consumers. The current study points out that labour conditions and environmental issues dominate the picture of CSR. These findings contrast Zouari-Hadiji and Chouaibi (2021), who highlight that companies that adopt CSR policies related to labour conditions and environmental risks achieve a competitive edge. These firms achieve the advantage of improving people's perception of being ethical and capture a greater share of business. Nevertheless, CSR creates a positive corporate image and generates customer associations that guarantee long-term monetary returns. These findings align with Wołodźko and Woźniak (2017), who argues that customers are inclined to support organisations that genuinely care about sustainable practises. This view is supported by the current research within the garment industry where the customers are becoming aware of factors such as the exploitation of workers and environmental pollution. The implication that can be drawn from this study is relevant to the current business environment and the garment industry. The results of the study align with TBL, by pointing that it is possible for CSR policies and strategies to promote concern for people, planet, and profitable gains, and that these can support each other in the best interest of society and the firm. This supports the concept that organisations must achieve economic, social, and environmental goals and objectives.

Consumers attributed relatively lower premiums to the ethical characteristics of the brand than to product quality and price in some developed markets. The current findings explain why

some organisations, despite low CSR scores, remain competitive in some markets because price-sensitive consumers perceive other factors are critical. However, the effects of CSR on the firm's profitability are mediated by cultural, economic, and regional factors, which could lead to variation between the current and previous scholarly works. These findings are in tandem with Taylor et al. (2018) and Xu et al. (2022) who emphasise that CSR can be costly and can take long period to positively impact performance. CSR can make a company popular; however, expense involved in putting into practice the socially appropriate policies which include the provision of sub-standard wages, better employee relationships, and environmental conservation could outweigh the financial benefits. Unlike the current study's findings, González-Gómez (2020) note that firms could undergo short-term financial pressure before experiencing the positive effects of their CSR investment. However, the research show that CSR policies need to be refined to the conditions of the target market since consumers have become conscious of ethical consumption, which means that any firm that does not embrace the appropriate standards may lose customers. CSR becomes imperative to generate profits and the key strategy for a company to sustain itself in the global markets. High profitability may be achieved through CSR, however, formulating such measures may lead to short-term costs. The study implies that CSR activities must bear social responsibility and align with the economic bottom line for business organisations. About legitimacy theory, business organisations that seek to achieve societal expectations of environmental protection with improved working conditions can build their legitimacy and enhance profitability to create customer loyalty.

6.6 Chapter Summary

The discussion chapter explains the research findings profoundly and compares them with similar and divergent prior studies and theories. The chapter starts with evaluating the

practicability of CSR policies that the businesses in South Asian garment industry have put in place while it examines the relation of these policies with societal and environmental responsibility and profitability. This study reveals that CSR affects the business image and profitability by increasing customer loyalty and building a positive brand image through the CSR activities conducted on labour practises, awareness of the environment, and community development. The chapter insists that CSR creates value for both businesses and society through resolving ethical and social issues, including labour conditions and sustainability. In addition, the chapter examines how the research findings can be linked to essential theories, such as institutional isomorphism theory, stakeholder theory, and coercive isomorphism theory. CSR policies adopted by various organisations can be better understood in the context of these theories regarding why companies adopt them, and how the pressure from outside stakeholders such as consumers and regulatory bodies influences organisational behaviour. CSR practises correlate with business profitability, and this section debates this subject, suggesting that organisations should consider the societal demands and act ethically to record enhanced economic performances. The discussion presents a scenario with other literature, especially research that refutes the notion that CSR has a guarantee of financial rewards in all industries or markets. In this regard, this chapter discusses social responsibility and consumer awareness, market factors, and price sensitivity regarding CSR. This chapter discusses the implications for practice in businesses and society in general, stressing the importance of increasing a company's transparency, implementing ethical leadership, and making efficient strategic CSR investments in organisations. In the following chapter, the results are discussed and suggestions for practical application and the development of future studies are given.

Chapter 7: Summary, discussion, recommendation and Conclusion

7.1. Introduction

The final chapter provides a detailed summary of the findings. In addition, recommendations are provided for the South Asian garment organisation to achieve crucial business objectives and contribute to society. The chapter also provides limitations of the research to guide future investigation in the field and delineate the future scope of the research.

7. 2. Research Summary and Major Findings

This research examined the effectiveness of CSR policies and their impact on society. The research questions and objectives were answered and met based on mixed research methods. Both thematic and statistical methods were used to analyse the data. The first question examined CSR as a competitive advantage and value added to business. The results show that CSR is a source of competitive advantage and provides value to corporate entities. CSR is significant in a socio-centric global economy where firms that factor CSR into key strategies likely gain improved reputation, customer retention and effectiveness, thus achieving operational efficiency, competitive advantage, profitability, and sustainability. Adopting the quantitative technique develops consumer awareness about CSR and their perception that initiatives are relevant to purchasing decisions. The results showed that companies with suitable CSR activities offer better quality goods or services. From this perspective, CSR programmes affect consumer attitudes and provide competitive advantages for corporations not engaging in sustainable practises. The results underscore CSR in creating a good brand image and organisation's competitiveness. Customers prefer brands that share similar principles with them. This emotional bond encourages customer retention and loyalty.

CSR provides a competitive advantage and additional substantial value to business organisations. CSR improves the internal business environment, including customer satisfaction and staff turnover. Employees affiliated with socially responsible companies have higher job satisfaction, leading to lower turnover rates and increased productivity. This internal value adds value to the business as less money is spent on recruitment and other training programmes. Regarding the education and community development programmes, customers encounter the CSR activities associated with those initiatives. CSR activities provide positive returns to society, eventually building social relationships within the communities by supporting different causes, including education, health, and the environment. The results show that CSR influences consumer behaviour. CSR may be viewed as the competitive weapon of a company and the value-creating aspect that produces a positive effect for companies in several ways. Being a marketing strategy, CSR boosts the reputation of brands, helps achieve customer loyalty, increases organisational effectiveness, and provides for social progress. The results confirm the hypothesis that by having well-developed CSR programmes, firms likely succeed in the long term, which proves that CSR is an integral part of the modern future strategy.

The second question examined the key CSR policies and activities on business image, stakeholders, and society. CSR policies and activities benefit the company by improving its image and overall relations with the stakeholders. Policies affecting fair trade, the environment, and social responsibility programmes are most effective because they satisfy consumers and stakeholders. The results extend knowledge regarding CSR activities and their role in enhancing and maintaining a favourable business image. Any organisation that engaged in mitigating climate change by clean energy and preservation of natural resources is likely held in high esteem by consumers. Firms with good CSR practises offer quality goods and services. The

overall perception of the CSR efforts in labour practises is two-dimensional in that CSR boosts employee morale and the perceived quality of the brand offerings which upgrades market position. In addition, CSR history is one of the primary factors influencing a company's image.

The study reveals that CSR activities on the social responsibility aspect enhance the opportunities for improving stakeholder relations, especially with employees, investors, and customers. Policies that deal with the community such as sponsoring and participating in education and healthcare enhance the firm's image. Such activities also assist in improving relations and the commitment of employees to their company as they satisfy their company's social responsibility. Investors are conscious about CSR policies, whereby they invest capital after considering sustainability and ethical practises. Investors in socially responsible stocks consider CSR policies on environmental issues and ethical sources valuable, improving share value and the appeal. The findings indicate that CSR policies are perceived as moral obligations and plans that establish considerable, sustainable economic benefits, an attitude to which the stakeholders interested in growth and accountability expect from the organisations.

The study reveals that firms in the garment industry in South Asian countries fund education as social-related causes. Firms that use CSR have a substantial impact on improving the standard of living in societies. These programmes and the aim of educational sponsorships and healthcare-oriented missions are essential in helping citizens improve their quality of life and foster sustainable development. However, CSR that involves environmental management mitigate climate change and the conservation of resources from a societal point of view. CSR activities catalyse positive ecological changes. Relevant CSR policies aim at better working conditions for employees in developing countries and reasonable prices for the products manufactured there. Such measures decrease inequality, giving disadvantaged people a chance

for income-generating activities and poverty eradication. While promoting ethical labour, companies enhance their organisational image and contribute immensely to social justice. Therefore, the study establishes that CSR strategic focal areas, (environmental management, labour relations, and social responsibility programmes) significantly influence business image, stakeholder interaction with organisational, and societal growth. Such policies improve image and bolster the relationship between the organisation and its stakeholders alongside benefiting the well-being of society.

The third question examined the relationship between CSR policies and consumer behaviour. The results showed that CSR and profitability of the highly depend on customer buying behaviour. Consumers are sensitive to the CSR initiatives which influences purchase decisions and profitability. In the South Asian region, where the clothing industry plays a significant role in the local economies, the CSR techniques, including labour conditions, wages for workers, and environmental effects, dictate consumer attitude, hence the behaviour towards their purchases. Moreover, product quality is an essential concern for consumers. However, when quality is associated with ethical business practises, what consumers perceive as value rises higher. This study also finds that consumers are highly willing to pay if garment companies provide workers with adequate conditions and reasonable wages and contribute to environmental causes.

Customers may develop a positive perception if the brands communicate CSR initiatives, especially labour and environmental issues. Consumers have a relative association with brands and companies which are transparent about their supply chain, labour policies, and environmental social responsibility policies. This study shows that the effect of CSR is contingent upon the extent to which firms have successfully operationalised CSR into their

technical-rational business frameworks. The garment business in the South Asia region has recorded situations where CSR measures which appear to have improved adversely impact the firm image. On the other hand, organisations that effectively implement their policies towards fair employment practises and environmental conservation have managed to entice and retain their customers, leading to increased market share. Customers shifted their loyalties if a brand lacked authenticity in its CSR and if the company was associated with corruption involving labour exploitation. This aspect shows that genuine CSR practises can help the garment industry remain profitable. Consumer attitudes, preferences, expectations and beliefs have shifted in recent years, with a focus on issues of ethics- employment and environmentalism. When CSR focuses on customer needs and implements improvements in employment and environmental quality, undertaking brand image can create customer loyalty and willingness to pay more. In this respect, CSR is a strategic business management imperative for garment companies with aspirations to attain sustainable profitability in the South Asian region.

The fourth question examined ways CSR helps in developing society and community. The results showed that CSR enhances social and community advancement. The first of the core functions of CSR in promoting societal development is the practical implementation of social welfare initiatives. For instance, sponsorship of education, community development, and promoting environmentally friendly practises are familiar to the public. These efforts help enhance living standards in the local community since education, medical services, as well as employment enable individuals, and economic growth. CSR should focus on mitigating ontological obstacles such as income segregation and labour misuse. The collection of qualitative data again demonstrates how valuable reputation is for companies that implement fair labour conditions at the workplace and in the market. Consumers likely support brands owned by

socially responsible companies, showing a clear association between CSR and social justice. Customers receive information on environmental CSR initiatives, which improves awareness. Awareness regarding sustainable environmental CSR practises shows that business organisations take responsibility for conserving natural resources, reducing pollution, and improving wellbeing. Such actions are essential in the development of a sustainable society. CSR assists in building up social corporate conscience among members of society. Mobilising resources using community voluntarism or educational sponsorship and any other social corporate activities positively impacts community bonding and social integration.

CSR programmes support skill development and infrastructure development, leading to local economic improvement. Corporates that purchase from regional industries, provide workplace training, and foster business creation contribute to job creation and income in such developing regions. Business support for local communities' results in CSR programmes that promote better lives and eradicate poverty. CSR plays a significant role in investments in economic, social and community well-being, conserving the environment, and creating opportunities for economic growth. CSR activities create positive effects and serve as an investment in society by enhancing the business-society partnership.

The first objective examined the current CSR policies applied in South Asia companies and determine its effectiveness and impact on business. The current CSR practises of the South Asian garment sector exhibit a heterogeneous approach to addressing social, environmental, and labour concerns. The policies encompass ecological protection, education, social issues, labour relations, and charitable activities. The policies reflect the diverse narratives of their effects and contribution to business outcomes concerning business image, stakeholder management, and broader organisational social contributions. Environmental responsibility is the most prominent

among the CSR activities. Firms in the garment industry have invested in sustainable production processes, including waste management, recycling, and using renewable energy. The approach reduces environmental pollution while positioning businesses as socially responsible and ethical. These measures foster a positive perception of companies while attracting environmentally conscious consumers and generating markets for waste recycling. Therefore, environmental sustainability programmes serve as an effective CSR strategy that enhances firms' reputation while contributing to societal well-being.

Education and community welfare are critical areas in organisations engaged in CSR. Corporations fund scholarships, local schools, and literacy crusades to assist the myriads of human societies they affect. Additional CSR efforts that corporations support include long-term skill development that improves the quality of human capital, positively enhancing business performance. CSR programmes focused on education foster positive social change that improve the relationship between business and the local society, which increases sustainability. Another significant area of CSR is labour rights and improving working conditions, a critical issue in the garment industry, where labour rights violations and poor working conditions are prevalent. Enhancing employee welfare through improved wages, working hours, and conditions can boost job satisfaction and productivity. Despite companies striving to implement policies that satisfy their employees, inconsistent implementation and a lack of accountability often limit the effectiveness of such initiatives. Strategic employment policies can enhance the firms' reputation among employees, leading to higher employee engagement and ultimately improving business performance. Additional CSR measures include charitable activities and volunteering. Despite their infrequent implementation, these initiatives can still be beneficial in fostering strong community relationships while enhancing the company's image. Philanthropic efforts are often

employed when a company seeks to create immediate positive change. However, charitable and volunteering activities rarely provide long-term benefits compared to environmental conservation or educational programmes; thus, their overall impact may be limited.

The second objective examined essential CSR policies that can positively impact business profitability and brand image. The results show that CSR policies influence business profitability and brand image in the South Asian garment industry. Typically, CSR activities address societal issues, enhance financial revenue by building a favourable public image, help retain customers, and increase internal effectiveness. CSR policies include environmental, labour rights, education and community, and governance policies. The most critical policy in any firm is the environmentally sustainable policy. Environmentally conscious consumers opt for companies with organisational policies to reduce waste and increase recycling. Awareness of climate change and environmental pollution encourages consumers to prefer products and services from environmentally responsible businesses. Firms that adopt environmental management principles distinguish themselves from their competitors, eventually improving their market share and customer loyalty. Companies that ignore environmental sustainability in CSR risk losing in newer business areas where consumers make principle-based choices. Another significant CSR policy that affects companies' image and income relates to labour relations and wage equity. Organisations that continuously implement fair remunerations, safety measures, and employee welfare experience high employee productivity and satisfaction, reducing labour strikes and turnover that is unprofitable for companies. Companies that adhere to industry best practises attract a reputation for ethical treatment of employees and society. Today, purchasing managers are conscious about the products produced while ensuring fair labour practises to secure consumers with ethical trends. Excluding labour rights from CSR strategies threatens

competitive advantage and brand loyalty. Businesses can manage terms with increased public backing, which may handle specific operational and regulatory issues. Moreover, community development and education programmes can be designed to meet long-term organisational goals, such as preparing the workforce for higher social and economic returns. The implication suggests that effective oversight is vital for developing or implementing CSR policies, even when companies' general administration is transparent.

The third objective examined the relationship between CSR and profitability by assessing customer purchase patterns. CSR provides a vital link between the South Asian garments business and profitability through its influence on customer buying behaviour. Consumers of this sector are sensitive to CSR activities and their relationship to the ethical mandate of business, eventually impacting their buying behaviour. Additionally, a poor CSR history does not affect purchasing behaviour, affirming a certain degree of customer loyalty even where CSR is rated low. However, clients are willing to change their consumption behaviour when they encounter poor CSR practises, thus highlighting a critical risk to companies that neglect CSR responsibilities. CSR influences customer loyalty and brand preferences. Customers select product quality over price in their preferred brands, thus proving that ethical CSR practises, which maintain product quality through fair treatment of employees and environmentally friendly production create a competitive edge. Consumers from this sector expect corporations to link core and employment-related CSR issues, such as remuneration of workers and decent working conditions, with product quality. Garment manufacturers that embrace CSR will improve their brand image, gain sustainable customer loyalty, and enhance profitability. CSR is a component that adds value to a company's reputation and is a significant determinant of customer loyalty and profitability compared to other industries. Firms that behave ethically in

their operations and engage stakeholders in CSR achieve better returns. When consumers become aware of CSR, those companies without responsible accountability lose their market share to socially responsive competitors.

The fourth objective examined how CSR helps in developing society and community. The results showed that CSR is essential in developing society and communities in the South Asian garment sector. The findings show that CSR initiatives that are appropriately implemented directly enhance the quality of life and education of workers and their families. The garment sector is traditionally susceptible to employment issues. Most CSR activities in this field aim to improve the working environment over and above legal requirements to create better working conditions for employees. Strategic areas of social responsibility are significant areas where CSR provides sustainable social value. CSR programmes targeting labour, like better wages, help eradicate poverty and empower employees more than other sectors in developing nations. CSR practises in the South Asian garment industry educate and train employees who contribute to societal growth. CSR programmes enable people to get information and skills vital for evading poverty. By ensuring a better education, companies build a sustainable economic environment for the communities in which these firms operate. Environmental sustainability programmes are essential for regional ecological problems. Companies' initiatives of minimising pollution and becoming environmentally friendly improve society's health and safety, enhance corporate image, and contribute to the common welfare of society. Companies in the South Asian garment sector are committed to volunteering and charity work, including offering to build schools, hospitals, and community halls. These efforts positively influence the population's quality of life and reduce social injustice. Charitable events such as infrastructure development promote social cohesion and empower the community. Significant considerations are made from this study.

Through CSR, companies that invest in CSR add value to economic growth by enhancing living standards, ensuring a better-educated populace, and ensuring environmental conservation.

7.3. Recommendations

The results provide insight into the need to develop knowledge of the strategies for enhancing CSR implementation, fine-tuning the managerial approaches to achieving competitive advantage, and broadening the understanding of the role of CSR as to its impact on society and the business. CSR should become a part of the business strategic plans. If well-coordinated with organisational values and processes, CSR activities increase brand image, customer loyalty, and profitability. In general, CSR needs to be an integrated approach for businesses operating in the garment industry to ensure sustainable practice and positive performance. CSR is essential in the garment industry since it has many impacts on the environment and society. The sector involves the use of many resources, high carbon emission, use of complex supply chain systems, and sometimes social issues such as labour rights. By using the stakeholder approach this way, organisations can foster both the company's benefit and societal benefit. Therefore, there is a need to incorporate an inclusive company-level CSR strategy that constantly assesses the profitability of CSR initiatives without compromise to deliver value to the company and society. Future studies should also analyse how various industries embed CSR into their strategic management and impact business performance and market dynamism.

Secondly, there is a requirement for organisations to increase the visibility and exchange of info regarding CSR initiatives as they affect consumer credibility and organisational gain. The findings indicate the connection between effectively implemented CSR strategies and clients' purchasing behaviours; clients prefer to engage with brands advocating for ethical causes. Managers should pay special attention to the disclosure of CSR messages through various

platforms, including the firm's website, social networks, and sustainability reports. To a degree, this approach will simplify the consumers' decision-making process regarding the choice of product, and at the same time, it will establish trust between a customer and the business, a crucial factor for customer retention and ultimately high profitability. Thus, there is a need for future work to investigate the extent of using digital platforms in communicating CSR activities and the effect of transparency on consumer choices in various spheres. As such, such studies can identify how companies can use technology to enhance the awareness and effectiveness of CSR programmes.

Thirdly, there is a need to focus on the effects of CSR on the other internal stakeholders. The study proves that CSR impacts consumers and employees. Individuals want to work for ethical and socially responsible companies because employment has better prospects. Trends in the garment industry show that employees demand organisations to act with integrity, pay fair wages, and conserve the environment. CSR can also enhance the internal environment and operational effectiveness. From this perspective, further studies should explore the effect of CSR on employee performance, level of satisfaction and turnover intention of the employees within various organisations. This way, it can reveal how the CSR approach may be further refined to enable the business to engage the employees and improve organisational performance. Future scholars should assess CSR outcomes from a social point of view, particularly the long-term impact on society. In the garment industry, CSR relates to labour relations and community results in the global economic development, education, and overall social welfare of the people in communities. The CSR contribution to sustainable development goals and economic growth requires future studies to consider longitudinal research designs in vulnerable areas. When CSR is viewed through a social perspective, firms can define effective interventions that positively

contribute to the communities in which they operate and improve their global reputation as socially responsible business organisations.

7.4. Implications of the Findings

The study brings profound implications for businesses. Firms that embrace the appropriate CSR practises, including employment relations and environmental conservation, have a better brand reputations and customer loyalty. They also foster competitive positioning of socially responsible brands against other brands and enhance profitability by high and favourable consumer perception and buying behaviour. This research also establishes that CSR activities can repair and solidify stakeholder relationships while benefiting society. However, organisations that have not embedded their CSR policies with genuine ethical responsibilities may face performance since customers and other stakeholders are selective about organisations implementing CSR initiatives.

The recommendations in this research are based on the findings and the unique context of CSR in the South Asian garment sector. The results indicate the links between labour conditions and CSR disclosure and increased customer loyalty and reputation. Hence, the recommendations that are moot for ethical practises, welfare for employees, and community development correspond with the research findings. Although standard directions, such as the enhancement of environmental literacy, can be applied to many fields, which is why some of the analysed recommendations have sectoral and universal characteristics, the proposed guidelines are concrete and feasible for the studied field.

The study expands the knowledge of CSR as a competitive advantage by illustrating its influence on customer buying behaviour, brand image, and firm profitability. The outcomes show that every CSR undertaken directly impacts customer behaviours since consumers are

inclined to socially and ethically responsive businesses. Secondly, the research fills the gap in the knowledge about CSR and its effects on employees as internal stakeholders and consumers and communities. The author offers a practical insight into how CSR initiatives, especially those revolving around labour relations, ethical purchase, and environmentalism, can enhance employee satisfaction/retention and staff performance. CSR has a dual impact, including improving consumer recognition from outside the organisation and the internal employees/working population. Thirdly, the research provides knowledge of the effects of CSR in society. Taking CSR's contributions to enhance labour standards and advance community well-being into consideration, the general societal considerations of CSR undertakings were discussed in the research. The findings are crucial for policymakers and firms in developing nations as they support the view that CSR fosters sustainable development goals in developing countries and uplifts citizens' well-being. In addition, the study offers suggestions for further research by outlining areas in which theory and evidence are currently lacking and investigating how CSR will affect enterprises and society in the future. This study sanctions qualitative investigation of how CSR practises change with time across industries and geographical regions, leaving room for future scholars to advance on these assertions as the discourse on CSR in modern business continues to grow.

7.5. Limitation of the Research

The degree of generalising the findings depends on the circumstances of the research. Even though the study centres on CSR policies and their influence on society in the South Asian garment sector, the conclusions may be justifiable in similar industries and subjected to comparable economic, social, and rules and regulations. The results could not be easily transferable to other sectors or regions with different market structures, employee relations or

treatment, and cultural perceptions towards CSR. Thus, the conclusions are hardly refutable because of the mixed research approach and qualitative and quantitative data. Such methodological protocols argue resilience in asserting CSR's capacity to reshape customer behaviours, stakeholder loyalty and profitability. However, future studies for external validity should follow up and confirm these findings across different industries and countries to account for other socio-economic legal factors. Therefore, even though making a coherent argument as such, generalisation beyond the scope of the arguments and objectives of the study would call for further research.

Although this work provides a good foundation for understanding CSR and its relevant impacts on various organisational performances, it has the following limitations. First, combining data from the two methods may cause marginalisation of substance in either method being used qualitatively or quantitatively. Future research could consider mixed methods with the qualitative and quantitative components used sequentially. Consequently, the qualitative results inform the quantitative study, allowing enhanced investigation of both procedures. Secondly, sample size and representativeness can be considered as the existing limitations. However, the findings of this research are based on only 257 respondents, although it provides fair sample data to be generalised on the garment sector-related South Asian countries only. Future studies should extend the research coverage to many sectors and compare regions. However, it would be good to work with a more extensive and diversified sample of the population to arrive at better control and accuracy in the result. Thirdly, self-reporting bias could be evident when conducting qualitative interviews and quantitative surveys. The findings can be inflated or deflated because respondents may offer socially acceptable responses, especially concerning CSR issues. This issue can be prevented using other anonymous methods of data

collection or by comparing the respondent's subjective with objective data in corporate financial performances and third-party CSR ratings.

7.6. Conclusion

CSR adoption and implementation in South Asian garment industries remains sparse and mainly driven by regulatory forces and economic necessities. Given vast differences between social and business environments in South Asia, it is necessary to balance between global requirements and local conditions. An effective CSR policy should be grounded in the context of South Asian macro and microenvironments. South Asian Garment organisations have immense potential to adopt a CSR orientation in their business policy and activities. These policies are beneficial for both business and society. South Asian organisations must develop a strategic plan based on the ideals of sustainable development by conducting a thorough analysis of the internal and external environment and identifying opportunities and threats. It is the responsibility of South Asian governments to develop a strict regulatory framework to ensure that all enterprises comply with their CSR duties and obligations. This would help minimise the negative impact of business activities on the environment and society. From the primary analysis, it has been found that many managers lack clarity about the rules and regulations associated with CSR activities. South Asian garment companies need to forge partnerships with global organisations to create awareness about the importance of CSR on business performance. The research has also highlighted the need for South Asian companies to embrace corporate governance by developing mechanisms of verification that can deter any behaviour that goes against CSR principles.

The study ascertained that CSR could also positively impact communities. However, future studies should determine whether CSR improvements are sustainable and whether communities' living conditions, education, and health status are significantly improved. South

Asian CSR should be relevant to local needs, addressing issues like labour practises, gender equality, and the environment. The private sector, governments, and non-government organisations should enhance their partnership in the advancement of CSR in South Asia. This approach will enable the stakeholders to create a conducive environment for the practice of CSR, ensuring its outcomes address the general objective of sustainable development. The efforts will entail establishing laws and guidelines that support corporations in acting appropriately in society and offering rewards to employees. CSR can drive societal development in South Asia. The study findings showed that the region's companies willingly implement CSR practises to improve living standards, education, and the environment. For CSR to achieve its full potential, companies must embrace more radical strategies that engage with communities at the local level. This will enhance business profitability and brand image in South Asia and bring societal development in the long term. The core CSR policies of labour conditions, environment and community have significant implications for the business and brand in the South Asian garment industry. However, CSR does not necessarily have an automatic link with profitability as this can be an inverse depending on market trends and consumer opinions regarding CSR activities. Businesses must undertake a strategic view of CSR that integrates business policies to the expectations of its stakeholders and the peculiarities of its industry.

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Appendices

Appendix 1. Survey and interview questions

Survey questionnaire

Topic: CSR from Theory to Practice, a Distinguish between CSR as a Brand Image or a Contribution to Society

1-Are you aware of CSR concept?

Yes

No

2-Would you avoid buying products of a brand that is known to have a poor CSR history?

Yes

No

3-Are you aware of your favourite retail brand's history in operating in the past few years?

Yes

No

4-Would a brand with poor CSR history influence your purchasing?

Yes

No

5-On what basis do you choose your favourite brand?

Competitive prices

Product quality

Brand name

6- What type of CSR activities according to you is most effective?

- Educational support
- Support to refugees
- Support to the homeless and disadvantaged individuals

7-If you are made aware that your favourite brand has poor CSR and reputation, would this information change your attitude towards the brand?

- I will have the same attitude
- I will change my attitude
- Not sure

8- Would you consider paying extra for a product if retailer guarantees good work conditions and fair wages to factory workers?

- I would pay extra
- Retailer should reduce their profit

9- Select one of the following factors that you consider to be most important for making purchase decision?

- Price of product
- Retailer reputation
- CSR reputation
- Quality of product

10- What are the most important reasons for companies to get involved in CSR activities in your opinion?

- To Improve image of a company

To help society and environment

To attract customers' attention

To increase income

11- What is/are the most common CSR activity/activities of companies you have been exposed to?

Charitable event

Volunteering in the community

Environmental awareness activities

Sponsoring education, community and social development program

Appropriate employee recruitment and retention practices

12-Do you think brands with effective CRS activities are more prone to provide you with higher quality of product or services?

Yes

No

Maybe

13-Do you think all brands have a CSR committee on their Board?

Yes

No

Maybe

14-Are there transparent and effective monitoring mechanisms?

No

Poor mechanism

Acceptable mechanism

Strong mechanism

15- How important is it for you that companies implement socially responsible practices?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

16-What influence does CSR reputation have on your purchasing behaviour?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

17- How important is creating marketing campaigns that are ethical and contribute to social and environmental sustainability?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

18- How important is working with manufacturers that value diversity and good working conditions?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

19- How important is pay equity (making sure the employees are paid equally for equal work)?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

20- Is competitive price the main factor when purchasing clothing products?

Strongly agree

Agree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

21- Is product quality more important than price when deciding on buying products?

Strongly agree

Agree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

22- I buy from the same brand despite high prices or average quality.

Strongly agree

Agree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

23- I choose to buy products from brands that have good reputations and value their community.

Strongly Agree

Agree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

24- I avoid buying products from brands with poor reputation despite their low prices.

Strongly agree

Agree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

25. Is the word "Fair Trade" familiar to you?

Yes

No

Appendix 2. Interview questions

1. How do you as the manager of the company, perceive CSR?
2. What according to you, are some of the major benefits of opting for CSR activities for your organisation?
3. What according to you is the impact of the CSR policies on the society?
4. What are some of the key influential CSR policies and activities that have proven to be highly beneficial both for the society and for the organisation?
5. What as per you, are some of the major challenges faced by your company while adopting and implementing an ethical CSR approach?
6. What is your opinion on implementing CSR policies is their clarity on laws and tax regulations?
7. Do local communities participate in the CSR activities?
8. Does a third-party audit on the CSR Policies improve the implementation methods?
9. Monitoring CSR activities and liaising with NGOs does it really deliver the desired outcomes?
10. Does the CSR committee monitor and evaluate the CSR policies periodically?

Appendix 3. Interview Transcripts

Participant 1

1. How do you as the manager of the company, perceive CSR?

In my view as a manager and a student of business, I see CSR as a critical component of doing business in today's world. What used to be known simply as the bottom line is no longer enough for corporate America; modern organisations must combine the dollar with the public good.

2. What according to you, are some of the major benefits of opting for CSR activities for your organisation?

Also, CSR activities have many advantages for our organisation. Firstly, it improves brand identity and brand image. Today, consumers are not only concerned about the quality of what they are buying but also interested to know whether the owning company organisation has similar feelings with them concerning certain socially responsible issues. CSR empowers customers to take chance.

3. What, according to you, is the impact of CSR policies on society?

As for the effects of implemented CSR policies on society, they can be rather revelatory. On the same note, through concerns of community, education and environment the company is able to give back to society by supporting its operations in the various societies it finds itself.

4. What are some of the key influential CSR policies and activities that have proven to be highly beneficial both for society and for the organisation?

The CSR activity that may be highly influential is the environmental sustainability program that aims at cutting the use of plastics and encouraging recycling both at the company's premises and in the broader community. CSR enables us to set a niche. Consumers today tend to purchase from socially responsible companies and contribute to society.

5 What are some of the major challenges faced by your company while adopting and implementing an ethical CSR approach?

Here are some of the difficulties that define our path to the ethical CSR approach's adoption and implementation. Employing CSR strategies and programmes is, however, costly in many cases, and the costs can be incurred in the short run.

6. On Implementing CSR Policies is their clarity on Laws and tax regulations

A little more remains understandable regarding the laws and tax procedures concerning CSR; however, it is still confusing. However, the relevant regulations are not very clear, and sometimes when we are implementing them, especially on matters concerning compliance, we seek legal advice.

7. Do local community activities participate in the CSR activities?

In our organisation, local community participation is very important lest the CSR activities be unsuccessful. This changed last year and currently, we have been operating a vocational training for youth, especially women to enable the youths to join the job market.

8. Does a third-party audit on the CSR Policies improve the implementation methods?

The CSR policies get a great boost from having third-party audits on their implementing methods. External audits help us know whether the specific CSR programmes that are being implemented are relevant and meet the required level of performance.

9. Does monitoring CSR activities and liaising with NGOs really deliver the desired outcomes?

Absolutely. This helps us to keep check on most of our CSR activities and our interaction with most of the NGOs to make sure that the intended objectives are met.

10. Does the CSR committee monitor and evaluate the CSR policies periodically?

For this purpose, we have a well-composed CSR committee that is responsible for the regular evaluation of our CSR policies. This evaluation assists in indicating the level of success in CSR undertakings and guarantees that objectives are accomplished.

Participant 2

1. How do you as the manager of the company, perceive CSR?

Mmm... CSR, you know what it is; it is just part and parcel of our business development. It is the right thing to do for the community and the environment while at the same time making it an organisational advantage.

2. What, in your opinion, are some of the major benefits of opting for CSR activities for your organisation?

First, CSR increases our organisation's reputation. Today's customers are very selective about where they are spending their hard-earned money. CSR is not a cost; it's an investment. Therefore, when they notice that we are responsible and have embraced the various social causes, they are more loyal.

3. What, according to you, is the impact of CSR policies on society?

CSR policies, if done in the right manner, can have a very positive effect. We have constructed schools and have ensured the provision of clean water to those in the neighbouring villages to our industries. From our company's CSR calendar, we undertake to construct schools, roads, and health centres.

4. What are some of the key influential CSR policies and activities that have proven to be highly beneficial both for the society and for the organisation?

I would classify key ones as education sponsorships and environmental conservation as the most effective ones.

5. What as per you, are some of the major challenges faced by your company while adopting and implementing an ethical CSR approach?

Well, you know what they say, smooth seas do not make good sailors, but stormy waters also make a good sailor. One of the significant problems is that costs must always be controlled.

6. On Implementing CSR Policies, is there clarity on Laws and tax regulations?

Okay. There is a fair degree of certainty concerning laws and taxes though I would not go as far as saying that it is cut and dried.

7. Do local community activities participate in the CSR activities?

Indeed, the local community is involved. Perhaps, the reason for community engagement in any CSR project is because members of society will benefit from it. In terms of how audiences engage with it, we've seen a lot of positive receptions, particularly with our educational programmes and with our environmental work.

8. Does a third-party audit on the CSR Policies improve the implementation methods?

Yes, in my opinion, third-party audits are relatively useful. They come from outside our system and help us make sure that we are achieving on par with our objectives.

9. Does monitoring CSR activities and liaising with NGOs deliver the desired outcomes?

Oh, yes, it does in many circumstances I suppose. In general, it could be argued that NGOs usually have knowledge and data not available to us, as a business.

10. Does the CSR committee monitor and evaluate the CSR policies periodically?

Yes, our CSR committee is very important because it oversees the evaluation of our policies.

Participant 3

1. What perception do you have towards CSR as the manager of the company?

CSR for me is really about accountability for more than just revenues. In that sense it can also help to be an effective manager in helping to support the local populace while simultaneously improving the company's image.

2. What according to you, are some of the major benefits of opting for CSR activities for your organisation?

Of course, the advantages are seen very clearly. Implementing CSR has helped improve the view that customers have about our brand we are seen as ethical, and this is critical in the current business environment. Our CSR in sustainability has given us windows to new markets, especially those in the European region that are very much conscious of conservation of environment, we would have lost good opportunities had we not adopted CSR.

3. What, according to you, is the impact of CSR policies on society?

Okay, I think the impact is complex. The CSR instrument can focus on enhancing the living standard of people in a specific area by investment in educational services, health, or environmental protection.

4. What are some of the key influential CSR policies and activities that have proven to be highly beneficial both for the society and for the organisation?

Sorry to say, but we've had positive experiences; thus, environmental initiatives are not so bad. We have engaged in recycling processes and wastage minimisation initiatives, and such are of benefits to the natural setting besides saving cost within the firm.

5. What as per you, are some of the major challenges faced by your company while adopting and implementing an ethical CSR approach?

Actually, there are some difficulties out there. One big one is the cost. Sometimes, it will be challenging to persuade shareholders or top management that this cost will help the firm in the future. CSR are just 'window-dressing activities.

6. On Implementing CSR Policies, is there clarity on Laws and tax regulations?

"Honestly, not always. Still, the issue of whether CSR spending is fully comprehensible from the tax angle remains unclear, at least within our area. Some laws are clear about one thing, but when it comes to how they are to be interpreted—there is some leeway.

7. Do the local community participate in CSR activities?

Yes, they do, but this depends on the initiative being undertaken. For instance, our campaigns on environmental conservation, such as tree planting or cleaning up of the environment, receive a lot of public support. Via CSR programmes, our firm works through supporting local schools, scholarship programmes, and training teachers. The activities solve long-term social problems by giving people knowledge. Education brings change to a community's welfare.

8. Does a third-party audit on the CSR Policies improve the implementation methods?

"Definitely. Third-party audits are independent, and that is critical because they offer a first-party perspective; thus, we can figure out where the firm makes a significant impact and where it barely scrapes the surface.

9. Monitoring CSR activities and liaising with NGOs does it really deliver the desired outcomes?

Yes, I agree with you, but it depends on how one is done. Being only an observer is not allowed. Certainly, getting in touch with NGOs is useful because they have knowledge and experience helpful in the given country.

10. Does the CSR committee monitor and evaluate the CSR policies periodically?

Oh yes, we have specific CSR activities that we embark on throughout the year, we sit down on a quarterly basis to check whether we are on track with the targets set. Customers view us as more ethical.

Participant 4

1. How do you as the manager of the company, perceive CSR?

I consider CSR not only a set of obligations but a social activity that is tightly connected to the company's functioning.

2. What according to you, are some of the major benefits of opting for CSR activities for your organisation?

Of course, CSR does have some actual material advantages for the organisation. First, there is the rights' reputational effect. CSR has assisted us in avoiding risks by especially adopting sustainable practises which help us avoid penalties and fines that would have cost us a lot of money in the long run.

3. What, according to you, is the impact of CSR policies on society?

Alright, CSR has several effects on the society. For instance, our educational sponsorship programmes facilitate the overall enhancement of literacy in the societies we find ourselves.

While people are today interested in knowing how we handle CSR before investing, it shows that investors are interested in how we handle CSR than ever before.

4. What are the key influential CSR policies and activities that have proven to be highly beneficial both for the society and the organisation?

Both ways, it has proved quite effective – on one side such youths get their way to a better future along with a better chance in the community. This not only benefits the physical environment but

also finds new avenues for the economic resources of the community, and thus, it is possible to successfully foster two facets of a community: the ecological and the economic.

5. What are some of the major challenges faced by your company while adopting and implementing an ethical CSR approach, according to you?

Yeah, actually carrying out an ethical CSR practice is not always a walk in the park I must concede. Unfortunately, one of the main issues is the cost.

6. On Implementing CSR Policies is their clarity on Laws and tax regulations

Yes, there has been confusion concerning the laws and tax regulations quite honestly, we've had some minor issues there. It may be clear that CSR exists, and that there are recommendations on how much money businesses should spend and on what kind.

7. Do local community activities participate in the CSR activities?

Yes, of course, we involve the local community in many of our CSR activities, particularly those oriented towards education and environmental conservation.

8. Does a third-party audit on the CSR Policies improve the implementation methods

To have a third-party audit is a big plus because one finds it difficult to be impartial, and impartiality is essential so that we are not just chasing our tails and claiming that we are changing the world.

9. Monitoring CSR activities and liaising with NGOs does it really deliver the desired outcomes?

Yes, it does, but as far as I am concerned, it has its own complications. Cooperation with NGOs is important because sometimes they are better equipped and more credible than we are.

10. Does the CSR committee monitor and evaluate the CSR policies periodically?

Yeah, you are correct. The CSR committee is responsible for regularly evaluating and monitoring the policies on a frequency basis.

Participant 5

1. How do you, as the manager of the company, interpret CSR?

CSR is, for us not simply an issue of charitable giving and suchlike. It's a significant part of how we operate in the firm. And we view it as a duty for our employees, to the community, and to the environment as well.

2. In your opinion, what are the biggest advantages of choosing CSR activities for your organisation?

Yes, indeed, there are. I also agree with the point that it enhances relationships with local stakeholders. Sure. Since consumers and stakeholders trust organisations that are environmentally sensitive, we are always committed to such initiatives to create a positive image.

3. In your opinion, how do the CSR policies affect society?

CSR policies do not cause significant positive changes in society at all. Well...Through recycling programmes, we have been able to minimise wastage and encourage the conservation of the environment among the people.

4. It is high time to mention some of the highly effective CSR policies and activities that may gain a great influence according to their benefits for society and the organisation.

Well, one of the best examples of CSR may have been based on improving the environment and education systems.

5. In your opinion, what were the main difficulties your organisation faced while incorporating and practising ethical CSR?

Oh, surely there are challenges there, I can tell you. One of the greatest challenges is managing the cost of CSR with the business organisation's short-term objectives. Sometimes, there are

very high initial costs which are often associated with themes such as sustainable supply chain management.

6. When, for example, a company begins a CSR policy, does it know the legislation and tax regulations?

Oh, well, the laws and tax regulations are not entirely clear anyway sometimes, if you'll pardon my honesty. Of course, there are even some specific, clearly stated advantages in some locations, such as tax deductions for CSR costs, but the rules can vary.

7. Are there engagements of the local community in the CSR activities?

It's funny you asked that question because, yes, the local community is quite directly engaged in our CSR. Ah, well, most of the time, we cooperate with the local schools, NGOs, and other community-based organisations to determine where we are likely to be of most help.

8. To what extent does the third-party audit enhance the implementation methods of the CSR policies?

When undertaking proper CSR strategies, such consumers feel that you are not driven by the green aspect but by the welfare of their needs. Hence, customers provide you with their loyalty, which, in the long run, is very profitable.

9. Is it working in terms of the impact observed for CSR monitoring and NGOs' cooperation?

Hmm... yeah, I believe so. There has been a good relationship with NGOs, which have been useful in providing checks and balances on our CSR initiatives.

10. Does the CSR committee review the CSR policies to check whether they are still effective?

Yes, it is! Here, the CSR committee exercises its significant duty; they sit at least quarterly to chip away and assess our progress, analyse the impact of our programmes and make the right changes where necessary.

Participant 6

1. As the manager of the company, what is your view on CSR?

These outweighed the perceived weakness in that I view CSR as an imperative element of business in the current world. In my view CSR means that our business operations are conducted in a responsible manner for the benefit of our own company and society in which we are located.

2. In your opinion, what would be some of the most significant advantages for your organisation when choosing CSR activities?

The company has taken the lead to embrace ethical practises for its operations and this has brought about a better quality of employee. People want to work with a company that reflects their culture. CSR makes our employees feel motivated and valued when they are part of a company that is socially responsible.

3. In your opinion, how do CSR policies affect society?

I think that CSR does something good for society. It makes them more aware and makes them do things they perhaps they wouldn't have done otherwise.

4. What are some of the most significant and effective CSR policies and activities that exhibit greater influence in society and the organisation?

Let me recall that one of the most popular ones is our green policies, starting with fighting waste and ending with the rational use of energy. Of course, it's beneficial for the Earth and also allows us to save some money.

5. There are invariably some significant difficult visited to your organisation when implementing an ethical CSR practice, in your opinion what are some of them?

Yeah... there are of course some that are hurdles especially when it comes to issues to do with costs.

6. When implementing CSR policies, is there a clear understanding of laws and regulations of taxes?

Well... it's good and bad, I guess. On one hand, CSR is regulated by laws and regulations, most especially when relating to taxes or taxation. This begs the question of why there isn't a clear set of rules so that enterprises will be aware of what they can and cannot do and hence avoid getting into legal zones that are often grey.

7. Does the local community engage in CSR activities?

On the contrary, parochial participation plays an important role in us. Whenever we conduct a CSR project, whether it is the cleanup of the environment or any educational exercise, we always involve the community.

8. Does the third-party audit increase the degree of extensivity of the implementation methods of the CSR policies?

Absolutely. So, when you have a third-party audit, it comes with a sense of impartiality, does it not? The value of having a fresh perspective is often outstanding because you begin to realise where changes are required when you have been engrossed in a project for a length of time.

9. CSR work and how the companies engage with the NGOs – is it effective in achieving the expected objectives?

Umm, yes, I'd say so. It's generally the case that NGOs are closer to the problem and have knowledge that we, as a corporation, may lack. The monitoring is essential – without it, the resources invested in the endeavour are not guaranteed to have an impact.

10. Is the CSR committee then responsible to either monitor or at specific intervals check on the CSR policies?

Oh, definitely. Our CSR committee sits from time to time to assess the policies and the efficiency of the undertakings. CSR cannot be fixed in concrete because it has to grow and develop to meet new demands of society and business.

Participant 7

1. As the manager of the company, what is your view on CSR?

I believe that CSR is a very significant aspect of operations for any organisation in the market. It is not just about regulations, standards, and performing something because we must; it is more about paying back to society.

2. Please provide a list of the key plausible advantages of choosing CSR for your organisation.

I will admit that it improves our brand image or at least that it can do so depending on the context and the nature of the advertising message. CSR has a positive image, especially when it comes to local community involvement, and there is a direct relation between our organisation's promotion of CSR and increased traffic at our stores. Customers trust us because they can understand that we are working to be more than just making profits for them. On this aspect of trust, the customers remain loyal to our brand for a long time.

3. In your opinion, how does the implementation of CSR policies affect society?

Well, to my mind CSR policies can bring a great change in society. For instance, when we target programmes in the environment, we are working towards achieving a cleaner environment.

4. Which influential CSR policies and activities can be considered rather useful for society and the organisation?

Our environment awareness campaigns were always very effective ones. They assist the community in adopting environmentally friendly practises and, at the same time, the agenda shows that we as a company also care for the environment, hence enhancing our image.

Furthermore, sponsoring educational programmes has been a mutual gain. And I think our policies regarding fair wages and a good working environment bear fruit in fixing the morale and motivating others.

5. In your opinion, what are some of the key difficulties your firm faces when implementing an ethical CSR strategy?

Well, I believe that one of the larger issues is the ability to keep costs in check. There is also another problem of how to guarantee that these projects are effective and not just a façade. The problem is that sometimes there is no clear definition of what can make a CSR initiative ethical, and this is sometimes a challenge.

6. When CSR policies are implemented, is there certainty in the laws and the tax regime?

I would say a degree of clarity is often needed but rarely provided fully. Tax laws are quite sensitive as they pertain to CSR expenditures and initiatives. Sometimes, they may not be written or fluctuate, so consulting professionals may question whether you are fully legal.

7. Do local community activities participate in the CSR activities?

Yes, they do so, for the most part. There are slight differences. We always strive to get the community to participate as much as possible in environmental or social issues activities. Yes, their participation just really enhances the accomplishment.

8. Does a third-party audit on the CSR Policies enhance implementation methods?

Oh, absolutely. An external audit introduces an outsider's perspective, which may help managers identify successful and unsuccessful processes. Moreover, it helps to avoid the situation when organisations check the corresponding boxes but do not make a positive impact.

9. Does a third-party audit on the CSR Policies improve the implementation methods?

I believe it does. It is effective because it allows us to connect with the right people through the NGOs. They complement us by providing something that we may not have internally, so our action plans are more effective.

10. Is the CSR committee required to perform periodic assessments of the CSR policies?

Yes. The company has a CSR committee which convenes on a regular basis to consider the stated policies and determine whether the company is on target with the objectives set in place.

Participant 8

1. What perception does the manager of the company have about CSR?

As a manager, I see CSR as a useful tool for the organisation in achieving its goals and objectives. It is more than a matter of recapturing social value; however, it also means making investments for the long term, both for the business and society.

2. In your opinion, could you outline some of the most important advantages you can reap from CSR activities for your organisation?

First, it facilitates the build-up of a stronger brand image. People want to be related to companies that are responsible and ethical in everything they do. Our suppliers and partners want to work with companies that have a well-developed CSR profile.

3. In your opinion, how do CSR policies affect society?

Mmm, the impact is enormous. With socially responsible policies in place, we are supporting communities, keeping both environmental and ethical implications to a minimum and ensuring fair treatment of workers.

4. What are the most important influential CSR policies and activities which are highly beneficial for society as well as for the organisation?

One of the main goals of the company's CSR is to fight poverty. We operate and support community programmes that offer financial support, food, and education to families living in poverty. Another aspect of our CSR plan is to lift people out of poverty, and we organise community development programmes, including offering cash and food handouts and scholarships to needy families.

5. According to you, what are some of the largest difficulties your company faces while conducting and enforcing ethical CSR policy?

There are quite a few challenges, I would say. One of the most significant challenges it comes with is the cost. There's also the problem of project sponsorship – getting all the stakeholders motivated for ethical practises; some may not be motivated at first. Although CSR is wonderful in concept, the truth of the matter is that here in our markets, consumers are always price-conscious to some extent, meaning that we cannot always afford the luxury of investing in expensive CSR programmes even if the returns are long-term in nature, not immediate.

6. Indeed, do these organisations clearly understand laws and tax regulations when implementing CSR policies?

Oh well, there is always a consultation with legal advisers to ensure that the company meets tax laws and regulations on CSR. The problem, however, arises when laws vary across regions across the country.

7. To what extent do local community activities engage in CSR activities?

For sure. The community is central to our approach to CSR. We often involve local chiefs and the people in designing and implementing these programmes.

8. To what extent do the implementation methods improve by having a third party conduct an audit on the CSR policies?

Absolutely. This means using third-party auditors who hold us accountable regarding CSR so that consumers can be assured that we are not making any false claims about our products.

9. Is there an optimal outcome in monitoring the CSR activities and interacting with the NGOs?

Working with the NGOs has, therefore, helped make sure that CSR is well delivered to deserving people.

10. Is the CSR committee able to track and review the policies that relate to CSR regularly?

Yes, I agree, the CSR committee is responsible for the periodical evaluation of the policies. They recall the promotion's implication, ensure that the laid objectives are achieved, and recommend changes, if any.

Participant 9

1. What roles do you think CSR plays in your company, as the manager of the company?

So for me, CSR is a way of donating. CSR is sometimes a myth; it means the company wants to create an impression that it is working for the society's development without doing so.

2. As per your knowledge, share some of the most important advantages that can be gained by choosing to incorporate CSR for your organisation?

CSR also has the impact of creating a favourable brand image for the implementation of the company. Also, customers are more likely to invest in companies that will demonstrate that they have a conscience of ethical conduct.

3. As far as potential benefits are concerned, what view do you have regarding CSR policies in your firm and their impact on society?

Oh, I do see you can try making a change towards something so that we can make people's quality of life better, and we can aim at environmental sustainability or education programmes. It extends beyond breaking a monetary donation for charitable purposes.

4. What are some of the outstanding influences of CSR policies and activities on society and organisations?

Okey... About us, sponsoring educational programmes and community development projects, for instance, has had a real positive impact. Local governments have been supportive because they find us significant players in societal advancement, thus providing many business prospects.

5. Where do you think are the major difficulties for your company whilst pursuing and implementing an ethical CSR strategy?

Most often, CSR is just a facade to get appreciation without trying to enhance society considerably. It is hard to quantify. Hey, look at the amount of money we made this quarter because of CSR. It's like a feel-good thing. It helps our image, but I do not think it is driving profitability.

6. When CSR policies are implemented: are there legal and tax certainty?

Mmm... not always. Now and again, it becomes a little cloudy as to where the laws and tax rules regarding CSR are. It also takes time to consult legal teams or external consultants to ensure we are doing the correct compliance.

7. Can local community activities also fund CSR activities?

Oh, absolutely. The community is usually very responsive, especially when the initiatives taken are in their perceived interest. This fosters a good relationship between the company and the community.

8. Is there an enhancement in the implementation methods through the third-party CSR audit on the policies?

Yeah, for sure. It is beneficial to have a third-party audit to help guide the process back on track if needed.

9. Scrutinising CSR activities and interacting with NGOS, does it help to achieve these results?

It depends. As we have seen, cooperating with NGOs may be very efficient because these organisations may know the communities' needs better.

10. Is it necessary for the CSR committee to follow and assess the CSR policies from time to time?

Yes, of course, we have. We perform our evaluations frequently. The CSR committee examines the short—and long-run consequences of the policies it implements regarding sustainable development.

Participant 10

1. What do you, as the company manager, think about CSR?

I will agree with you that with regards to CSR, I view it as a responsibility, right? And it is not a formal protocol performance or fulfilling a legal requirement. For me, it has more to do with contributing back to the society in which we operate.

2. In your opinion, what are some of the great advantages for your organisation to include CSR activities?

First, CSR activities cloud our corporate image. Customers do not want to be affiliated with business organisations that engage in unethical business practises. Second, productivity is increased through the promotion of disease awareness. Customers trust us more.

3. In your consideration, what is the CSR policies' effect on society?

CSR policies are known to possess far-reaching effects. For example, when we think of environmentally friendly practises, we are working towards the long-run health of the community. Furthermore, organizing sponsorship for educational programmes benefits underprivileged sectors of society.

4. What are the main CSR policies and activities highly effective for the benefit of society and the organisation?

It's a win-win, I'd say. One community project response our activities have positively impacted is job creation. Our community projects have helped increase employment opportunities for individuals in the areas of operation, and people are receptive to that.

5. According to you, what are the few significant issues that you think your company faced in adopting and employing an ethical CSR strategy?

Cost – The CSR program is costly. We tried implementing CSR initiatives, but the results were mixed. There was no clear link between our CSR activities and increased sales or profitability.

It's difficult to measure the direct impact, which makes it hard to justify the expense.

6. When companies initiate the implementation of CSR policies, are the legal and tax aspects of the countries understood?

Hmm... I'd say it's a mixed bag. While they can be straightforward, other regulations can be a little complicated to follow sometimes. There is a need for a lot of legal advice, and this may also be costly.

7. Within local communities, do they engage in CSR activities?

Yes, absolutely. Community participation is a very important aspect for us. We attempt to involve local leaders and various group figures in our projects so that the endeavours benefit them.

8. That is, does the third-party audit of the CSR policies enhance the implementation methods?

Yes, sometimes it's good to shake things up a bit so that you are grounded, and someone is keeping you accountable.

9. Regarding CSR activities and relationships with NGOs, does the monitoring assure positive outcomes?

Yes, most of the time. Working with NGOs, we can also draw on their experience and tools.

However, I think that though it will work, many follow-ups are needed.

10. Do the CSR committee track and assess the CSR policies from time to time?

Yes, we do that. The CSR committee meets every quarter to assess our position, and adaptations to strategies have been made accordingly.

Appendix 4 – Raw data

[CSR Original Data.xlsx](#)